

MOBILITY C3: A DIGITAL CARBON CALCULATOR FOR ACCURATE AND EFFICIENT MONITORING OF MOTOR VEHICLE CO₂ EMISSIONS

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Author Ricardo Braun
PhD, Project Developer

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Note

Mobility C3 is a deep tech spinoff of the Doctor Entrepreneur Program of the Carlos Chagas Filho Foundation for Research in the State of Rio de Janeiro (FAPERJ) in Brazil that provided funding to develop the Mobility C3 Project. The Project was incubated at the Brazilian National Laboratory for Scientific Computing (LNCC) of the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation (MCTI) from 2021 to 2024. This document is an original project report for FAPERJ that outlines the principal results achieved during the development of the Mobility C3 Project. The results presented in this document constitute a reference of the project's concept, technical innovation, achievements and research activities. Ongoing developments of the project and subsequent analyses are being used for a scientific manuscript for submission to a peer-reviewed journal. In this document some tables and graphs are in still the Portuguese language because they are being improved as part of the project's development.

Abstract

Extreme climate events are becoming increasingly frequent worldwide, highlighting the need for effective strategies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and mitigate their impacts. Carbon dioxide (CO₂), primarily generated through the combustion of fossil fuels by motor vehicles, is one of the most significant contributors to climate change. Globally, more than 1.4 billion vehicles are in operation, while Brazil alone has a fleet exceeding 120 million vehicles, most of which generate emissions without ecological compensation.

In addition, there are more than 1.4 million km² of degraded area in Brazil (MMA, 2012), which corresponds to four times the size of Germany. These areas should be replanted with trees to obtain environmental services such as CO₂ sequestration, O₂ (oxygen) emissions, and evapotranspiration (water to the atmosphere), among many other services (Constanza, et al., 1998). Carbon offset through tree planting, forest protection, and the trading of carbon credits represent viable and urgently needed measures to combat climate change and its impacts, in line with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 13 and 15.

The Mobility C3 (Carbon Car Calculator) Project was developed to address this challenge through the creation of an innovative digital platform designed for the carbon market. The platform integrates three core functions: measuring the distance traveled (km), calculating vehicle-specific CO₂ emissions based on vehicle characteristics and real-world operating conditions, and automatically determining the ecological compensation required through tree planting, forest conservation, or carbon credit acquisition. The project is aligned with the objectives of the Carlos Chagas Filho Research Foundation of the State of Rio de Janeiro (FAPERJ) Call No. 10/2021, Dr. Entrepreneur Program which seeks to transform research, development, and innovation into technology-based enterprises. We were incubated at the Incubator of the National Laboratory of Computer Science (LNCC/ MCTI).

Between 2021 and 2024, a series of laboratory and field studies were conducted using 13 light-duty vehicles. The research compared the Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Protocol, the most widely used carbon accounting standard, with the Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicles Test Procedure (WLTP) and the New European Driving Cycle (NEDC). Additional activities included proof-of-concept (PoC) testing, platform conceptualization, market research, carbon offset methodology development, and the establishment of forestry and commercial partnerships.

The results demonstrated that the WLTP and NEDC methodologies provide more accurate and economically efficient estimates of vehicle emissions than the GHG Protocol. Unlike the GHG approach, which relies primarily on generic fuel emission factors, WLTP and NEDC incorporate real driving emissions and multiple vehicle performance parameters, resulting in more precise

carbon accounting. These findings supported the development of the Mobility C3 mobile application, which operates using smartphone GPS technology without requiring dedicated vehicle tracking devices.

The entire development process included Proof of Concept (PoC) and Minimum Viable Product (MVP) stages, as well as laboratory and field measurements using light-duty motor vehicles. The results demonstrated that the calculation standards implemented in the backend of the Mobility C3 application are based on Real Driving Emissions (RDE) conditions and on methodologies established by United Nations Global Technical Regulations. These standards proved to be more comprehensive and effective than conventional methods derived from the GHG Protocol, positioning Mobility C3 as a potential game changer in the carbon market and providing a competitive advantage within the Brazilian carbon market.

The software development of the Mobility C3 was carried out by the team of the 11 Tech IT company that was contracted by the Project with resources from FAPERJ. In 2023, Mobility C3 became a deep tech startup that offers services for CO₂ monitoring of fleets of vehicles in the carbon market. The project successfully advanced from Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 5 to TRL 7, demonstrating strong potential for commercialization within the Brazilian and the international carbon market. Furthermore, strategic partnerships with carbon offset organizations and technology companies have strengthened its market viability and its potential contribution to climate mitigation and green job creation.

For this Mobility C3 has begun to established commercial partnerships with several carbon offsetting companies and organizations to strengthen its competitiveness within the Brazilian and the international carbon market. As a result, two initial strategic partnerships were formalized in June 2024: one with PRIMA, a Civil Society Organization of Public Interest (OSCIP) that has operated in the carbon market for more than 20 years, and another with 11 Tech, that has long experience in software development and geo-tracking.

With its innovative technology available directly through a mobile application and supported by partnerships with carbon offsetting companies and organizations, Mobility C3 represents a positive market-entry strategy as a climate-tech company with an active corporate registration and a proprietary digital technology platform. Nevertheless, further development is required to improve offline navigation capabilities in remote areas, develop a desktop-based management interface for both Mobility C3 administrators and fleet-management clients, and expand business opportunities and customer acquisition through its commercial partnerships.

This report submitted outlines the principal results achieved during the development of the Mobility C3 Project. The results presented herein constitute an initial account of the project's achievements and ongoing research activities. Future developments and subsequent analyses will underpin the preparation of a scientific manuscript for submission to a peer-reviewed journal.

- The Mobility C3 application was nominated for the Google Maps Platform Award 2025. <https://mapsplatform.google.com/awards/?nominee=mobility-c3>
- See the Mobility C3 page: <https://www.mobilidadec3.com/en>
- Watch the Mobility C3 0.1 demonstration video on **YouTube**. [Click here](#)

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1. INTRODUCTION

This document constitutes the Partial Technical Report as established under FAPERJ Call No. 10/2021. It describes the activities carried out during Phase 1 – Research and Technology Development of the Mobility C3 Project up to the tenth month of the fellowship period, including an evaluation of the results (R) achieved during this stage.

The project aims to develop a digital technology platform for commercialization within the emerging carbon market. The technology consists of a digital platform designed to monitor carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from motor vehicles, including the calculation of ecological carbon offsets, which will be implemented through commercial partners via tree planting, forest conservation, and carbon credit trading. These measures are intended to contribute to climate change mitigation and the reduction of its impacts, in accordance with Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 13 of the United Nations.

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is the most abundant greenhouse gas in urban areas due to the combustion of fossil fuels by motor vehicles (IPCC, 2014). In 2018, Brazil had a vehicle ownership rate of approximately 350 vehicles per thousand inhabitants, totaling more than 74.5 million vehicles of various categories, including buses, passenger cars, vans, and trucks (DENATRAN, 2019), with virtually no ecological carbon-offset mechanisms in place.

Research demonstrated that the CO₂ monitoring of fleet of vehicles requires improvement. We identified that certain applications and digital platforms in the carbon market that calculate CO₂ emissions of motor vehicles have limitations and may present inaccurate results that affects economic investments in carbon offsetting. Having said that the objective of this paper is to demonstrate that the CO₂ monitoring of light motor vehicles moved by fossil fuels can be technically improved to become more accurate for the carbon market. Based on research and laboratories with motor vehicles we were able to develop an innovative digital application called Mobility C3 (carbon car calculator) that measures remotely in realtime the distance travelled and the CO₂ emitted by each monitored vehicles. As described further our research and the application development contributes to improve knowledge and efficiency in the field of CO₂ monitoring of motor vehicles because it saves time and costs. The application was indicated for the Google Maps Platform Award 2025¹. To reach this point we first analyzed and tested the Green House Gas (GHG) Protocol (GHG Protocol, 2024; FGV, 2023) which is the most commonly used CO₂ standard in the market and tested it against two other CO₂ measuring methods: the Worldwide Harmonized Light Duty Test Procedure (WLTP) (United Nations, 2014) and New European Driving Cycle (NEDC) (Tsokolis et al, 2016) in order to analyze the efficiency of these methods.

The principal challenge faced by the project is the limited timeframe available for simultaneously developing the digital technology and designing strategies for its commercialization. Innovative digital technologies cannot be developed overnight; achieving excellence requires adequate resources, time, rigorous testing, and continuous refinement.

The project also experienced setbacks related to its Information Technology (IT) team, which hindered its progress and necessitated a formal request to FAPERJ for a six-month suspension of the fellowship. During the suspension period, research and development activities continued. Following the resumption of the project, all necessary steps were undertaken to advance the construction of the platform. The platform prototype was scheduled for completion in April 2023, after which final testing would be conducted prior to its market launch.

The methodology adopted in this report follows the IMRAD framework—Introduction, Methods, Results, and Discussion (Jacobs, 2022). The report comprises an Introduction and project

¹ In 2025 the Mobility C3 application was nominated for the Google Maps Platform Award. <https://mapsplatform.google.com/awards/?nominee=mobility-c3>

objectives, followed by a description of the multiple methods applied to each result (R) and project target, an analysis and discussion of the products and outcomes generated, and concludes with the reference bibliography.

In accordance with FAPERJ guidelines, the sources of verification related to project planning, evaluation procedures, digital technology development, graphs, tables, discussions, and commercial strategies are presented in Annexes I-1, I-2, I-3, I-4, I-5, and I-6. Evidence supporting the achievement of project results (targets) is presented in Annexes II-1, II-2, II-3, II-4, and II-5. The questionnaires developed and applied in the fields of information technology, forestry-based carbon offsetting, and corporate market research are presented in Annexes III-1, III-2, III-3, III-4, and III-5.

2. METHODOLOGY

Based on the IMRAD methodology (Introduction, Methods, Results, and Discussion) (Jacobs, 2022), each result (R), or project target, was addressed through specific methodological approaches developed through a series of activities described in the subsections below and documented in Annexes I, II, and III.

2.1. Method for Result 1 – Project Planning and Operations

The Mobility C3 Project was divided into two phases: Phase 1 – Research and Technology Development, with a duration of 10 months, and Phase 2 – Administrative and Commercial Development, with a duration of 14 months. For the first phase, planning instruments commonly employed by international development and funding agencies were adopted, namely the Logical Framework (LF) and the Results-Based Schedule of the Mobility C3 Project (Sida, 2004; GTZ, 1997). In addition, an Evaluation Matrix was developed to assess the results achieved during the first ten months of Phase 1. (See Annex I-1: Mobility C3 Project Planning and Evaluation Instruments).

2.2. Method for Result 2 – Proof of Concept (PoC) and MVP Laboratories

This result (R) represents one of the most important components of the Mobility C3 Project, as it is directly aligned with the objectives of FAPERJ Call No. 10/2021, which seeks to transform research and innovation into scientific and technological knowledge capable of supporting entrepreneurship.

The MVP enabled a comparative analysis between the traditional method (e.g., the Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Protocol) and a new methodological approach implemented in the Mobility C3 3-in-1 digital platform (application), which measures vehicle CO₂ emissions using the United Nations Global Technical Regulation methodology (United Nations, 2014). This methodological choice positions the Mobility C3 Project as a potential game changer, as it introduces an innovative approach to the conventional—and to some extent limited—methods used for estimating CO₂ emissions from light-duty motor vehicles in Brazil and globally.

The first laboratory was the proof of concept (PoC) offline laboratory. It was developed in two stages. The first stage was carried out with 7 selected light motor vehicles using the NEDC and WLTP CO₂ standard of each vehicle.

Formulas and vehicle data were input into an Excel spreadsheet (logbook) to calculate distance measurements (km) and CO₂ emissions. On the basis of the kilometers traveled the formulas automatically calculated also the CO₂ emissions and the ecological compensation (carbon offset)

of each vehicle: the number of trees to be planted and the hectares (ha) of forest to conserve. The fuel used in all the vehicles was 'regular gasoline', which was filled at known branded stations in Brazil (e.g., Shell, Petrobras, and Ipiranga).

Nevertheless, during Phase II of the Mobility C3 Project, additional laboratory tests for vehicle CO₂ emissions were required. These tests compared the methodologies of the GHG Protocol, which estimates emissions based on fuel consumption during trips, with the Global Technical Regulation No. 15 methodology (United Nations, 2014), as described in Appendix I-2.

2.3. Method for Result 3 – Mobility C3 Platform Model

This result is closely associated with the previous item, since the PoC laboratory methodology and the development of the platform model were intrinsically interconnected. The platform was visually designed to display the monitored motor vehicle on a digital map together with the key variables of distance traveled (km), CO₂ emissions, number of trees required for carbon offsetting, forest conservation area, and carbon credits through user-friendly and intuitive interfaces.

The scientific framework on how the application should calculate CO₂ emissions and work using the Google Maps platform API (application programming interface), including the application's basic user interface (UI) design was provided to the 11 Tech Company for them to develop the architecture and programming of the application.

The algorithm and results obtained from the offline PoC laboratories (see items 2.1 and 3) was used to develop the online MVP laboratory (see item 2.4 for more details). The online laboratory uses the Google Maps geo-tracking technology to monitor the kilometers traveled (km) by each motor vehicle and to calculate CO₂ emissions based on the NEDC and WLTP methods. All information is stored at a digital cloud provider (e.g. King host) that make back-end calculations during the laboratory.

The five (05) vehicles used in the online MVP laboratory were as follows: Vehicle built before 2017: *Vehicle 1* - Suzuki/Gran Vitar 1.6/2001 - gasoline. Vehicles built after 2017: *Vehicle 2* - Fiat Palio ELX 1.4, 8v, FLEX 2017 - alcohol/gasoline; *Vehicle 3* - Renault, Oroch, 1.6 Pickup, 2020 - alcohol/gasoline; *Vehicle 4* - Citroen C3 Air Cross, Flex 2024 - alcohol/gasoline; *Vehicle 5* - Hyundai ix35, 170hp - alcohol/gasoline. All motor vehicles used gasoline as fuel during the online laboratory. This laboratory confirmed Mobility C3 as a prototype application, version 0.1, for Android cell phones with a technological maturity of 7 (Technology Readiness Level 7), a technology approved in an operational environment.

Annex I-3 provides a detailed description of the methodology and design of the Mobility C3 Platform. Methodological procedures were also established to achieve an appropriate balance between the platform's User Interface (UI) and User Experience (UX).

2.4. Method for Result 4 – Forest Partnerships

Based on the Mobility C3 Project Schedule, extensive research was conducted on scientific standards and methodologies related to carbon absorption (sequestration) by trees and native tropical forests. The findings were synthesized through graphical representations, tables, and technical summaries.

Subsequently, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and major forestry companies operating across the different Brazilian biomes were identified and mapped with the objective of establishing a network of forestry partners. Semi-structured questionnaires were then prepared and distributed to selected NGOs and forestry companies to collect baseline information necessary for the establishment of future partnerships.

This forestry and carbon-offset research is particularly relevant because the resulting data will be incorporated into the Mobility C3 digital platform as reference parameters for carbon offset calculations. Further details are provided in Annex I-4.

2.5. Method for Result 5 – Market Research

Market research constitutes a fundamental component of the Mobility C3 business model. To achieve this result, internet-based research was conducted on the sustainability reports of prospective corporate clients. Preliminary contacts were also established with potential customers through LinkedIn and other social media platforms.

Following the identification and mapping of potential clients, semi-structured questionnaires were developed and administered to assess their interest in contracting the services offered by Mobility C3. Direct commercial engagement with prospective clients will be undertaken during Phase 2 – Administrative and Commercial Development of the Project, once the Mobility C3 Platform becomes fully operational online.

Further details regarding this phase are provided in Annex I-5. Additional information on market research can be found in Braun (2023), *Mobility C3 Business Plan*.

2.6. Method for Result 6 – Business Plan

Based on the Mobility C3 Project Schedule, a Business Plan was prepared following the methodology developed by SEBRAE (SEBRAE, 2013). The Business Plan includes essential information for the commercialization of the technology, including Market Analysis, Strategic Assessment, Marketing Plan, Operational Plan, Financial Plan, and Scenario Development, in accordance with the requirements established under FAPERJ Call No. 10/2021.

Upon completion, the Mobility C3 Business Plan will be submitted to FAPERJ through the SisFAPERJ platform. For additional information, see Braun (2023), *Mobility C3 Business Plan*.

2.7. Method for Result 7 – Technical Report

The present Partial Technical Report follows the recommendations established under FAPERJ Call No. 10/2021. It describes the activities carried out during the first ten months of the project and includes supporting materials that contribute to a clear understanding of the development process.

The report adopts the IMRAD methodology—Introduction, Methods, Results, and Discussion (Jacobs, 2022)—comprising an Introduction and project objectives, a description of the methods applied to each result (R) and project target, a discussion of the products and outcomes generated, and concluding sections presenting conclusions, recommendations, and the reference bibliography.

In accordance with the Mobility C3 Project Schedule (see Annex I-1), the principal results (R) achieved and described in this section are presented following the structure established in Section 2, Methods. The annexes were organized to provide supporting evidence of the activities carried out during the project. Supporting documentation can be found in Annexes II-1, II-2, II-3, II-4, and II-5. Additional information is provided in Annexes I-1, I-2, I-3, I-4, I-5, I-6, and III-1, III-2, III-3, and III-4.

3. RESULTS

In accordance with the Phase II Schedule of the Mobility C3 Project, the principal results (R) achieved are presented in this section following the structure established in Section 2, Methods. The annexes accompanying this Report were organized to provide supporting evidence of the activities carried out throughout the project.

3.1. Result 1 – Project Planning and Operations

Based on the Mobility C3 Project Schedule and the Logical Framework (see Annex I-1), a Project Evaluation Matrix was developed (see Annex I-1) to compare planned activities with those effectively implemented and achieved throughout the first ten months of the Mobility C3 Project. Of the seven (7) results established for the first phase, only one result, R5, was partially achieved, as the activities associated with this result are also scheduled for implementation during the second phase of the project (Phase 2 – Administrative and Commercial Development). Additional information regarding the evaluation process is provided in Annex II-1.

3.2. Result 2 – Proof of Concept (PoC) and MVP Laboratories

This stage represented one of the most important components of the project because it directly addresses the primary objective of FAPERJ Call No. 10/2021, namely, promoting the transformation of research, development, and innovation projects into enterprises based on scientific and technological knowledge.

As an important outcome, academic research activities (see the Bibliographic References, Section 6), together with numerous technical consultations and interviews with Information Technology (IT) specialists (see Annexes I-2, II-1, III-2, III-3, and III-4), revealed the need to organize the various methodologies used for measuring vehicle CO₂ emissions and to define the most appropriate methodology to be adopted by the Mobility C3 Platform.

Furthermore, methodologies were established for the development of the platform, including the definition of several technical parameters considered essential for the development, calibration, and validation of the Mobility C3 Platform. The platform prototype was scheduled for completion in April 2023, after which final testing would be conducted prior to its commercial launch. Additional laboratory data related to the platform's architecture and software development will be generated and reported to FAPERJ during the first semester of 2023.

In addition, graphs and tables were developed based on the research findings and technical interviews. The formulas required to calculate CO₂ emissions, the number of trees required for carbon offsetting, the area of forest conservation, and carbon credits were also provided to 11 Tech for incorporation into the platform's computational framework and calculation spreadsheets (see Annex III-5).

The PoC laboratory resulted in a total number of kilometers (km) traveled by the 7 tested light motor vehicles after 15 days across different locations in Brazil was 4.5 thousand Km, with emissions ranging across almost one ton of CO₂ (e.g. 891 kg). The ecological compensation for the 891 kg of CO₂ was calculated for almost 5 trees (e.g. 4.7), and the area to be preserved was 0.02 ha of tropical forest. Based on the logbooks (Excel sheets) of the offline laboratory (see item 2.2.1) the resulting information was used to create cartesian graphs to compare different variables, such as kilometers (km) traveled and CO₂ emitted, the number of trees to be planted by each vehicle, and the area of tropical forest to be preserved per vehicle per hectare (ha).

During Phase II of the Project, a CO₂ emission laboratory experiment was conducted using a volunteer vehicle, incorporating fuel consumption as a key variable based on the Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Protocol (FGV, 2023) and the United Nations Global Technical Regulation (United Nations, 2014).

The Mobility C3 methodology is based on Real Driving Emissions (RDE) conditions, as supported by multiple authors and defined in the United Nations Global Technical Regulation, due to its more advanced and up-to-date methodological framework.

The online MVP laboratory was developed with five 5 vehicles of different manufacturers, models and years of construction. The Mobility C3 application 0.1 prototype was installed on five Android cell phones with Google Maps Platform to track the routes traveled by each one (see Table 4 for details).

As described previously the calculations of kilometers traveled, CO₂ emissions and carbon offset were performed at the managerial back-end of the application and the data generated was stored at the King Host cloud provider. The core methods for determining CO₂ emissions used in this laboratory are based on the NEDC / WLTP methods (Ciuffo and Fontaras, 2017) and standards obtained in Inmetro (Inmetro, 2020). The Mobility C3 application measured the routes of the five vehicles totaling more than three thousand kilometers (e.g. 3,315 km) over 15 days.

The Mobility C3 methodology is based on Real Driving Emissions (RDE) conditions, as supported by multiple authors and defined in the United Nations Global Technical Regulation, due to its more advanced and up-to-date methodological framework.

3.3. Result 3 – Mobility C3 Platform Model

The Mobility C3 Platform model was not developed overnight, considering that the development of a digital platform (application) may require several months of research, design, and implementation. Discussions and research activities aimed at developing the Mobility C3 model began in May 2021 during the preparation of the proposal submitted to FAPERJ and continued through April 2023.

The Mobility C3 methodology was structured through successive stages of development involving fundamental content and design elements. The process began with the creation of interface mock-ups and screen designs to define how the platform would operate, followed by the establishment of the platform's back-end architecture and the design of its User Interface (UI) and User Experience (UX) components.

A set of 12 basic functional screens of the Mobility C3 Application (Version 01) was developed based on four prototype iterations between January 2023 and June 2024. For further details and basic application interfaces, see Appendix I-3.

However, the application still requires improvements to achieve full operational functionality, as the development of a digital platform inherently involves an iterative process of refinement, testing, and correction. The system will require continuous evolutionary maintenance, including the modularization of the application and the development of a desktop-based platform for both Mobility C3 administrators and corporate clients (legal entities) responsible for managing vehicle fleets.

Additional enhancements include enabling offline functionality for operation in remote areas, as well as integrating NFC and QR Code technologies into the driver application. The Mobility C3 application is also expected to be deployed on the Google Play Store, with a corresponding version developed for Apple iOS and published on the Apple App Store. Furthermore, intellectual property protection measures are required, including registration of the software code and

conceptual framework with the Brazilian National Institute of Industrial Property (INPI) and international patent or trademark offices.

These design elements were specifically developed to support the monitoring and visualization of distance traveled (km), CO₂ emissions, number of trees required for carbon offsetting, forest conservation areas, and carbon credits. Additional details regarding the platform methodology and design are provided in Annexes I-2 and I-3.

3.4. Result 4 – Forest Partnerships Strategy

The Mobility C3 Project is not limited to developing the digital platform technology required to measure carbon emissions from motor vehicles; it also seeks to facilitate the ecological offsetting of CO₂ emissions through partnerships with forestry organizations and carbon-offset companies.

During this phase, an extensive academic review of carbon offsetting methodologies was conducted using multiple sources and authors (Freitas, 2022; Prima, 2020; Embrapa, 2020a; Embrapa, 2020b; Movida, 2019; Braun, 2015; MMA, 2012; Tonon, 2007; Santos, 2007; Imazon; IBF, 2022; Movida, 2022; among others listed in the bibliography).

Carbon-offset graphs were developed, and a methodology was designed together with the User Interface (UI) and User Experience (UX) components specifically related to forestry partners. Questionnaires were prepared and distributed to twenty-three (23) organizations, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and forestry companies engaged in forestry projects and environmental businesses across different Brazilian biomes.

Subsequently, the eleven most relevant carbon-credit commercialization companies operating in Brazil were identified and mapped. Online meetings and information exchanges were conducted with seven (7) of these organizations with the objective of establishing future commercial partnerships.

During this stage, contact was also established with vehicle-tracking companies, including Getrak, Trimble, and BMS, in order to acquire technological know-how and evaluate potential commercial partnerships.

Additional information is presented in Annex I-4 and Annex II-4.

3.5. Result 5: Market Research

Market research was initiated on a preliminary basis during the technological development phase (Phase 1) of the project because it directly addresses the overall objective of FAPERJ Call No. 10/2021, namely, transforming scientific knowledge into an innovative business venture.

The main outcomes of this stage included the identification and mapping of companies participating in the Corporate Sustainability Index (ISE²), preliminary commercial contacts with seven companies through customer-service channels and LinkedIn, and the distribution of questionnaires to selected organizations and businesses.

² Companies in Brazil (selected) that are among the 200 most liquid stocks on the B3 stock exchange, focusing on environmental, corporate governance, social, and climate change issues (ISE, 2020).

Further details are provided in Annexes II-5 and III-4.

3.6. Result 6: Business Plan

In accordance with the requirements established by FAPERJ Call No. 10/2021, a comprehensive 46-page Business Plan was developed following the guidelines presented in the publication *How to Prepare a Business Plan* (SEBRAE, 2013).

3.7. Result 7 – Technical Report

The present document constitutes the **Partial Technical Report** itself. In other words, it represents the final result (R) of Phase 1 of the Mobility C3 Project, corresponding to the research, development, and technological innovation activities undertaken during the initial stage of the project.

This report documents the methodologies applied, the activities performed, the results achieved, and the products generated throughout the first ten months of project implementation. It also provides supporting evidence of the research and technological development processes through the annexes, tables, figures, technical analyses, and complementary documentation presented herein.

Accordingly, this report serves as a comprehensive record of the progress achieved during Phase 1 and as a basis for the continuation of the project into Phase 2, which will focus on the administrative, commercial, and operational deployment of the Mobility C3 Platform.

4. DISCUSSION

The discussion is presented in a concise thematic format following the sequence established in the Methods (Section 2) and Results (Section 3) chapters discussed above.

4.1. Project Planning and Operations

The Mobility C3 Project encountered several challenges at the outset of its implementation due to changes within the Information Technology (IT) team, the need to recruit a new IT engineer, and the requirement for additional technological tools that had not been originally budgeted under the FAPERJ funding proposal.

The lack of adequate technical resources necessitated the formal suspension of the project in May 2022 for a period of six months. Although this interruption represented an emergency measure, it provided an opportunity to restructure the IT team and refine the development strategies of the Mobility C3 Project. Project activities resumed in November 2022.

Before and during the suspension period, more than twenty IT specialists were interviewed, providing valuable technical insights that contributed to the alignment of the platform development strategy and ultimately supported the contracting of the technology company 11 Tech (see Annex III-6). The project continued from November 2022 through April 2023.

The recruitment of 11 Tech represented a major milestone for the project, as it enabled the architectural design and software development of the Mobility C3 Platform. The platform prototype was scheduled for completion in May 2023, after which final testing would be conducted prior to commercialization.

During this period, potential forestry partners were identified and mapped, and the feasibility of partnerships was assessed both within the vehicle monitoring sector and among organizations and companies specializing in carbon offsetting and emissions neutralization. Further details are provided in Annexes I-1 and I-2.

Technical interviews (see Annexes I-2 and III-1) indicated that the timeframe established under FAPERJ Call No. 10/2021 for simultaneously developing the digital technology and commercializing the Mobility C3 product was highly challenging given the diversity and complexity of the activities involved.

4.2. Proof of Concept (PoC) and MVP Laboratories

According to Braun (2021) the offline proof of concept (PoC) laboratory with seven different light motor vehicles moved by gasoline was essential not only to test formulas, but also to evaluate carbon offset calculations. However, due to financial restrictions of the Mobility C3 Project during the research phase in Brazil had a great operational challenge, to find voluntary drivers to collaborate with the laboratories. After identifying and selecting the drivers they were asked to report the mileage they had driven every day over 15 days. The laboratory work was carried out effectively and we were able to evaluate the calculation for measuring the CO₂ of each vehicle.

Once the formulas and procedures were tested and approved off-line, we used the results to develop the minimum viable product (MVP) on-line laboratory. In other words, the proof of concept was achieved to continue towards the construction of the Mobility C3 prototype application and test it with 5 light motor vehicles.

Although there are several methods to measure CO₂ emissions of motor vehicles we selected the GHG Protocol and the NEDC / WLTP methods because they are the most effective to be tested and economically viable compared to other methods. As mentioned previously the GHG Protocol developed in 1998 is used by a large number of carbon compensation companies (e.g. Way Carbon) to determine the broad carbon inventory of cliente companies. As mentioned previously the GHG Protocol considers that all vehicles that use fossil fuel (e.g. gasoline, diesel) burn and emit a standard amount of CO₂ into the atmosphere. In a simple manner if a motor vehicle of any manufacturer or model uses 10 liters of gasoline to travel, it will in principle emit 22,90 kg of CO₂³ to the atmosphere independently of vehicle design, technology, modelo or year. Additionally the GHG Protocol requires the user to periodically fill in the amount of fossil fuel (in liters) used to travel to calculate the CO₂ emissions. In certain cases it is also necessary to input the distance traveled (km) and the fuel consumption efficiency standard of 10 km/liter to calculate emissions (Weng et al, 2017; Carvalho, 2011; Soares et al, 2009; Alvares and Linke, n.d.). All these procedures takes time and resources to accomplish when compared to the efficiency of the Mobility C3 that does not require the input of periodical data because all data of a monitored vehicle is input and stored previously in the data bank of the application to calculate CO₂ emissions automatically.

A very revealing result from the online MVP lab is that it not only confirmed the NEDC / WLTP methods as being more efficient than the GHG Protocol but also because the latter can generate errors. This became evident comparing the performance of two light motor vehicles: the Fiat 1.4

³ A simple formula is 10 liters x 2.29 gasoline burning factor = 22,90 kg of CO₂. Although some authors can include additional factors in the calculations (E.g. density of fuel and percentage of ethanol).

Palio ELX Flex, and the Suzuki / Gran Vitara 1.6 / 4X4 (see Table 5 in Item 3.2). During the online laboratory we observed that although the FIAT Palio travelled more 623,29 km than did the Suzuki Gran Vitara, it emitted less CO₂ to the atmosphere than the Suzuki Gran Vitara because the former has a lower CO₂ signature than the latter. However, using the GHG protocol the Fiat Palio's CO₂ emissions was 428,70 kg CO₂ higher than those of Suzuki Gran Vitara, which is an overall inaccurate result. The GHG Protocol error has shown that despite being the most commonly used method in the carbon market it is less accurate than the NEDC and WLTP methods.

We have chosen to use the NEDC and WLTP methods in the Mobility C3 application not only because they are more accurate than the GHG Protocol, but also because the user does not need to periodically input liters of fuel consumed and/or kilometers traveled to calculate CO₂ emissions.

The field of Information Technology (IT) is extensive and encompasses a wide variety of development pathways, tools, methodologies, and technological solutions. This diversity presents significant challenges in the design and implementation of a digital platform architecture.

In general, each IT specialist tends to possess preferred programming languages, cloud-computing environments, and software development methodologies. Furthermore, many specialists focus on particular areas of expertise, such as prototype development using Arduino systems, data management in cloud environments such as Amazon Web Services (AWS), cloud architecture using Google Cloud technologies, or software development in programming languages such as Java, Python, PHP, among others.

These findings demonstrated that there is no single linear pathway for developing a digital application. The knowledge acquired through technical consultations, informal discussions, and semi-structured interviews provided a deeper understanding of the complexity of the IT sector and its implications for platform development (see Annexes I-2 and III-1).

Within the current market of carbon-monitoring applications, carbon-offset services, and emissions measurement methodologies, it was observed that no existing system directly monitors vehicle CO₂ emissions using the manufacturer-certified emissions standard of the monitored vehicle. Current market solutions generally require users to manually input fuel consumption data and/or the distance traveled by the vehicle.

Consequently, the Mobility C3 Platform offers a significant competitive advantage, as users are not required to manually enter data to calculate CO₂ emissions. Instead, vehicle-specific emissions factors are embedded within the platform itself. These manufacturer-certified emissions standards are derived from complex research and testing procedures that combine fuel consumption rates, distance traveled, and tailpipe emissions measurements to establish standardized emissions values for each vehicle make and model.

Additional discussion analysis is presented in Annex II-6.

4.3. Forestry Partnerships and Carbon Credits

Ecological carbon offsetting through tree planting, native forest conservation, or carbon-credit commercialization is a highly complex process. Beyond the scientific complexity associated with biodiversity and forestry sciences, successful forest restoration and conservation initiatives require extensive coordination, long-term management, and collaboration with both local workers and surrounding communities.

On average, trees require approximately twenty to thirty years to sequester around 70% of atmospheric carbon through the process of photosynthesis (Manfrinato et al., 2016).

Various authors (Freitas, 2022; Prima, 2020; Embrapa, 2020; Movida, 2019; Braun, 2015; MMA, 2012; Tonon, 2007; Santos, 2007; Imazon; Movida, 2022; and IBF, 2022) report carbon sequestration rates ranging from approximately 150 kg to 300 kg of carbon per tree in tropical forests. A comparative analysis of these sources revealed a high degree of consistency, with only minor variations among the reported values.

Similarly, several sources indicate that one hectare of tropical forest may sequester between 40 and 80 tonnes of carbon over a twenty-year period (IPCC, 2008; CredCarbo; Santos, 2007; Yu, 2004; Manfrinato et al., among others).

However, Yu (2004) raises important questions regarding the long-term effectiveness of forest-based carbon sequestration, arguing that wood biomass will eventually decompose, resulting in the release of stored carbon back into the atmosphere. This observation suggests that forest carbon storage possesses inherent temporal limitations and should therefore be considered within a broader climate mitigation framework.

Additional analysis is presented in Annex II-6.

4.4. Market Research

The market research conducted during this stage should be regarded as preliminary, given that it was undertaken during Phase 1 of the Mobility C3 Project. The research focused on understanding the operational characteristics of the target market through internet-based investigations, online interviews, and participation in live events organized by carbon-offset companies and organizations.

These activities generated important information that contributed directly to the preparation of the Mobility C3 Business Plan.

Overall, the research indicated that the Mobility C3 Platform remains innovative and distinctive with respect to CO₂ emissions monitoring because it is based on manufacturer-certified vehicle emissions standards. Potential competitors include geo-navigation applications, ecological footprint calculators, and vehicle-tracking companies.

Specific interviews and online discussions were conducted with vehicle-tracking companies, including Trimble, BMS, and Getrak, to better understand their operational models, measurement methodologies, pricing structures, and potential opportunities for commercial collaboration.

Additional research was also undertaken with organizations and companies operating within the Brazilian carbon-credit market, including Carbon Free, EcoBraz, WayCarbon, and others, to understand their business models, pricing structures, and opportunities for partnership with the Mobility C3 Platform.

The findings revealed that vehicle-tracking companies are capable of estimating CO₂ emissions provided that vehicle fuel consumption data are supplied. Trimble, for example, offers a digital interface displaying distance traveled, estimated CO₂ emissions, and the number of trees required for offsetting; however, it does not establish direct connections with forestry organizations or carbon-offset service providers.

It is important to note that within the carbon-offset market, carbon-credit commercialization is associated not only with tree planting and forest conservation but also with recycling programs, waste management initiatives, renewable energy projects (wind, biogas, and solar energy), sustainable agriculture, and various other environmental mitigation activities.

The research further demonstrated that strategic partnerships with carbon-offset organizations and companies represent one of the most effective channels for promoting the Mobility C3 Platform and expanding its customer base.

Additional analysis is presented in Annex II-6.

4.5. Business Plan

The Mobility C3 Business Plan was developed based on the preliminary research findings and on the projected commercialization of the Mobility C3 technology, particularly targeting companies included in corporate sustainability indices. The business model also incorporates strategic partnerships with forestry organizations and carbon-offset companies.

For additional information, see Braun (2023), *Mobility C3 Business Plan*.

4.6. Technical Report

The present document constitutes the Partial Technical Report of the Mobility C3 Project.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the principal conclusions and recommendations derived from Phase 1 (Research and Technology Development Phase) of the Mobility C3 Project.

Conclusions

Brazil possesses a fleet of more than 74.5 million vehicles that should be incorporated into climate change mitigation policies through mechanisms designed to quantify and offset CO₂ emissions.

The voluntary carbon market in Brazil is experiencing significant growth and presents a promising business opportunity for the Mobility C3 Platform, particularly through strategic partnerships with carbon-offset organizations and carbon-credit companies.

With regard to the planning, research, and technological development of the Mobility C3 Platform, despite the initial setbacks involving the Information Technology (IT) team, the project successfully achieved approximately 90% of the planned results (R) for Phase 1 (see Annex I-1). Nevertheless, the timeframe established under FAPERJ Call No. 10/2021 for both developing the digital technology and commercializing the Mobility C3 product proved highly demanding.

The preparation of the Mobility C3 Business Plan demonstrated that establishing and operating a legally registered company requires continuous financial investments that may

not generate immediate returns. Mobility C3 is an innovative enterprise that remains relatively unknown within the market. Nevertheless, the research indicated that commercial partnerships with carbon-offset organizations and companies represent the most effective mechanism for promoting the platform and attracting potential clients.

The Information Technology (IT) sector encompasses a wide range of development approaches, tools, and technological possibilities. Each specialist typically employs distinct programming languages, cloud-computing platforms, and development methodologies, which may vary significantly in terms of efficiency and implementation speed. This diversity introduces uncertainty and complexity into the process of developing the digital platform and its underlying architecture.

The findings indicate that there are no simple or rapid solutions for developing a high-quality digital platform. Digital applications require substantial time for architectural design, testing, validation, and refinement, particularly when development must be conducted under financial and time constraints. However, according to 11 Tech, the Mobility C3 prototype represents a nearly complete version of the platform. Following final testing and validation, it will be ready for deployment within the carbon market in partnership with carbon-offset organizations and companies.

The research also demonstrated that equipment and interfaces are available for constructing carbon emissions monitoring prototypes, including sensors capable of being installed in vehicle exhaust systems downstream of the catalytic converter. However, it was concluded that the development of one or more monitoring prototypes using the Arduino Uno platform and associated measurement components (e.g., lambda sensors, cables, fire-resistant materials, among others) would result in relatively high unit costs, exceeding R\$1,000 per device. In summary, direct measurement of CO₂ emissions at the vehicle exhaust outlet represents the most accurate approach but is financially impractical for large vehicle fleets.

Current competing methodologies generally require users to manually enter fuel consumption and/or distance traveled in order to estimate CO₂ emissions. Both the Mobility C3 methodology and competing methods are subject to inherent limitations because they rely on average travel distances, estimated fuel-consumption rates, or the conversion of different greenhouse gases (CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O) into carbon dioxide equivalents (tCO₂eq). Additional variables, such as engine calibration, fuel adulteration, and user input errors, may further affect accuracy.

Considering that manufacturer-certified CO₂ emissions standards for each vehicle type, make, and model are derived from sophisticated laboratory testing and extensive research, this methodology was selected as the basis for the Mobility C3 Platform. Under this approach, users are not required to manually enter fuel-consumption or mileage data because vehicle-specific emissions factors are already embedded within the platform's calculation algorithms and are applied automatically based on the distance traveled in real time.

Furthermore, the research demonstrated that there are currently no applications, services, or vehicle emissions monitoring methodologies available in the market that utilize manufacturer-certified emissions standards as their primary calculation parameter. Consequently, Mobility C3 remains an innovative and distinctive project within the vehicle carbon-monitoring sector.

With regard to the Mobility C3 offline and online laboratory methodologies (including OBD-II Bluetooth systems), the offline methodology proved fundamental for calibrating the calculation framework associated with the variables of distance traveled, CO₂ emissions, number of trees required for offsetting, and forest conservation areas, thereby providing the foundation for the platform's management back-end. Conversely, the OBD-II laboratory approach presented significant operational difficulties related to device installation, data accessibility, and compatibility with existing applications. Consequently, the use of OBD-II devices is not recommended as the primary method for monitoring CO₂ emissions in vehicle fleets.

It can be concluded that the development of the digital platform technology for monitoring CO₂ emissions from light-duty motor vehicles represents the most significant achievement of the Mobility C3 Project. As a three-in-one application, it not only aligns with the objectives of FAPERJ Call No. 10/2021, which seeks to transform research and innovation into scientific and technological knowledge for entrepreneurship, but also constitutes a potential game changer by introducing improvements to the methodology used for measuring vehicle CO₂ emissions.

Unlike conventional approaches based on the GHG Protocol, the Mobility C3 platform adopts the United Nations Global Technical Regulation and the technical principle of Real Driving Emissions (RDE), in accordance with European Parliament regulations and methodologies analyzed by several authors. As a result, the Mobility C3 technology offers an innovative and distinctive solution for the carbon market.

Despite its innovative character and potential to transform the sector, it is important to adopt a realistic perspective regarding paradigm shifts in both technological and commercial cultures. The introduction of a new methodology does not guarantee its immediate acceptance or widespread adoption within the carbon market. The GHG Protocol is a long-established framework derived from the Kyoto Protocol, adopted by the United Nations in 1997, and is supported by an extensive conceptual structure, institutional framework, and established market practices.

Consequently, the successful adoption of the Mobility C3 methodology will depend not only on its technical superiority and scientific robustness but also on its acceptance by market stakeholders, regulatory institutions, and organizations operating in carbon accounting and offsetting activities. Continuous validation, dissemination of scientific evidence, strategic partnerships, and practical demonstrations of its advantages will therefore be essential to facilitate its incorporation into the evolving carbon market ecosystem.

The conceptual framework surrounding the GHG Protocol is largely based on fuel combustion patterns and vehicle fuel-efficiency standards established under that methodology. Two possible scenarios may therefore be considered. The first is the acceptance by the carbon market of the new CO₂ emission monitoring standard proposed by Mobility C3. The second is the continued reliance on the traditional GHG Protocol methodology and the maintenance of existing carbon accounting practices.

This uncertainty reflects the broader challenges associated with paradigm shifts in scientific, technological, and commercial systems. The adoption of new methodologies often requires significant time for validation, institutional acceptance, and market integration. Similar processes have been observed in the gradual recognition and acceptance of climate change by the global community. Consequently, although the Mobility C3 methodology presents technical and scientific advantages, its widespread

adoption will depend on the willingness of market participants, organizations, and regulatory stakeholders to embrace new approaches to carbon accounting and emissions monitoring.

Regarding ecological carbon offsetting, Mobility C3 will not directly engage in tree planting, forest conservation, or carbon-credit trading activities. Rather, these activities will be carried out by specialized forestry and carbon-offset partners. While tree planting and forest conservation may appear straightforward in theory, their practical implementation is highly complex and depends upon biodiversity conditions, climate factors, forestry science, and the effective organization and management of human resources. Continuous monitoring of these activities is essential to ensure the quality and credibility of the environmental services provided.

Despite the numerous challenges and complexities associated with the development of the Mobility C3 technology, the project seeks to contribute to climate-change mitigation, promote green employment opportunities, and generate positive environmental services for present and future generations.

Recommendations

Based on the studies conducted and the conclusions reached, a number of recommendations were developed, as presented below.

Mobilidade C3 Application

AsMobility C3 App Version 0.1 is a highly integrated digital platform incorporating three distinct login functionalities, it requires further evolutionary maintenance and technological enhancement.

The following actions are recommended:

- Develop a desktop-based platform for both Mobility C3 administrators and corporate clients (legal entities) to facilitate vehicle fleet management and monitoring.
- Enable offline functionality for application use in remote areas and implement the capability to export data in KMZ format.
- Integrate Near Field Communication (NFC) and QR Code technologies into the driver application.
- Register the Mobility C3 application on the Google Play Store and develop an iOS version for deployment through the Apple App Store.
- Register the software code, technological concept, trademarks, and associated intellectual property with the Brazilian National Institute of Industrial Property (INPI) and, where appropriate, seek international intellectual property protection.
- Adapt Mobility C3 application to use the Heavy Vehicle Energy Consumption Calculation Tool (VECTO) methodology to also monitor the CO₂ of heavy vehicles (e.g. Lorries, Busses and Coaches) in the carbon market.

Business Development and Commercial Partnerships

To strengthen market positioning and accelerate commercialization, the following actions are recommended:

- Participate in intensive entrepreneurship and business development programs to support the market launch of Mobility C3.
- Establish direct commercial relationships with potential corporate clients through professional networks such as LinkedIn, as well as direct engagement with private companies and government agencies.
- Develop new strategic partnerships with carbon offsetting companies and organizations, including EcoBraz, Moss Earth, Carbon Free, WayCarbon, SOS Amazônia, and other relevant stakeholders.
- Create and maintain a directory of carbon offsetting organizations on the official Mobility C3 website while encouraging partner organizations to promote Mobility C3 through their own digital communication channels.
- Improve the business model governing service fees and revenue-sharing mechanisms with carbon offsetting partners.
- Monitor carbon offsetting activities conducted by partner organizations—including tree planting, forest conservation, and carbon credit generation—to ensure service quality and environmental integrity.
- Evaluate international carbon markets and assess the feasibility of expanding Mobility C3 operations beyond Brazil.
- Maintain incubation within the National Laboratory for Scientific Computing (LNCC/MCTI) until the completion of the funding period established under Call No. 20/2021.

Mobilidade C3 Marketing Strategy

The following marketing initiatives are recommended:

- Develop and implement a comprehensive marketing strategy and promote Mobility C3 through major social media platforms, including LinkedIn, Instagram, and other relevant channels.
- Participate in COP30, the 30th Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), scheduled to take place in Belém, Pará, Brazil, from 10 to 21 November 2025.
- Participate in information technology and vehicle-tracking trade fairs to promote Mobility C3 through banners, brochures, videos, and other communication materials, while also conducting technical visits to government agencies and corporate organizations.

Resource Mobilization

To support technological development and business expansion, the following funding strategies are recommended:

- Identify opportunities for financial and material support within Brazil through initiatives such as the FINEP Startup Program, Ocyan Startup Booster, Bamboo,

Natura Campus, BNDES financing programs for micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises, and other relevant funding mechanisms.

- Pursue international funding opportunities through organizations such as Siemens Stiftung, The Global EbA Fund, The Minor Foundation, Global Innovation Fund, Wallace Global Fund, Credit Suisse AG, and other institutions that support climate innovation, sustainability, and technology-based entrepreneurship.

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Annexes

Project Mobility C3

April 2023

ANNEXES

This document forms part of the Partial Technical Report of the Mobility C3 Project. The annexes are organized into three sections.

Annex I presents the methodologies applied, including supporting graphs, tables, and materials generated during the research and technology development process.

Annex II contains the results achieved and their respective supporting evidence.

Annex III includes questionnaires, interviews, and supporting data related to the Information Technology (IT) and forestry/carbon-offsetting components of the project.

ANNEX I – 1

2.1. Method for Result 1 – Project Planning and Operations

The Mobility C3 Project employed two planning instruments widely used by international development and funding agencies: the Logical Framework (LF) and the Results-Based Schedule of the Mobility C3 Project (Sida, 2004; GTZ, 1997). These instruments provided the methodological basis for planning the entire Phase 1 – Research and Technology Development.

Based on the Logical Framework (LF) and the Mobility C3 Project Schedule, an evaluation of project performance was conducted during the first ten months of implementation (see Project Evaluation Matrix below).

It is important to highlight that, at the beginning of the project in November 2021, the Mobility C3 Project experienced setbacks related to its Information Technology (IT) team, as described in Table 1, *Project Challenges and Solutions of the Mobility C3 Project*. These difficulties required the submission of a formal request to FAPERJ for a six-month suspension of the fellowship. The suspension was approved by FAPERJ and remained in effect from May 2022 to November 2022, when project activities officially resumed. During the suspension period, research, technical development, and entrepreneurial activities associated with the project continued on an unofficial basis.

The principal planning instruments adopted by the Mobility C3 Project were the Project Schedule and the Logical Framework (LF), as presented below.

Mobility Ce Project Schedule

Based on the Mobility C3 Project Schedule, the following activities were carried out: establishment of the Mobility C3 IT team; planning of project results, targets, and implementation schedule; definition of the project management structure; and financial management and accountability of all cash-flow activities associated with Phase 1.

The schedule is structured around seven Results (or Targets) to be achieved, together with the corresponding activities required to attain each result (R), the responsibilities assigned to team members, the planned start dates, the number of days (D) allocated for implementation, and the overall project timeline, as presented below.

CRONOGRAMA DO PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3®				Versão Abril/2022																												
LIDER: RICARDO BRAUN, PhD - EQUIPE RICSNETWORK																																
RESULTADOS (R)				2022												2023																
FASE 1 - PESQUISA E TECNOLOGIA				D J F M A M J J A S O N D												J F M A M J J A S O N D																
	ATRIBUIÇÃO	INÍCIO	Nº DE DIAS																													
1 START DO PROJETO	R1 - PLANEJAMENTO E OPERACIONAL DO PROJETO																															
	• Montar equipe de TI Mobilidade C3®	R. Braun	1/12/21	5D																												
	• Planejar resultados / metas e cronograma do Projeto	R. Braun / Equipe TI	5/1/22	15D																												
	• Definir esquema gerencial do Projeto	R. Braun	5/1/22	15D																												
	• Prestar contas de todo fluxo de caixa da Fase 1	R. Braun	5/1/22	15D																												
2 TECNOLOGIA MOBILIDADE C3®	R2 - LABORATÓRIO PROVA DE CONCEITO (POC)																															
	• Realizar levantamento e análise bibliográfico	R. Braun	1/12/21	120D																												
	• Definir e ativar plataforma AWS (outras).	Equipe TI	4/4/22	5D																												
	• Ativar celulares e/ou rastreadores para laboratório	R. Braun / Equipe TI	4/4/22	5D																												
	• Medir percursos e emissão de carbono	R. Braun / Equipe TI	9/4/22	30D																												
	• Tabular informações em banco de dados	Equipe TI	9/4/22	15D																												
	• Análise da performance laboratorial	Equipe TI	15/4/22	20D																												
	• Criar sistema de centralização/banco de dados	Equipe TI	30/4/22	20D																												
	• Montar protótipo MVP e sistema de monitoramento	Equipe TI	5/5/22	30D																												
		R3 - MODELO DA PLATAFORMA DESENVOLVIDO																														
	• Otimizar a interface da plataforma	Equipe TI	15/5/22	30D																												
	• Realizar design UI e UX em dois idiomas	Equipe TI	15/5/22	30D																												
3 PARCERIAS FLORESTAIS	R4 - PARCERIAS FLORESTAIS IMPLEMENTADAS																															
	• Mapear organizações / empresas nos biomas brasileiros	R. Braun	15/1/22	90D																												
	• Preparar e aplicar questionários com ONGs e empresas	R. Braun	15/01/2022	120D																												
	• Desenvolver parcerias para plantio de árvores	R. Braun	15/4/22	90D																												
	• Definir critérios técnicos / comerciais - preços florestais	R. Braun	15/3/22	90D																												
	• Incorporar parceiros florestais na plataforma C3®	R. Braun / Equipe TI	15/5/22	30D																												
4 MERCADO	R5 - PESQUISA DE MERCADO																															
	• Mapear potenciais clientes corporativos / ISE e Governo	R. Braun	20/5/22	180D																												
	• Preparar e aplicar questionários com empresas	R. Braun																														
	• Definir preços dos serviços da plataforma C3®	R. Braun	1/6/22	45D																												
	• Realizar contatos comerciais com clientes e parceiros	R. Braun	15/6/22	40D																												
5 PLANO DE NEGÓCIOS	R6 - PLANO DE NEGÓCIOS DA EMPRESA																															
	• Elaborar Plano de Negócios	R. Braun	1/8/22	45D																												
	• Criar logo, marketing e mídias sociais da empresa C3®	R. Braun	15/8/22	60D																												
	• Plano de Negócios para <i>DemoDay</i> Paperj	R. Braun	15/9/22	15D																												
	• Patentiar no INPI a tecnologia da Plataforma C3®	R. Braun	15/9/22	30D																												
6 AVALIAÇÃO I	R7 - RELATÓRIO TÉCNICO PARCIAL																															
	• Avaliar resultados de negócios e tecnologia	R. Braun	1/9/22	30D																												
	• Elaborar Relatório Técnico Parcial	R. Braun	15/9/22	30D																												

Table 1. Timeline for Phase 1 Research and Technology of the Mobility C3 Project.

Logical Framework

The Logical Framework (LF) (Sida, 2004; GTZ, 1997) contains the higher objective (HI) and the project objective (PO) for C3 Mobility, including the results (R) (Goals) to be achieved, the sources of evidence (SF), and the assumptions (S), which represent the project risks. The LF for the C3 Mobility Project is shown below.

QUADRO LÓGICO Versão01/Abril 2022	Instituição: FAPERJ / Incubadora doLNCC Projeto: MOBILIDADE C3® Duração do Projeto: 2 anos		Datas: Início: Novembro 2021 Fim: Outubro 2023
Descrição Sumária	Indicadores (IOC)	Fontes de Comprovação (FC)	Suposições (S) (Riscos)
Objetivo Superior do Projeto (OS): Contribuir para minimizar efeitos climáticos para as futuras gerações através da compensação ecológica do carbono emitido por veículos automotores.	Veículos automotores no Brasil medem e compensação suas emissões de carbono minimizando efeitos climáticos de longo prazo, a partir de Novembro de 2022 .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Índices de poluição por carbono em centros urbanos. Áreas degradadas regeneradas. Índice de áreas agrícolas plantadas. 	Governo não fomenta medidas sustentáveis para conter mudanças climáticas.
Objetivo de Projeto (OP): Desenvolver Plataforma de monitoramento ambiental de veículos automotores, emissão de CO2 e compensação ecológica.	100% da plataforma digital operante e disponível para serviços de monitoramento em Abril de 2022, com parceiros florestais engajados em compensação ecológica das emissões de carbono de veículos automotores contratados em diversos biomas brasileiros.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plataforma na internet. Contratos de serviços de monitoramento C3®. Fotos de áreas plantadas. Fotos de engajamento social no campo. 	Empresas e governo, priorizam mecanismos de desenvolvimento limpo (MDL) ao invés de compensação ecológica do carbono.
FASE 1			
RESULTADOS (R) R1 - INFRAESTRUTURA E OPERACIONAL DO PROJETO	Equipe organizada e 100% do Cronograma Operacional elaborado, e laboratório de rastreamento em Janeiro de 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cronograma Operacional impresso. Notas fiscais dos rastreadores. Fotos de reunião da equipe de trabalho. 	FAPERJ não viabiliza recursos do Edital Doutor Empreendedor.
R2 - LABORATÓRIO PROVA DE CONCEITO (POC)	Plataforma ativada entre 05 e 10 celulares 100% instalados, dados processados e protótipo MVP da plataforma a partir de Março de 2022 .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plataforma em desktop e celulares. Fotos de veículos. Medidas de Km, emissão de CO2 e árvores para compensar na plataforma. 	Sistema de rastreamento impossibilitado com Google ou AWS.
R3 - MODELO DA PLATAFORMA	Modelo da plataforma desenvolvido com design UI e UX em funcionamento a partir de Junho de 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plataforma digital Mobilidade C3 Desktop e celulares com design UI e UX 	Sistema de rastreamento impossibilitado com Google ou AWS.
R4 - PARCERIAS FLORESTAIS	X parcerias com silvicultores, ONGs e empresas de reflorestamento, concretizadas e parceiros florestais inseridos na plataforma C3 até Agosto de 2022 . Obs. X representa um número variável.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contratos / MOU (<i>Memorando of Understanding</i>) de parcerias. Fotos dos locais de plantio de árvores. 	Parceiros florestais carecem de infraestrutura para demanda de compensação ecológica.
R5 - PESQUISA DE MERCADO	Empresas com ISE mapeadas e contatadas para oferecer serviços com preços definidos em Reais e em US Dólares, para a plataforma C3, e para serviços florestais, até Setembro de 2022 .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lista de empresas selecionadas. Preços tabelados de serviços da plataforma. Preços tabelados de serviços florestais. 	Empresas e governo, priorizam mecanismos de desenvolvimento limpo (MDL) ao invés de compensação ecológica do carbono.
R6 - PLANO DE NEGÓCIOS DA EMPRESA	01 Plano de Negócios, base Sebrae, elaborado até o dia 20 de Agosto de 2022, contendo logo da empresa, estratégia de marketing e mídias sociais definidas até Outubro de 2022 .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plano de Negócios Mobilidade C3® 	FAPERJ não viabiliza recursos do Edital Doutor Empreendedor.
R7 - AVALIAÇÃO FASE I & RELATÓRIO TÉCNICO I	01 Relatório Técnico I de Avaliação dos Resultados (R) do Projeto, elaborado para a FAPERJ, até Outubro de 2022 .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relatório Técnico I Matriz de Avaliação de Resultados e Objetivos. 	FAPERJ não viabiliza recursos do Edital Doutor Empreendedor.

Tabela 2. Planning Logical Framework of the Mobility C3 Project

Setbacks and Solutions Chart

Timeline of Setbacks and Solutions for the Mobility C3 Project

Delays and Setbacks in the Team and Cost Expenses in the C3 Mobility Project

Unfortunately, the IT engineer who had been with the RicsNetwork team since 2020, when the project was launched, had to leave the team due to unforeseen circumstances in December 2021. IT specialists are very scarce in the job market today. With the loss of the project team, we had to find a new IT engineer to develop the C3 Mobility Platform.

In January 2022, we found a qualified and motivated professional with experience in IT architecture and programming aligned with the C3 Mobility Project. However, this new professional required financial and material resources that we were not prepared to meet (unforeseen operating expenses), particularly regarding the use of cloud technology and specific tools such as Compute Node (EKS), DataBase (RDS), Load Balancer, DNS Route 53, Domain, and others from Amazon Web Services (AWS). The cost of this service is R\$ 16,951.68 over 24 months. This amount was not included in the project approved by FAPERJ.

Between January and February 2022, we exchanged emails with FAPERJ, the LNCC Incubator, and the SERRATEC organization to seek these resources, but we were unsuccessful.

In mid-April 2022, due to bureaucratic issues within the LNCC legal department, the incubation contract had not yet been prepared for signature. This meant that access to Amazon Web Services (AWS) had not yet been granted, further delaying the development of the C3 Mobility Project.

Therefore, the construction of the C3 Mobility Project's digital platform was delayed by 3 months in its schedule.

IT Tool and the Mobility C3 Project

Chronologically, on March 15, 2022, an online meeting was held with the management of the LNCC Incubator regarding the official incubation process of the C3 Mobility Project.

In the second half of March 2022, the LNCC Incubator informed that, through an agreement between FAETEC and the LNCC Incubator, it would be possible to enable access to the Amazon Web Services (AWS) resources necessary for the development of the C3 Mobility Project platform. However, this tool could not be made available due to force majeure. Therefore, the signing of the incubation contract (Agreement) for the C3 Mobility Project was postponed. Without the IT tools, it was necessary to officially request a six-month suspension of the C3 Mobility Project grant from FAPERJ in order to have sufficient time to acquire the necessary IT tools and restructure both the Project and the IT team. The suspension granted by FAPERJ was from May to November 2022.

In October 2022, an official request was made to FAPERJ to resume the C3 Mobility Project in November 2022. Also in October 2022, the 'Technical-Business Development Agreement' with the LNCC Incubator was officially signed. In November 2022, contact was made with Professor Mozar Baptista regarding the construction of the C3 Mobility Platform through the IT company 11 Tech, to conduct tests and launch the platform online.

Table 3. Overview of setbacks and solutions for the Mobility C3 Project..

Project evaluation ion Phase I

To evaluate the C3 Mobility Project, it was necessary to compare what was planned in the Project Schedule (Table 1) and the Logical Framework (LF) (Table 2) with what was executed during the 10 months of the project in Phase 1 - Research and Technology. To do this, a Project Evaluation

Matrix was created using an ordinal evaluation scale. The Project Evaluation Matrix is shown below.

A - 100% goal achieved;

PA - partially achieved goal (up to 70% of the result);

NA - goal not achieved, 0%.

R1 - PLANEJAMENTO E OPERACIONAL DO PROJETO				
Atividades	A	PA	NA	Observações
• Montar equipe de TIMobility C3	X			Todas atividades foram desenvolvidas
• Planejamento e resultados do Projeto com a equipe.	X			Todas atividades foram desenvolvidas
• Planejamento e resultados do Projeto com a equipe	X			Todas atividades foram desenvolvidas
• Definir esquema gerencial do Projeto	X			Todas atividades foram desenvolvidas
• Prestar contas do fluxo de caixa da Fase 1	X			Todas atividades foram desenvolvidas
R2 - LABORATÓRIO PROVA DE CONCEITO (POC)				
Atividades	A	PA	NA	Observações
• Realizar levantamento e análise bibliográfica.	X			Pesquisas foram realizadas para se chegar aos dados em diversas fontes e autores para definir os parâmetros do clima, de emissão de CO2 e neutralização de carbono com vegetação plantada e / ou protegida. Por exemplo, varios autores descrevem que em 1 hectare de floresta é possível sequestrar X toneladas de carbono. Então a pesquisa define o padrão mais seguro a ser usado na plataforma digital.
• Definir e ativar plataforma.	X			
• Ativar celulares e/ou rastreadores • para laboratório	X			
• Medir percursos e emissão de carbono : • Laboratório off-line. • Laboratório on-line.	X			Realizado laboratório com medição off-line de veículos automotores para aferir dados e cálculos para o laboratório on-line do protótipo MC3.
• Tabular informações em banco de dados	X			Dados do laboratório off-line tabulados.

• Análise da performance laboratorial	X			Análise e gráficos de dados do laboratório off-line realizado.
• Criar sistema de centralização/banco de dados	X			Banco de dados criados do laboratório Off-line. Sem acesso a AWS vide item 2 do Relatório Técnico Parcial.
• Montar protótipo MVP e sistema de monitoramento	X			
R3 - MODELO DA PLATAFORMA DESENVOLVIDO				
Atividades	A	PA	NA	Observações
• Otimizar a interface da plataforma	X			
• Realizar design UI e UX em dois idiomas	X			
R4 - PARCERIAS FLORESTAIS				
Atividades	A	PA	NA	Observações
• Mapear organizações / empresas nos biomas brasileiros	X			Mapeamento pode ser ampliado.
• Preparar e aplicar questionários com ONGs e empresas	X			
• Desenvolver parcerias para plantio de árvores	X			4 questionários respondidos.
• Definir critérios técnicos / comerciais - preços florestais	X			Critérios técnicos criados e preços parcialmente estabelecidos.
• Incorporar parceiros florestais na plataforma C3®	X			
R5 - PESQUISA DE MERCADO				
Atividades	A	PA	NA	Observações
• Mapear potenciais clientes corporativos / ISE e Governo	X			Mapeamento pode ser ampliado.
• Preparar e aplicar questionários com empresas	X			
• Definir preços dos serviços da plataforma C3®	X			
• Realizar contatos comerciais com clientes e parceiros	X			
R6 - PLANO DE NEGÓCIOS DA EMPRESA				
Atividades	A	PA	NA	Observações
• Elaborar Plano de Negócios	X			
• Criar logo, marketing e mídias sociais da empresa C3®	X			
• Plano de Negócios para <i>DemoDay</i> Faperj	X			
• Patentiar no INPI a tecnologia da Plataforma C3®			X	

R7 - RELATÓRIO TÉCNICO PARCIAL				
Atividades	A	PA	NA	Observações
• Avaliar resultados de negócios e tecnologia	X			
• Elaborar Relatório Técnico Parcial	X			
Total Parcial	29 de 30	0 de 30	1de 30	

Table 4. Project Evaluation Matrix.

The table above shows that of the 30 planned activities, 29 were achieved in the first 10 months of the Project.

Annex I – 2

2.2. Methodology for Result 2 – Proof of Concept (PoC) Laboratory

Academic Research

Prior to conducting the Proof of Concept (PoC) laboratory on motor vehicle CO₂ emissions monitoring and ecological compensation, whether in an offline or online environment, an extensive quantitative and qualitative academic review was undertaken. This review focused both on carbon emissions generated by motor vehicles and on the various methodologies employed to measure the carbon footprint of vehicular transport (IPCC, 2020; IEA, 2020; Braun, 2020; Institute of Energy and Environment, 2017; OICA, 2021; IPCC, 2014; Movida, 2019; MMA, 2012; Braun, 2015; IPCC, 2006; among others).

Based on the methodological framework proposed by Kitchin and Tate (2000), the research was conducted through the examination of specialised databases, secondary data sources, and bibliographic materials available online, including reports, academic journals, books, and publications produced by national and international organisations, academic institutions, and scientific research bodies, as well as peer-reviewed scientific articles.

The studies undertaken were intended to identify the most robust and reliable methodological standard to be adopted within the digital platform. To this end, particular attention was given to vehicle emissions assessment methodologies and carbon footprint estimation approaches, drawing upon relevant studies in the field (Costa et al., 2018; Weng et al., 2017; Manfrinato et al., 2016; among others). The objective was to establish a scientifically sound framework for the monitoring and assessment of CO₂ emissions from motor vehicles.

Contacts with IT Technicians

During the PoC lab, several technical contacts were made with information technology (IT) specialists, and in certain cases, questionnaires were applied aiming at the development of the C3 Mobility platform and partnerships. The following specialists were contacted to develop the C3 Mobility Platform. Some contacts served as a basis for making new contacts to solve the issue of the development of said Platform.

TEMA	NOME	ORGANIZAÇÃO	DATA
Plataforma MC3 via Google Cloud	Eng. Renan Machado e Richard Siqueira	RicsNetWork	Maio 2020 / Novembro 2021
Plataforma MC3 via Amazon Web Service (AWS)	Eng. Paulo Jesus e Richard Siqueira	RicsNetWork	Janeiro de 2022
Acoplamento do MC3 na Plataforma Iceberg Getrak	Giver de Oliveira e Isabela Guimarães	Empresa GETRAK	Janeiro de 2022
Tecnologia OBD2 (Sistema de Diagnóstico de Bordo para Veículos Automotores)	Daniel Roberto dos Santos Pinto	Inovacell Comercio de Eletrônicos Ltda.	Fevereiro 2022
Telemetria e o calculo de CO2 por litros de combustível	Sirlei Roieski	Empresa BMS Rastreamento	Agosto de 2022
Tecnologia de rastreamento e plataforma do MC3	Prof. Fabio Licht	Eng. Comp. da Universidade Católica de Petrópolis UCP	Setembro de 2022
Plataforma Google Maps	Roberto Sermenó	Google	Setembro / Outubro de 2022
Construção da Plataforma Mobilidade C3	Prof. Mozar Baptista	11 Tech / UCP	Novembro de 2022
Valor da construção da Plataforma Mobilidade C3	Lucas Zefi	Ministry of Interior da Belgica	Novembro de 2022

Table 5. Experts contacted during the development of the Mobility C3 Project.

Questionnaires

In addition to the initial contacts, semi-structured questionnaires (Kitchin, et al, 2000) were also applied to selected IT specialists, aiming to define the tools, possibilities, methods, and limitations of the technology to guide the development of the C3 Mobility platform.

The table below lists the topics covered and the specialists interviewed.

NOME	ESPECIALIDADE	TEMA TRATADO	OBSERVAÇÃO
Richard Siqueira	Web design e programação	UX e UX, gestão de projeto de TI	Planejamento da construção do MC3 via Google cloud. Web design e entrevista técnica (ET)
Renan Machado	Arduino Uno e programação	Google Cloud	Estruturação da plataforma MC3 via Google cloud e (ET) Síndrome do sumiço (SS)
Paulo Jesus	Programador / arquiteto	AWS	Estruturação da plataforma MC3 via AWS
Ulysses Fiuza	Tecnologia de nuvem		Não é programador de APP
Gustavo	Programação de TI	Serratec	Sem tempo para se engajar.
Gabriel Broitman	Programação	Desenvolvimento da plataforma	Sem tempo para se engajar (SS)
Marcela Souza	Web Design / PUC	Estagnario	Não identificou programador de TI.
Daniel Roberto Santos Pinto	Desenvolvimento de Sistemas - OBD2	Consultor de TI	Laboratório OBD2 Incompleto. (SS)
Prof. Fabio Licht	Modelagem computacional - Coordenador Eng. Computacional UCP	Linhas gerais sobre dispositivos e ferramentas Google Maps para o MC3.	Após o 4º encontro o prof. Não teve mais tempo para o projeto. (SS)
Roberto Sermeno	Google Business	API Google Maps	Indicação da ferramenta API Google para o MC3. (SS)
Cezar Francisco Bolonini	Coordenador de Equipe de Robótica - Kings	Equipe de TI para programar	Não respondeu a solicitação.
Carlos Luiz Paiva	Coordenador de Equipe de Robótica - Elétronsbot	Equipe de TI para programar	Não respondeu a solicitação.
Robson Braga de Andrade	Diretor Sesi Robótica	Equipe de TI para programar	Não respondeu a solicitação.
Sirlei Roieski	BMS	Parceria e rastreamento e medição de CO2	Não há como fazer parceria nesse momento.
Giver de Oliveira	Getrak	Parceria e uso plataforma Iceberg Getrak	Parceria não concretizada sem explicação (SS)
Marcus Tanaka	Angel Investidor e especialista em vendas online	Estagio pre-sede do Projeto MC3	Investimento somente quando a tecnologia estiver pronta em Plano de Negócios.
Jorge Variadan	Prof. Tecnologia de TI Universidade Estácio de Sá	Plataforma digital e equipe técnica	Recursos de cloud Google e AWS.
Mozar Baptista da Silva	Prof. Engenharia da Computação da Universidade Católica de Petrópolis (UCP)	Arquitetura e programação da plataforma Mobilidade C3	Desenvolvimento efetivo da plataforma Mobilidade C3 pela Empresa 11 Tech.
Lucas Zefi	Liaison of IT services for the Ministry of Interior, Bélgica	Construção da Plataforma Mobilidade C3 na Bélgica	Valor pode custar entre EU 60 mil e Eu 100 mil e levar até um ano.
Claudio Teva	Engenheiro Elétrico gestor de Projeto de TI	Arquitetura e programação da plataforma Mobilidade C3	Desenvolvimento efetivo da plataforma Mobilidade C3 pela Empresa 11 Tech.

Table 6. Topics covered and IT experts interviewed

Partnerships

During the PoC, partnerships were sought with computer engineering departments at universities (e.g., PUC and UCP), including partnerships with freelance IT technicians, as well as with vehicle tracking companies that possess expertise in monitoring and security of motor vehicle fleets, such as Getrak, Trimble, and BMS (See Table 6).

Stages of the PoC Laboratory

The Proof of Concept (PoC) Laboratory was divided into three stages: the **Offline Measurement Laboratory**, the **OBD-II Bluetooth Measurement Laboratory**, and the **Prototyping Laboratory**.

Each laboratory stage involved a series of activities that generated important data for the development of the Mobility C3 digital platform. All laboratory stages and the materials produced are described below.

The PoC Laboratory was divided into three stages:

Stage 1 – Offline Measurement Laboratory

This stage was conducted using selected volunteer motor vehicles to validate quantitative calculations and refine data-processing procedures. The variables measured included distance traveled (km), CO₂ emissions based on distance traveled, and the number of trees required to offset carbon emissions.

Annex II-2 contains the logbook records of the seven vehicles analyzed, together with the corresponding data systematization.

Stage 2 – OBD-II Measurement Laboratory

This stage was developed with the voluntary support of IT consultant Daniel. The online measurement laboratory utilized an OBD-II (On-Board Diagnostics) Bluetooth Scanner, specifically the ELM327 Automotive Diagnostic System. This device accesses engine data, diagnostic codes, and vehicle performance information and is widely used in automotive repair workshops and by vehicle owners interested in monitoring vehicle performance. A detailed description of this system is presented later in this document.

Stage 3 – Prototyping Laboratory

This stage was initiated based on interviews and brainstorming sessions conducted with Information Technology (IT) specialists (see tables above) regarding the development of the Mobility C3 Platform technology using the Google Maps platform as its foundation. These discussions contributed to the development of the theoretical methodology underlying the Mobility C3 application, as described later in this document.

Part of this stage was developed in collaboration with the RicsNetwork team, while the remaining activities were carried out in partnership with Professor Fabio Licht from the Department of Information Technology at the Catholic University of Petrópolis (UCP). In both cases, extensive internet-based research was conducted on vehicle-tracking technologies, digital boards, sensors, and carbon-measurement devices designed for installation in vehicle exhaust systems, followed by research on data-acquisition and monitoring devices.

Based on the studies conducted (KBB, 2022; Roieski, 2022; Licht, 2022; Costa et al., 2018; Weng et al., 2017; Carvalho, 2011; FGV, 2004; among others), the following alternatives were identified for calculating CO₂ emissions from motor vehicles powered by petroleum-based fuels:

- 1. Installation of a sensor capable of directly measuring CO₂ emissions at the vehicle exhaust outlet, downstream of the catalytic converter.**

Calculation:

Distance traveled (km) = Corresponding quantity of CO₂ emitted.

- 2. Use of the vehicle's onboard computer system to estimate CO₂ emissions** (applicable primarily to vehicles manufactured after 2015).

Calculation:

Distance traveled (km) = Corresponding quantity of CO₂ emitted.

3. Adoption of a standardized CO₂ emission factor based on fuel consumption.

Example calculation:

$$\text{Emissions} = 50 \times 0.82 \times 0.75 \times 3.7 = 114 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{-eq per week.}$$

4. Use of engine oxygen-consumption data obtained through the OBD-II system to estimate vehicle CO₂ emissions.

Calculation:

The gasoline combustion equation (C₈H₁₈) in relation to oxygen (O₂) is:

Thus, for each unit of gasoline consumed, approximately 12.5 units of oxygen are required.

5. Adoption of a single average CO₂ emission standard applicable to all vehicle types and brands.

Calculation:

$$\text{Distance traveled (km)} \times 170 \text{ g CO}_2\text{/km} = \text{Total CO}_2\text{ emissions.}$$

6. Use of manufacturer-certified CO₂ emissions standards established for each vehicle type, make, and model.

Calculation:

$$\text{Distance traveled (km)} \times \text{Vehicle-specific CO}_2\text{ emission factor (g/km)} = \text{Total CO}_2\text{ emissions.}$$

The Offline Laboratory adopted Alternative 6, utilizing the manufacturer-certified CO₂ emissions standard corresponding to each vehicle make and model included in the study.

Research, Materials, and Data Generated by the Offline Laboratory

In accordance with the project planning instruments (see the Logical Framework and Project Schedule in Annex I-n), volunteer vehicles were selected to participate in the Offline Laboratory. Of the twelve drivers invited to participate, only seven agreed to conduct the measurements over a 15-day monitoring period.

The following table presents the makes and models of the monitored vehicles, their year of manufacture, fuel type, and the manufacturer-certified carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions standard, as shown below.

VEICULO	ANO	COMBUSTIVEL	PADRÃO DE EMISSÃO CO2	FONTE	ESTADO
Veículo 1 - Suzuki / Gran Vitara 1.6 /	2001	Gasolina	200 g/Km	Suzuki	Rio de Janeiro
Veículo 2 - Fiat Palio ELX Flex 1.4, 8v, FLEX	2016	Álcool / gasolina	169,9 g/Km	Fiat	Rio de Janeiro
Veículo 3 - Renault, Sandero, 1.0 12 V, Expression, 2018, FLEX	2018	Álcool / gasolina	93 g/Km	Renault	Amazonas
Veículo 4 - Citroen Picasso Xsara 2.0	2003	Gasolina	199 g/Km	Citroen	Rio de Janeiro
Veículo 5 - Citroen Cactus C4 Shine, 1.98, 170CV / 1598 - 2022	2022	Gasolina	111 g/Km	Citroen	Rio de Janeiro
Veículo 6 - Renault/Sandero Exp 10 16V	2013	Álcool / gasolina	161 g/Km	Renault	Rio Grande do Sul
Veículo 7 - Renault Oroch, 16, camionete 4x2, 120cv/1599, 2021	2021	Álcool / gasolina	120 g/Km	Renault	Ceará

Table 7. Characteristics of the Motor Vehicles Monitored

Each volunteer vehicle selected for the study possesses a manufacturer-certified CO₂ emissions standard established during engine design and testing. Table 7 shows that newer vehicles generally emit lower levels of CO₂, whereas older vehicles tend to contribute higher levels of CO₂ emissions to the atmosphere.

Once the emissions standard for each vehicle had been identified, the distance traveled (km) by each vehicle was monitored in order to estimate the corresponding carbon emissions. The subsequent step consisted of determining the number of trees required to offset the calculated CO₂ emissions.

To achieve this objective, an extensive review of the literature was conducted (Prima, 2020; Embrapa, 2020; Movida, 2019; Braun, 2015; Tonon, 2007; IPCC, 2006; among others) to identify the most appropriate ecological offsetting standard, specifically the average CO₂ sequestration capacity of individual trees in tropical forests. Additional research was also undertaken (Embrapa, 2020; Tonon, 2016; IPCC, 2006; Maderas Nobles, 2008; Santos, 2007) to determine representative carbon sequestration rates per hectare of preserved tropical forest.

Furthermore, a guided interview was conducted with Freitas (2022) to estimate the average number of trees per hectare in native tropical forests, based on research coordinated by the Federal University of Amazonas (IBAMA, n.d.).

The Offline Measurement Laboratory generated individual logbooks for each of the seven monitored volunteer vehicles. These records included the distance traveled (km), estimated CO₂ emissions, and the corresponding ecological compensation requirements expressed as the number of trees to be planted and the area of tropical forest to be preserved (hectares), as illustrated in the example below.

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3							
DADOS DO VEÍCULO: RENAULT, SANDERO, 1.0 12 V, Expression, 2018, FLEX		KILOMETRAGEM			EMISSÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	ÁRVORES/MÊS	Floresta (ha)
18-Mar-22	G	146866	146914	48	9,6	0,0582	0,0001

Table 8. Example of a logbook for measuring motor vehicles.

After 15 days in the laboratory, seven logbooks were obtained, as shown in the tables below. (The complete logbooks are in Appendix III - 2).

Veículo 1

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO										
PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3										
Suzuki / Gran Vitara 1.6 / 2001		KILOMETRAGEM			EMIÇÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA			
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D / GS)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	Nº ÁRVORES	Ha			
18-Mar-22	G	146564	146914	48	9,6	0,0582	0,0001			
19-Mar-22	G	146514	146914	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
20-Mar-22	G	146914	146914	0	0	0	0			
21-Mar-22	G	146914	146914	0	0	0	0			
22-Mar-22	G	146914	146928	14	2,8	0,0170	0,0000			
23-Mar-22	G	146928	146928	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
24-Mar-22	G	146928	146937	9	1,8	0,0109	0,0000			
25-Mar-22	G	146937	146944	7	1,4	0,0085	0,0000			
26-Mar-22	G	146944	146944	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
27-Mar-22	G	146944	146954	10	2	0,0121	0,0000			
28-Mar-22	G	146954	146954	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
29-Mar-22	G	146954	146954	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
30-Mar-22	G	146954	146954	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
31-Mar-22	G	146954	146963	9	1,8	0,0109	0,0000			
1-Apr-22	G	146963	146966	3	0,6	0,0036	0,0000			
		TOTAL	100	20		0,1212	0,0002			

Veículo 2

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO										
PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3										
FIAT PALIO ELX Flex 1.4, 9v, FLEX, 2016		KILOMETRAGEM			EMIÇÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA			
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D / GS)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	Nº ÁRVORES	Ha			
15-Mar-22	G	48733	48778	45	7,65	0,0644	0,0001			
16-Mar-22	G	48778	48778	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
17-Mar-22	G	48778	48806	28	5,1	0,0309	0,0001			
18-Mar-22	G	48806	48821	15	2,7	0,0214	0,0000			
19-Mar-22	G	48821	48841	20	3,4	0,0206	0,0000			
20-Mar-22	G	48841	48852	11	1,87	0,0113	0,0000			
21-Mar-22	G	48852	48883	31	5,27	0,0319	0,0001			
22-Mar-22	G	48883	48920	37	6,29	0,0381	0,0001			
23-Mar-22	G	48920	48949	29	4,93	0,0299	0,0001			
24-Mar-22	G	48949	48957	8	1,36	0,0082	0,0000			
25-Mar-22	G	48957	48970	13	2,21	0,0134	0,0000			
26-Mar-22	G	48970	48991	21	3,57	0,0216	0,0000			
27-Mar-22	G	48991	49001	10	1,7	0,0103	0,0000			
28-Mar-22	G	49001	49038	37	6,29	0,0381	0,0001			
29-Mar-22	G	49038	49080	42	7,14	0,0433	0,0001			
		TOTAL	347	69,4		0,4206	0,0007			

Veículo 3

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO										
PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3										
RENAULT SANDERO, 1.0 12 V, Expression, 2018, FLEX		KILOMETRAGEM			EMIÇÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA			
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D / GS)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	ÁRVORES/MÊS	Floresta (ha)			
14-Mar-22	G	35400	35400	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
15-Mar-22	G	35400	35480	80	7,2	0,0436	0,0001			
16-Mar-22	G	35480	35500	20	1,8	0,0109	0,0000			
17-Mar-22	G	35500	35500	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
18-Mar-22	G	35500	35530	30	2,7	0,0164	0,0000			
19-Mar-22	G	35530	35560	30	1,8	0,0109	0,0000			
20-Mar-22	G	35560	35575	15	1,35	0,0077	0,0000			
21-Mar-22	G	35575	35575	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
22-Mar-22	G	35575	35575	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
23-Mar-22	G	35575	35600	25	2,25	0,0127	0,0000			
24-Mar-22	G	35600	35693	93	8,37	0,0235	0,0000			
25-Mar-22	G	35693	35722	29	2,61	0,0158	0,0000			
26-Mar-22	G	35722	35864	142	12,78	0,0775	0,0001			
27-Mar-22	G	35864	35864	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
28-Mar-22	G	35864	35864	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
		TOTAL	464	92,8		0,5624	0,0005			

Veículo 4

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO										
PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3										
Citroen Picasso Xara 2003, 2.0, gasolina		KILOMETRAGEM			EMIÇÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA			
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D / GS)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	Nº ÁRVORES	Ha			
15-Mar-22	G	150418	150472	54	10,26	0,0622	0,0001			
16-Mar-22	G	150472	150474	2	0,38	0,0023	0,0000			
17-Mar-22	G	150474	150476	2	0,38	0,0023	0,0000			
18-Mar-22	G	150476	150543	67	12,73	0,0772	0,0001			
19-Mar-22	G	150543	150548	5	0,95	0,0058	0,0000			
20-Mar-22	G	150548	150570	22	4,18	0,0253	0,0000			
21-Mar-22	G	150570	150681	111	2,09	0,0127	0,0000			
22-Mar-22	G	150681	150621	40	7,6	0,0461	0,0001			
23-Mar-22	G	150621	150738	117	22,23	0,1347	0,0002			
24-Mar-22	G	150738	150742	4	0,76	0,0046	0,0000			
25-Mar-22	G	150742	150757	15	2,85	0,0173	0,0000			
26-Mar-22	G	150757	150777	20	3,8	0,0230	0,0000			
27-Mar-22	G	150777	150780	3	0,57	0,0035	0,0000			
28-Mar-22	G	150780	150829	49	9,31	0,0564	0,0001			
29-Mar-22	G	150829	150921	92	17,48	0,1059	0,0002			
		TOTAL	503	100,6		0,6097	0,0011			

Veículo 5

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO										
PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3										
CITROEN CACTUS C4 SHINE 1.8, 170CV / 1598 - 2022		KILOMETRAGEM			EMIÇÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA			
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D / GS)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	Nº ÁRVORES	Ha			
7-Mar-22	G	197	267	70	7,7	0,0467	0,0001			
14-Mar-22	G	267	407	140	15,4	0,0933	0,0002			
15-Mar-22	G	407	407	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
16-Mar-22	G	407	407	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
17-Mar-22	G	407	407	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
18-Mar-22	G	407	407	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
19-Mar-22	G	407	649	242	48,4	0,2933	0,0005			
20-Mar-22	G	649	660	11	2,2	0,0133	0,0000			
21-Mar-22	G	660	667	7	1,4	0,0085	0,0000			
22-Mar-22	G	667	671	4	0,8	0,0048	0,0000			
23-Mar-22	G	671	679	8	1,6	0,0097	0,0000			
24-Mar-22	G	679	921	242	48,4	0,2933	0,0005			
25-Mar-22	G	921	931	10	2	0,0121	0,0000			
26-Mar-22	G	931	931	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
27-Mar-22	G	931	1003	72	14,4	0,0873	0,0002			
		TOTAL	736	134,6		0,8158	0,0015			

Veículo 6

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO										
PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3										
Renault/Sandero Exp 10 18V ano 2012 mod 2013 álcool/gasolina		KILOMETRAGEM			EMIÇÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA			
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D / GS)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	Nº ÁRVORES	Ha			
16-Mar-22	G	109073	109137	64	6,74	0,0378	0,0001			
17-Mar-22	G	109137	109132	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
18-Mar-22	G	109132	109132	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
19-Mar-22	G	109132	109155	23	3,68	0,0223	0,0000			
20-Mar-22	G	109155	109253	98	15,36	0,0872	0,0002			
21-Mar-22	G	109253	109306	53	5,6	0,0311	0,0001			
22-Mar-22	G	109306	109381	75	7,8	0,0436	0,0001			
23-Mar-22	G	109381	109479	98	15,68	0,0872	0,0002			
24-Mar-22	G	109479	109494	15	1,5	0,0082	0,0000			
25-Mar-22	G	109494	109523	29	3,04	0,0162	0,0001			
26-Mar-22	G	109523	109523	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
27-Mar-22	G	109523	109539	16	1,6	0,0082	0,0000			
28-Mar-22	G	109539	109623	84	8,8	0,0488	0,0001			
29-Mar-22	G	109623	109623	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
30-Mar-22	G	109623	109745	122	12,8	0,0711	0,0002			
		TOTAL	869	173,8		1,0533	0,0015			

Veículo 7

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO										
PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3										
Renault 1.6 / Orch, Camionete 4x2, 120cv, 2021		KILOMETRAGEM			EMIÇÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA			
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D / GS)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	Nº ÁRVORES	Ha			
23-Apr-22	G	12790	12790	0	0	0,0000	0,0000			
24-Apr-22	G	12790	12797	7	0,84	0,0051	0,0000			
25-Apr-22	G	12797	13003	206	24,72	0,1498	0,0003			
26-Apr-22	G	13003	13091	88	10,56	0,0640	0,0001			
27-Apr-22	G	13091	13171	80	9,6	0,0582	0,0001			
28-Apr-22	G	13171	13254	83	13,28	0,0805	0,0001			
29-Apr-22	G	13254	13340	86	13,76	0,0834	0,0002			
30-Apr-22	G	13340	13395	55	6,8	0,2473	0,0004			
1-May-22	G	13395	13696	301	36,16	0,0979	0,0002			
2-May-22	G	13696	13838	142	22,72	0,1377	0,0003			
3-May-22	G	13838	13839	1	0,16	0,0010	0,0000			
4-May-22	G	13839	13942	103	15,48	0,0999	0,0002			
5-May-22	G	13942	13950	8	1,28	0,0078	0,0000			
6-May-22	G	13950	14075	125	20	0,1212	0,0002			
7-May-22	G	14075	14152	77	18,72	0,1135	0,0002			
		TOTAL	1567	313,4		1,8994	0,0025			

Table 9. Logbooks of the vehicles analyzed (Full logbooks see Annex II - 2).

Step 1 - Offline Measurement Laboratory Data Systematization

The systematization of data from the offline laboratory was essential to compare data between different vehicles. With this, a table was created that summarizes the variables collected from each vehicle, enabling the construction of graphs with systematized data to evaluate performance.

The systematization took into account the km driven and CO2 emitted; the number of trees to be planted; and the preservation of forests in hectares, as organized in the table below.

VEICULO	KM PERCORRIDO	EMIÇÃO DE CO2 Kg	Nº DE ÁRVORES	FLORESTA PRESERVADA Ha
1. Suzuki / Gran Vitara 1.6 / 2001	100	200	0,12	0,0002
2. Fiat 1.4 Palio ELX Flex, 8v, FLEX / 2016	347	69,4	0,42	0,0007
3. Renault, 1.0 Sandero, / 12 V, Expression, 2018, FLEX	464	92,8	0,56	0,0005
4. Citroen Picasso 2.0 / Xsara / 2003	500	100,6	0,60	0,0011
5. Citroen C4 2.0 /Cactus Shine, 1.98, 170CV / 1598 - 2022	736	134,6	0,081	0,0015
6. Renault / Sandero 16V / Flex / Exp 10 / 2013	869	173,8	1,05	0,015
7. Renault 1.6 / Orch / Camionete	1567	120,0	1,9	0,0025
Total	4583	891,2	4,731	0,0215

Table 10. Quantitative synthesis of the offline vehicle laboratory.

Graphs of Systematized Logbook Data

The information presented in the table above was used to generate Cartesian graphs for the comparative analysis of different variables, including distance traveled (km) and CO₂ emissions, the number of trees required for carbon offsetting by each vehicle, and the corresponding area of forest to be preserved for each vehicle.

These graphical representations facilitated the visualization and comparison of the relationships among the monitored variables, supporting the evaluation of vehicle emissions and the ecological compensation requirements associated with each vehicle analyzed.

Figure 1. Graph of CO₂ Emissions Standards by Vehicle

Figure 1 illustrates the manufacturer-certified CO₂ emissions standards for the vehicles included in the study. The results indicate that the Suzuki Grand Vitara and the Citroën Picasso exhibit the highest CO₂ emissions per kilometer traveled, whereas the Renault Sandero and the Citroën Cactus present the lowest emissions levels. This difference is primarily associated with the age and technological efficiency of the vehicles, with newer models generally demonstrating improved fuel efficiency and lower carbon emissions.

The graphs presented below illustrate additional variations and relationships among the variables analyzed in the study.

Figure 2. Graph of Distance Traveled and CO₂ Emissions by Vehicle

Figure 3. Graph of compensation for planting the number of trees per vehicle.

Figure 4. Graph of forest preservation in hectares per vehicle.

Stage 2 – OBD-II Measurement Laboratory

The **ELM327 Bluetooth OBD-II Scanner** is a generic vehicle diagnostic device that communicates via Bluetooth. It is widely used in automotive repair workshops and by drivers interested in monitoring the performance and operational parameters of their vehicles.

Four volunteer vehicles were selected to participate in the OBD-II Measurement Laboratory. The purpose of this stage was to evaluate the potential use of OBD-II technology for monitoring vehicle operating data and assessing its applicability to the Mobility C3 Platform.

The following table presents the characteristics of the vehicles included in the OBD-II laboratory.

VEICULO	ANO	COMBUSTIVEL	PADRÃO DE EMISSÃO CO2	FONTE	ESTADO
Veículo 1 - Suzuki / Gran Vitara 1.6 /	2001	Gasolina	200 g/Km	Suzuki	Rio de Janeiro
Veículo 2 - Fiat Palio ELX Flex 1.4, 8v, FLEX	2016	Álcool /g asolina	169,9 g/Km	Fiat	Rio de Janeiro
Veículo 3 - Renault Duster 2.0 12 V, Expression, 2018, FLEX	2014	Álcool / gasolina	147 g/Km	Renault	Rio de Janeiro
Veículo 4. Honda HR-V 2018 16V 140 cv 1800cc SUV	2018	Álcool / gasolina	120 g/Km	Honda	Rio de Janeiro

Table 11. Characteristics of the Motor Vehicles Monitored Using the OBD-II System

Systematization of Data from the Online Bluetooth OBD-II Laboratory

The laboratory methodology comprised the following activities: identification of four volunteer vehicles for participation in the study; acquisition of an OBD-II device through online suppliers; acquisition and testing of several OBD-II applications available for Android and iOS operating systems (e.g., InfoCar, Kiwi OBD, Torque Pro, EOBD Facile, Torque Car, Car Scanner, and OBD2 Expert); installation of the OBD-II device in the selected vehicles and integration with the mobile applications; evaluation of device performance, measurements, and data outputs; and assessment of the advantages and limitations of the technology.

The OBD-II system is capable of monitoring a wide range of vehicle operating and environmental parameters, including fuel consumption, oxygen levels, engine revolutions per minute (RPM), catalytic converter performance, exhaust-gas sensor data, oxygen sensor readings, NOx/SCR monitoring systems, among other diagnostic variables.

Analysis of the OBD-II Laboratory

The following table summarizes the performance of the OBD-II device when tested on the selected vehicles.

VEICULO	INSTALAÇÃO OBD2	APLICATIVO	MEDIÇÃO	DESEMPENHO
Veículo 1 - Suzuki / Gran Vitara 1.6 /	Realizada	InfoCar	Não	InfoCar não fez a conexão com o OBD2
Veículo 2 - Fiat Palio ELX Flex 1.4, 8v, FLEX	Intalação complicada	Torque Pro	Não	OBD2 não Instalado
Veículo 3 - Renault Duster 2.0 12 V, Expression, 2018, FLEX	Realizada	InfoCar	Sim	Medições foram perdidas devido a acidente com o celular
Veículo 4 . Honda HR-V 2018 16V 140 cv 1800cc SUV	Realizada	TorquePro	Sim	Relatório parcial gerado

Table 12. Synthesis of the OBD2 laboratory with volunteer vehicles.

The table shows that the vehicles listed in Table 12 were evaluated with respect to the ease of OBD-II installation, the application selected for use (following the testing of several alternatives), the successful completion of measurements, and the overall performance of the application in conjunction with the OBD-II device.

The initial analysis indicated that Vehicle 1 was unable to establish a Bluetooth connection between the OBD-II device and the InfoCar application. This limitation was attributed to the vehicle's age (manufactured in 2001), which prevented compatibility with the generic OBD-II scanner. Vehicle 2 presented significant difficulties in accessing the OBD-II diagnostic port, as installation would have required the removal of a substantial portion of the vehicle's front dashboard. Consequently, OBD-II testing was discontinued for both vehicles.

After numerous attempts, only two vehicles (Vehicles 3 and 4) successfully performed measurements using the OBD-II system. However, the driver of Vehicle 3 (Renault Duster) experienced the loss of measurement data after the mobile phone used for data collection was accidentally damaged by water. As a result, only Vehicle 4 (Honda HR-V) generated a

partial measurement report, due primarily to difficulties encountered when recording and exporting data using the Torque Pro application.

The partial report generated from Vehicle 4 is presented below.

Figure 5. OBD2 report from the Torque Pro app.

Stage 3 – Online Prototyping Laboratory

The prototyping laboratory phase began with an extensive review of information available through specialized databases, secondary data sources, and scientific publications. To complement the theoretical research, several technical interviews were conducted with Information Technology (IT) specialists, with the objective of incorporating their expertise into the development of the Mobility C3 Platform (see questionnaires in Annex III-1).

Preliminary Methodology

The preliminary prototyping methodology was developed through collaborative work with the RicNetwork team (Eng. Renan Machado and Richard Siqueira) with the objective of organizing the sequential stages required for the development of the Mobility C3 Platform, as presented in the table below.

ATIVIDADES	OBSERVAÇÃO	EXEMPLO	VISUAL																																																								
<p>1. Definir plataformas de coleta</p> <p>2. Definir sistema de coleta de dados</p>	<p>Dispositivos: 1. Celular; 2. Plug in para rastreador(es) utilizados por empresas de rastreamento (ex. Getrak, Trimble, BMS) e 3. Arduino Uno para ter como referência, no caso de simular a centralização de dados (ex. instalação de rastreador, plataforma / painel de gerenciamento de frota... outros).</p> <p>Outros rastreadores pesquisados anteriormente: Gps Traker Tk-103b; Arduino Gps shield, Raspberry, Apple Air Tag, Rastreador GPS Tk915.</p>	<p>Getrak, qual o melhor rastreador: https://gettrak.com.br/rastreador-veicular/</p> <p>Getrak Vídeo sobre um bom rastreamento precisa: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=geDwo4LqtaU&t=175s</p>																																																									
3. Escolher plataforma para armazenar processar dados	Ex. Google, WS Amazon, outros																																																										
4. Adquirir e instalar dispositivos em veículos	Dispositivos: Celular, Rastreador Gps Traker Tk-103b; Arduino Gps shield, Raspberry, Apple Air Tag, Rastreador GPS Tk915.																																																										
5. Medir percurso e emissão de carbono	<p>Alternativas de Intervalos de medição por GPS. Opções:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Medir integralmente todo trajeto; Medir a cada 2 segundos - 2 metros; Medir a cada 15 Seg. - 15 metros; Medir a cada 25 Seg. - 25 metros; Medir a cada 60 Seg. - 60 metros <p>Pergunta: Se for medir a cada 25 ou 60 metros de intervalo, poderia adicionar um percentual de 20 a 30 % na quantidade de CO2 emitido para compensar a falta de precisão?</p>																																																										
6. Análise de performance laboratorial - Percurso	<p>ANÁLISE DE PERFORMANCE LABORATORIAL - Rota: Rota de coleta - 021</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Nº DE VEÍCULO</th> <th>DISPOSITIVO</th> <th>CENTRO DE PERFORMANCE</th> <th>VEÍCULO / ANO</th> <th>COMPRIMENTOS</th> <th>CO2 E PLATAFORMA</th> <th>OBSERVAÇÕES</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Celular</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Gps Traker Tk-103b</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Arduino Gps shield</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Raspberry</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Apple Air Tag</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Rastreador GPS Tk915</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Outros</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Nº DE VEÍCULO	DISPOSITIVO	CENTRO DE PERFORMANCE	VEÍCULO / ANO	COMPRIMENTOS	CO2 E PLATAFORMA	OBSERVAÇÕES	1	Celular						1	Gps Traker Tk-103b						2	Arduino Gps shield						1	Raspberry						1	Apple Air Tag						1	Rastreador GPS Tk915							Outros							
Nº DE VEÍCULO	DISPOSITIVO	CENTRO DE PERFORMANCE	VEÍCULO / ANO	COMPRIMENTOS	CO2 E PLATAFORMA	OBSERVAÇÕES																																																					
1	Celular																																																										
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1	Raspberry																																																										
1	Apple Air Tag																																																										
1	Rastreador GPS Tk915																																																										
	Outros																																																										
7. Análise de performance laboratorial - CO2	<p>Percurso Km + CO2 emitido</p> <p>Veículo Suzuki Gran Vitara 200gr CO2/Km</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percurso a cada 2 seg. = CO2 emitido; Percurso a cada 15 seg. = CO2 emitido; Percurso a cada 25 seg. = CO2 emitido; Percurso a cada 60 seg. = CO2 emitido; <p>Compensação do percurso não medido.</p> <p>Exemplo:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percurso a cada 25 seg. = CO2 emitido + 15% do total = CO2 real 																																																										
8. Criar sistema de centralização / banco de dados e back-end gerencial	Rota, carbono, árvores	<p>Km 95</p> <p>CO2 170 kg</p> <p>compensação</p> <p>1,03</p>																																																									
	<p>Banco de Dados: de veículos. Marca, modelo, ano, combustível, CO2/Km. Criar banco de dados na nuvem e ir preenchendo a medida que for sendo contratado. (ex. VW Golf GTI; Ford Fiesta; Suzuki Gran Vitara, outros).1616</p>	<p>VEÍCULO 1.1 Golf GTI:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Percurso Km totais: 30,5Km. Tempo de viagem total: 1,3 horas. CO2 emitido no percurso: 5,3 Kg. Compensação - Número de Árvores: 0,029 																																																									
9. Montar protótipo MVP e sistema de monitoramento																																																											

Table 13. C3 Mobility platform development methodology.

Nine methodological activities were defined for the development of the Mobility C3 Platform. One of the principal challenges identified concerned the frequency of vehicle route measurements. The shorter the interval between measurements (e.g., every 1–2 seconds), the more accurate the reconstruction of the vehicle's route and the calculation of distance traveled. Conversely, longer measurement intervals (e.g., 30–60 seconds) reduce the accuracy of the route mapping and distance estimation.

According to Richard Siqueira, storing geographic coordinates in Google's online database platform (Google Firebase) is advantageous because geographic coordinates require relatively little storage capacity and can be managed efficiently within cloud-based systems.

Amazon Web Services (AWS) Platform

A technical interview was conducted with Mr. Paulo Jesus, an IT architect and software developer from RicsNetwork, regarding the use of the Amazon Web Services (AWS) cloud platform (see Annex III-1). During the interview, it was emphasized that the development of the Mobility C3 Platform would require not only software developers but also an IT architect with expertise in AWS cloud infrastructure.

The first step in developing the Mobility C3 Platform would be the establishment of an integrated data collection and management system capable of handling route, carbon emissions, and ecological compensation data. This management back-end would operate through data inputs originating from Arduino-based devices, mobile applications, or vehicle-tracking systems.

Within this context, AWS offers a range of tools suitable for the development of the Mobility C3 Platform, including Amazon EC2 (Compute Services), Amazon RDS (Relational Database Services), Amazon API Gateway, Route 53 (DNS Services), Amazon S3 (100 GB storage), Domain Registration Services, and Amazon CloudFront. The estimated operational cost of these services was approximately R\$730 per month. However, due to the relatively high monthly cost, this alternative was not adopted during the current stage of development.

Analysis of Devices for the Mobility C3 Platform Prototype

The prototyping methodology of the Mobility C3 Platform was developed with the collaboration of Professor Fabio Licht from the Department of Information Technology at the Catholic University of Petrópolis (UCP) (see Annex III-1). The initial phase consisted of brainstorming sessions regarding the Mobility C3 Project, followed by internet-based research aimed at identifying sensors, equipment, and carbon-measurement devices suitable for installation in vehicle exhaust systems.

The research included an assessment of sensors and electronic devices using the following keywords and search terms:

- CO₂ sensors (e.g., infrared sensors and inductive sensors);
- CO₂ probes;
- MQ-135 sensors;
- Arduino Uno boards and Raspberry Pi kits;
- MQ-135 kits;
- Arduino Uno electronic systems;
- FelipeFlop electronic components;
- FelipeFlop educational electronics kits;
- PIC F877 microcontrollers;
- Lambda probes for exhaust-gas measurement; and
- Air-quality monitoring devices.

The research demonstrated that equipment and interfaces are readily available for the construction of carbon dioxide (CO₂) monitoring prototypes, including sensors capable of measuring emissions directly from vehicle exhaust systems downstream of the catalytic converter.

However, it was concluded that the development of one or more prototypes based on the Arduino Uno platform, together with the required measurement components (e.g., lambda probes, wiring systems, fire-resistant materials, and related equipment), would involve relatively high implementation costs, exceeding R\$1,000 per unit. Furthermore, such a solution would partially duplicate functionalities already available through vehicle-tracking systems and onboard vehicle computers currently available in the market.

In addition, the proposed prototype would require extensive testing and validation procedures. According to Professor Licht, a minimum testing period of three months would be necessary to

ensure reliable operation, while six months of testing would be preferable for optimal validation. The development process would comprise three stages:

1. Development of the system interface;
2. Execution of testing and validation procedures; and
3. Iterative refinement through adjustment and error-correction processes.

Google Maps Platform

Based on a technical interview with Roberto Sermeno from Google, it was possible to identify the principal tools required for the development of the Mobility C3 Platform. According to Sermeno, the recommended approach was to utilize Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) available through the Google Maps Platform. (<https://developers.google.com/maps/solutions/transport-tracker>).

For measuring the distance between two geographic points, the **Distance Matrix API** was recommended. At the time of the consultation, the service cost approximately US\$5.00 per 1,000 requests.

Google also offers two additional tools with potential applications for the Mobility C3 Platform: **Google Transport Tracker** and **Google Timeline**. The Google Timeline service records the movement history of a mobile device using any mode of transportation, including automobiles, bicycles, walking, and other forms of travel. These movements can be monitored directly through the user's smartphone.

Google measures and records geographic coordinates at intervals of approximately five seconds, providing a detailed representation of the user's route and travel history. However, certain Google tools and services are available free of charge only for a limited period, typically up to twelve months, after which usage fees may apply.

The figure below presents an example of route tracking using the Google Maps application (Google Timeline) on an Apple mobile device, illustrating the monitoring of a Suzuki Grand Vitara vehicle on October 5, 2022.

Figure 6. Google Timeline of the Suzuki Grand Vitara vehicle.

When the Google Maps application is activated on a mobile device, it enables continuous location tracking through the GPS system. Google Timeline records the historical route traveled by the user, including, in this case, a journey of 74.9 km completed in 5 hours and 4 minutes on October 5, 2022, as illustrated in Figure 6.

As noted above, Google Maps records geographic coordinates at intervals of approximately five seconds. While this frequency provides a reliable representation of vehicle movement, it is less precise than measurements collected at shorter intervals, such as every two seconds. More frequent data collection results in a more accurate reconstruction of the route traveled and a more precise calculation of the total distance covered.

The following figure illustrates this difference in measurement accuracy.

Figure 7. Route measurement intervals and accuracy of actual vehicle displacement.

Figure 7 illustrates that the accuracy of vehicle location tracking is directly influenced by the interval between geographic coordinate measurements. Longer measurement intervals result in lower positional accuracy, whereas shorter intervals provide a more precise representation of the vehicle's route and location.

Once the distance traveled by a vehicle has been determined, the next step is to calculate the corresponding CO₂ emissions generated during the journey, as well as to estimate the number of trees required to offset those emissions. Figure 8 presents an example of the graphical outputs proposed for each monitored vehicle, including distance traveled, estimated CO₂ emissions, and the corresponding ecological compensation requirements.

Figure 8. Illustration of the graphical evolution of CO₂ emissions and trees planted.

Google Timeline and Eco-Friendly Routing

Eco-friendly routing is a feature available through the latest Routes API of the Google Maps Platform (Google Maps Platform, 2022). This functionality enables users to make more sustainable travel decisions by identifying routes that optimize energy efficiency and potentially reduce fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. Drivers can specify the type of vehicle engine and receive route recommendations based on estimated energy efficiency.

According to Licht (2022) and Machado and Siqueira (2021), calculating CO₂ emissions and estimating the number of trees required for carbon offsetting necessitates the establishment of a robust data-management infrastructure. This includes selecting appropriate data-collection devices (e.g., smartphones, Arduino Uno kits, or Raspberry Pi systems), defining a cloud-computing platform for data storage and processing (e.g., Google Cloud services), and implementing a centralized data-management system capable of integrating route, carbon emissions, and ecological compensation information.

In practical terms, CO₂ emissions and the number of trees required for offsetting can initially be calculated using spreadsheet-based systems (e.g., Microsoft Excel or Apple Numbers), similar to the methodology adopted in Table 8. These calculations can subsequently be integrated into the management back-end of the Mobility C3 Platform, which will be responsible for processing and managing all operational data.

According to Professor Fabio Licht (UCP), this system must undergo extensive testing and validation to ensure reliability and operational accuracy, particularly if it is to be deployed commercially for the monitoring of corporate vehicle fleets.

Online Prototyping MVP Laboratory of the Mobility C3 Platform Developed by 11Tech

The development of the final prototyping methodology was carried out through collaborative work with the IT company 11Tech, coordinated by Professor Mozar Baptista da Silva from the Computer Engineering Department of the Catholic University of Petrópolis (UCP), IT Project Manager Claudio Tava, and Engineer Edric Vila Campo Borges.

The initial methodology consisted primarily of a series of in-person and online meetings aimed at discussing the concepts, objectives, and technical requirements of the Mobility C3 Platform. Particular attention was given to the challenge of developing the Mobility C3 technology within a limited timeframe and under budget constraints.

The second stage involved the submission of the proposed platform screens and visual layouts (pictorial representations) by the Mobility C3 team to 11Tech. These visual prototypes served as the basis for discussions regarding the platform architecture, functionality, user interface design, and software development requirements (see Table 13. Methodology for the Development of the Mobility C3 Platform).

ASPECTOS OPERACIONAIS	DESAFIOS	POSSÍVEIS SOLUÇÕES
1. Usuário deve ligar o aplicativo manualmente.	Usuário esqueceu de ligar o aplicativo manualmente	O aplicativo dá um alerta quando o veículo se deslocou acima de 15 Km / hora
2. Usuário deve passar o celular na etiqueta NFC para acionar o aplicativo e para fechar o aplicativo.	Usuário não passou o celular na etiqueta NFC	O aplicativo dá um alerta quando o veículo se deslocou acima de 15 Km / hora
3. Usuário deve conectar um cabo USB no veículo para iniciar medida do aplicativo.	Usuário não conectou o cabo USB	O aplicativo dá um alerta quando o veículo se deslocou acima de 15 Km / hora
4. O aplicativo mede os deslocamentos no back-ground sem ele ter sido aberto.	Usuário esqueceu de ligar o aplicativo manualmente	O Aplicativo mede o deslocamento do veículo e armazena dados.
5. O veículo dentro de um engarrafamento com o motor ligado (ex. Para- anda) emitindo CO2. Velocidade média Km 15 / hora.	Como medir a emissão de CO2 durante o engarrafamento?	Básico: Considerar os Km percorridos e descartar o tempo no engarrafamento
6. O veículo dentro de um engarrafamento com o motor ligado (ex. Para- anda) emitindo CO2. Velocidade média Km 15 / hora.	Como medir a emissão de CO2 durante o engarrafamento?	Avançado: Premissa: Menor aceleração do veículo, menor emissão. Solução: Reduzir a emissão padrão do veículo entre 20% a 30% durante o engarrafamento.
7. Usuário leva o celular no bolso e pega carona com outro veículo...	Como distinguir o veículo usual do novo veículo que pegou carona?	Aplicativo não mede Km no novo veículo... Aplicativo distingue a velocidade média do veículo usual versus a velocidade média do novo veículo...
8. Durante a medição do deslocamento do veículo, o celular perde conexão com os satélites, ou da um tila como acontece com o Google Maps ou Ways em locais com muito desvios.	Um trecho do percurso não foi mensurado (ex. Km e emissão de CO2). Exemplo: 10 Km não medidos 100 Km não medido	Se for um percurso relativamente curtos (ex.10 Km desconsiderar). Se for um percurso maior (ex. 100 Km) proceder com o cálculo manual....e fazer um in put de dados no aplicativo.
9. Veículo automotor sem padrão de emissão de CO2 estabelecido pelo fabricante.	Como definir a emissão do veículo?	Identificar veículo com características de motor semelhantes e definir a emissão padrão de CO2.
10. Cálculo do valor cumulativo de CO2 do veículo monitorado.	Como calcular o volume cumulativo de CO2 emitido durante período de tempo.	Definir somatória cumulativa do veículo no período semanal, mensal e semestral.
11. Lista de ONGS e Empresas Florestais	Como fazer o link para compensação	A se pensar...
12. Outros		

Figure 9. Example of Platform screens as planned by company 11 Tech.

The third stage consisted of the submission by 11Tech of a Commercial Proposal based on the screen layouts and platform concepts presented by the Mobility C3 team. The proposal outlined the scope of prototype development, including compliance with the specifications of the preliminary project, the planned functionalities, and the proposed screen sketches (see Contract in Annex III-6).

The fourth stage involved aligning the 11Tech proposal with the objectives and operational requirements of the Mobility C3 Platform. Through a series of brainstorming sessions, it was possible to simulate the operational functioning of the platform and identify potential challenges that could arise during its development and implementation.

To support this analysis, a table entitled “**Operational Aspects of the Application**” was developed. The table summarizes the principal operational challenges identified during the planning process, together with potential solutions and mitigation strategies, as presented below.

Table 14. Operational aspects, challenges and practical solutions of the C3 Mobility Platform.

The fifth stage involved the preparation and execution of a **Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA)** between 11Tech and Mobility C3. The confidentiality agreement was established to protect

proprietary information, technical concepts, business strategies, methodologies, and other sensitive data exchanged during the development of the Mobility C3 Platform.

The sixth stage consisted of the preparation of a **Specific Prototype Development Schedule** for the Mobility C3 Platform. This schedule was designed to complement and align with the overall Mobility C3 Project Schedule, detailing the activities, milestones, deliverables, responsibilities, and timelines specifically associated with the design, architecture, programming, testing, and validation of the platform prototype.

CRONOGRAMA DA PLATAFORMA MOBILIDADE C3 E ATIVIDADES DA 11 TECH

CRONOGRAMA DO PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3 RICARDO BRAUN, FAPERJ/ INCUBADORA LNCC / 11 TECH		2023																
RESULTADOS (R)	ATRIBUIÇÃO	INICIO / Nº DIAS	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D	J	F	M	A
FASE 1 - PESQUISA E TECNOLOGIA																		
R3 - MODELO DA PLATAFORMA DESENVOLVIDO	11 Tech																	
- 4.01 - Tabelas de domínio : - Cadastro da empresa (frota) / autenticação - Veículos com CRUD - parte adm. - Empresas de plantio (ONGs) com CRUD - parte adm.	11 Tech	5/1/23 30D																
- 4.02 - Rotas e percursos determinados - a partir do GPS e deslocamento do veículo - via aplicativo em celular.	11 Tech																	
- 4.02.1 - Tabela de histórico de viagem (sem georeferenciamento) - (placa veículo - data e hora start; data hora fim, km rodado, se compensado ou não o carbono deste lançamento, qual empresa carbono);	11 Tech / R. Braun	5/2/23 60D																
- 4.03 - Cálculos efetivos e volumes em CO ² gerados	11 Tech / R. Braun	15/2/23 70D																
- 4.04 - Seleção de empresa de plantio	11 Tech / R. Braun	5/3/23 90D																
- 4.05 - Dados de contato empresa de plantio.	11 Tech / R. Braun																	
R4 - PARCERIAS FLORESTAIS IMPLEMENTADAS	R. Braun																	
R5 - PESQUISA DE MERCADO	R. Braun																	
R6 - PLANO DE NEGÓCIOS DA EMPRESA	R. Braun																	
R7 - RELATÓRIO TÉCNICO PARCIAL	R. Braun																	
R8 - PARCERIAS TECNOLÓGICA / COMERCIAL	R. Braun																	
R9 - EMPRESA MOBILIDADE C3 MONTADA	R. Braun																	
R10 - MOBILIDADE C3 DIVULGADA	R. Braun																	
R11 - PLATAFORMA ATUALIZADA	11 Tech / R. Braun																	
R12 AVALIAÇÃO II & RELATÓRIO TÉCNICO FINAL	R. Braun																	

Table 15. 11Tech's work schedule with Mobility C3.

The seventh stage consisted of a series of online meetings with the architect of the Mobility C3 Platform, Engineer Edric Villa Campos Borges, the specialist responsible for designing the platform architecture and implementing its software development.

During the prototype phase, it was determined that each vehicle user would require a unique password and vehicle license plate registration to ensure proper vehicle identification and user authentication. Vehicle trips would be measured using two complementary methods: GPS-based tracking through geolocation services (e.g., Google Distance Matrix API) and the manual entry of the vehicle's initial and final odometer readings to determine the distance traveled.

The eighth stage involved the preparation of calculation formulas in spreadsheet format (Microsoft Excel) to estimate the distance traveled (km), calculate CO₂ emissions, determine the ecological

compensation required through tree planting, estimate the corresponding area of preserved forest (hectares), and calculate the carbon credits necessary for offsetting emissions, as illustrated below.

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO								
PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3								
Suzuki / Gran Vitara 1.6 / 2001		KILOMETRAGEM			EMISSÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	FLORESTA NATIVA	CREDITOS DE CARBONO
DATA	COMBUSTIVEL	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	Nº ÁRVORES	ha	Ton
18-Mar-22	G	146866	146914	48	9,6	0,0485	0,0001	0,0096

Table 16. Calculation formulas for Km, CO2, number of trees, native forest and carbon credits in a spreadsheet.

The detailed formulas are in Annex III - 5.

In this stage, the company 11 Tech created an HTML data entry form for the monitored vehicles on the C3 Mobility Platform, where data from the monitored vehicles is entered, as shown in the following figure.

Figure 10. HTML for monitored vehicle data.

The subsequent stage involved the development of the domain tables and the development environment required for the creation of the application responsible for monitoring distance traveled (km), CO₂ emissions, and ecological compensation through the calculation of the number of trees to be planted, hectares of forest to be preserved, and carbon credits to be offset.

The next step consisted of developing the application itself, including route and trip management functionalities, as well as the creation of a travel-history database capable of storing and retrieving records associated with vehicle journeys, CO₂ emissions monitoring, and ecological compensation activities.

To support these functionalities, a database architecture was designed to manage user information, vehicle identification data, route records, distance measurements, emissions calculations, ecological compensation metrics, and historical travel information. The resulting database schema is presented below.

Figure 11. Diagram of the C3 Mobility database.

At this stage, a comprehensive CO₂ emissions database was also developed, incorporating vehicle makes, models, and versions from an official registry containing more than one thousand vehicles published by the Brazilian National Institute of Metrology, Quality and Technology (Inmetro) under the Brazilian Vehicle Labeling Program. The database was structured using the CO₂ emissions values established by IBAMA, which quantify tailpipe emissions associated with fossil-fuel combustion in motor vehicles (Inmetro, 2020).

This database became a fundamental component of the Mobility C3 Platform, providing the reference emissions standards required to estimate CO₂ emissions based on vehicle type, make, model, and version. The incorporation of official emissions data enhanced the reliability and consistency of the platform's carbon accounting methodology and reduced the need for manual user input regarding fuel consumption and vehicle performance characteristics.

Table: CarVersion		
Column	Data type	Constraints
Id	INTEGER	*PRIMARY KEY AUTOINCREMENT *NOT NULL
IdModel	int	
Name	VARCHAR	*NOT NULL
GramsPerKm	INTEGER	*NOT NULL
Global table constraints		
*FOREIGN KEY (IdModel) REFERENCES Model(Id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE		

Table: Vehicle		
Column	Data type	Constraints
Id	INTEGER	*PRIMARY KEY AUTOINCREMENT *NOT NULL
IdCompany	int	
IdCarVersion	int	
Plate	VARCHAR	*NOT NULL
Password	CHAR	*NOT NULL
Global table constraints		
*FOREIGN KEY (IdCompany) REFERENCES Company(Id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE		
*FOREIGN KEY (IdCarVersion) REFERENCES CarVersion(Id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE		

Table: CarVersion				
#	Id	IdModel	Name	GramsPerKm
	INTEGER	int	VARCHAR	INTEGER
0	1	1	1.0-12V Look	98
1	2	1	1.0-12V Look Plus	98
2	3	1	1.0-12V Smile	98
3	4	1	1.0-12V Smile Plus	98
4	5	1	1.0-12V Act	98
5	6	1	1.0-12V ACT Plus	98
6	7	2	1.0-6V Drive	88
7	8	2	1.0-6V Drive GSR	89
8	9	2	1.0-6V Easy	92
9	10	2	1.0-6V Like	99
10	11	2	1.0-6V Way	100
11	12	2	1.0-6V Easy	99
12	13	3	1.0-6V Drive	94
13	14	3	1.0-6V Attractive	108
14	15	3	1.0-6V Way	94
15	16	4	Elétrico Intense	0
16	17	5	1.0-12V MPI	89
17	18	6	1.0-12V Connect 170TSI	88
18	19	6	1.0-12V Xtreme 170TSI	93
19	20	7	1.5-12V SP	105
20	21	7	2.0-16V S 5P	105
21	22	7	1.5-12V	106
22	23	8	1.0-12V Conforto	96
23	24	8	1.0-12V S	96
24	25	8	1.0-12V SV	96
25	26	8	1.6-16V S	99
26	27	8	1.6-16V SV	99
27	28	8	1.6-16V SL	99
28	29	8	1.6-16V SV	104
29	30	8	1.6-16V SL	104
30	31	8	1.6-16V Sedt	104
31	32	9	1.0-12V S	92
32	33	9	1.0-12V SE	92
33	34	9	1.0-12V SE Plus	92
34	35	9	1.0-12V FreeStyle	90

Figure 12. Part of the vehicle and CO2 emission table from Mobility C3.

Additional laboratory data related to the architecture and software development of the Mobility C3 Platform will be generated and reported to FAPERJ during this final phase of application development.

According to 11Tech, the platform prototype is essentially equivalent to the final version of the Mobility C3 Platform, with only final validation and refinement activities remaining. Following the completion of the prototype, short-term field tests will be conducted using volunteer vehicles to measure, validate, and generate reports for the parameters listed in Table 16. These tests will assess the platform's operational performance, identify potential issues, and support the implementation of any necessary corrections and adjustments.

Upon successful completion of the testing and validation process, the Mobility C3 Platform is expected to be fully operational and ready for commercialization within the Brazilian carbon market. The platform will provide vehicle emissions monitoring services integrated with ecological compensation mechanisms, including tree planting, forest conservation, and carbon-credit offsetting through strategic partnerships with environmental organizations and carbon-compensation providers.

ANNEX I – 3

2.3. Methodology for Result 3 – Mobility C3 Platform Model

During this phase, several activities were carried out that were closely interconnected with the previous Proof of Concept (PoC) Laboratory stage.

Questionnaires

As noted previously, throughout the PoC laboratory activities, numerous technical consultations were conducted with Information Technology (IT) specialists. During these interactions, semi-structured questionnaires (Kitchin et al., 2000) were administered with the objective of guiding and supporting the development of the Mobility C3 Platform (see completed questionnaires in Annex III-1).

Efforts were also made to establish technical partnerships with university departments specializing in Computer Engineering, independent IT consultants, and vehicle-tracking companies possessing expertise in fleet monitoring and security systems (e.g., Getrak, BMS, and Trimble). In addition, partnerships were developed with forestry organizations and environmental companies that are expected to form the network of carbon-offset providers to be integrated into the Mobility C3 Platform.

Prototyping MVP Laboratory

Based on the collaborative work conducted with RicsNetwork during 2020 and 2021, nine methodological activities were defined for the development of the Mobility C3 Platform, taking into consideration both **User Experience (UX)** and **User Interface (UI)** design principles (see Table 17).

From a preliminary design perspective, the platform was conceived to integrate digital maps and real-time vehicle location data with key environmental variables, including distance traveled (km), CO₂ emissions, number of trees required for carbon offsetting, forest conservation area, and carbon credits. These elements were designed to be presented through intuitive and user-friendly interfaces, facilitating ease of use and efficient interpretation of environmental performance indicators, as illustrated in the examples presented below.

Figure 13. Preliminary example of UI and UX design of the Mobility C3 platform.

In the example above, the first figure illustrates a map displaying the route of the monitored vehicle together with indicators for distance traveled (km), CO₂ emissions, and the number of trees required for carbon offsetting. The second figure presents a map of the biome where the ecological compensation activities, such as tree planting, will be implemented. The third figure displays a list of companies and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) responsible for tree planting, forest conservation initiatives, or the provision of carbon-credit services.

The numerous meetings conducted with the management team of 11Tech made it possible to refine important aspects of the platform screens and to define key elements of the architecture and software development process of the Mobility C3 Platform. Through brainstorming sessions, the operational use of the platform was simulated, enabling the identification of functional requirements, potential challenges, and opportunities for improvement.

The visual design stages of the Mobility C3 Platform were conceptualized through a combination of creative design processes and the analysis of existing vehicle-monitoring applications, particularly the Fleet application. These references contributed to the development of a user-centered interface and operational workflow, as illustrated in the examples presented below.

ATIVIDADES (A)	OBSERVAÇÃO	EXEMPLO	VISUAL
9. Montar protótipo MVP e sistema de monitoramento.			
10. Criar a interface dos usuários (UI e UX); funcionalidade e visualizações.	Settings da Plataforma 1. Log In 2. Identificação do Veículo 3. N° do Celular: 4. Idioma (Português e Inglês) 5. Sobre o Mobilidade C3® 6. Outros		
11. Identificação do Veículo	1. Placa: Detran Alfanumérico 2. Marca: 3. Modelo: 4. Ano: 5. Combustível: 6. CO ₂ / Km: 7. Data do início das medições:	Se for frota de veículos os dados se repetem para cada veículo da frota. Para cada frota uma pasta de arquivo.	

Table 17. Preliminary screens and UI and UX development methodology for the C3 Mobility platform.

In summary, the basic methodology of the Mobility C3 UI and UX model is described as follows:

- Design the screens intended for use in the application in order to build the prototype architecture.
- Vehicle registration: record the vehicle brand, year of manufacture, fuel type, and factory-standard CO₂ emissions.
- Select and deploy the platform on a cloud-based server (e.g., the Heroku platform).
- Configure the mobile device for registration and data collection. Authentication may be performed through a password, vehicle license plate, or NFC tag to initiate measurement within the vehicle. For example, upon entering the vehicle, the user activates the entry NFC tag to launch the application on the mobile device. Upon leaving the vehicle, the user activates the exit NFC tag to terminate the measurement process.
- Develop an administrative website to monitor data transmitted from mobile devices. Each mobile device functions as a client. The administrative platform should define the information to be

displayed to administrators and/or users. Examples include vehicle mileage, CO₂ emissions generated, and the number of trees to be planted or effectively planted.

Note: The mobile device collects vehicle travel data and transmits it to the server (e.g., Heroku).

f. Establish a simple access-control mechanism within the platform.

g. System testing may be conducted through a dedicated testing program developed in parallel with the main platform. This testing environment enables platform validation as well as system maintenance activities.

Finally, according to 11 Tech, the testing program is more costly because it essentially involves two programs operating in parallel. However, its primary advantage is that it enables the application to achieve a high level of security and reliability. This testing methodology has been employed by 11 Tech in several projects, including the Brazilian National High School Examination (ENEM) testing system, aircraft onboard systems, Petrobras' underwater rover systems, banking applications, among others.

ANNEX I – 4

2.4. Method for Outcome 4 – Forest Partnerships

Research

Initially, it is important to reiterate that this research is relevant because the data generated will be incorporated into the Mobility C3 digital platform as a basis for calculating carbon offsetting measures for its clients.

According to Embrapa (2022b), photosynthesis is the process through which plants, autotrophic organisms (organisms capable of producing their own food), and certain other organisms convert light energy into chemical energy by processing carbon dioxide (CO₂), water (H₂O), and minerals into organic compounds while producing gaseous oxygen (O₂). The simplified equation of the process corresponds to glucose formation:

Therefore, in addition to sequestering carbon from the atmosphere, plants and forests release oxygen into the atmosphere, representing an additional environmental service that can be economically valued (UNEP / Katoomba Group, 2008; Costanza et al., 1998).

Research conducted from multiple sources (Freitas, 2022; Prima, 2020; Embrapa, 2020a; Embrapa, 2020b; Movida, 2019; Braun, 2015; MMA, 2012; Tonon, 2007; Santos, 2007; Imazon; IBF, 2022; Movida, 2022; among others) enabled the development of an ecological compensation framework, facilitating the organization and systematization of the ecological compensation landscape in Brazil. This process made it possible to define, with greater accuracy, the carbon sequestration rate per tree from the time of planting and throughout the first 20 years of its development.

The table below summarizes the indices identified through the research.

HECTARES	Nº DE ÁRVORES	BIOMA	QUANTIDADE ABSORVIDO CO2 Kg	TEMPO Anos	FONTE
	1	Brasil	165	-	Maderas Nobles, 2008.
	1	FLORESTA TROPICAL	15,5	1	IPCC, 2006
	1	FLORESTA TROPICAL	300	20	IPCC, 2006
	1	MATA ATLANTICA	200	21	Prima, 2020
	1	FLORESTA Brasil	180	-	Tonon, 2007 / 2016
	1	MATA ATLANTICA	4,3/ano	30	Manfrinato, et al, 2016
	1	AMAZÔNIA	7,4/ano	30	Manfrinato, et al, 2016
	1	Brasil	1.000	Vida Toda	Embrapa, 2022
	1	Brasil	180	-	Tonon, 2007 / 2016
	1	MATA ATLANTICA	130 Kg CO2-eq	30	Manfrinato, et al, 2016
	1	FLORESTA AMAZONICA	222 Kg CO2-eq	30	Manfrinato, et al, 2016
			1 tonelada de Carbono (C) estocada na floresta, equivale a 3,7 toneladas de CO2-eq sequestrado da atmosfera.		
	5	MATA ATLANTICA	1 Ton	21	Prima, 2020
	5	Brasil	828	-	Maderas Nobles, 2008.
	7	MATA ATLANTICA	1 Ton	21 (?)	Movida , 2019
	10	MATA ATLANTICA	1 Ton	10,5	Prima / Ric (2022)
	550	FLORESTA TROPICAL	4 Ton	1	Braun, 2015

Table 18. Researched patterns of forest carbon sequestration compensation.

Forest Graphs

Based on the table above, the analysis of different authors made it possible to develop graphs representing average patterns of atmospheric carbon sequestration for the formation of plant biomass. The graph below focuses on tropical forests (Atlantic Forest or Amazon Rainforest) and refers to the carbon sequestration of a single tree over a period of 20 to 30 years.

Figure 14. Carbon sequestration patterns (Kg) by vegetation.

Based on several selected authors, a graph representing forest conservation in hectares (ha) was also developed. The graph adopts as its standard metric the amount of carbon, expressed in tonnes, that one hectare (1 ha) of preserved forest can sequester over a 20-year period.

Figure 15. Sequestration in tons of carbon in 1 hectare of tropical forest (Atlantic Forest).

UI and UX Methodology for Forest Partnerships

Unlike the User Interface (UI) and User Experience (UX) methodology adopted by the Mobility C3 Platform, which measures distance traveled (km) and CO₂ emissions, the UI and UX methodology developed for the ecological compensation activities of forest partners considered aspects related to forest conservation, tree planting, geolocation of planted areas, and monitoring tree growth throughout the first 20 years of development, as presented in the table below.

Considering the projected gigatonnes of carbon emissions generated by the Brazilian vehicle fleet, a substantial number of forest partners will be required to meet the demand for tree planting, both Forest Partners and Carbon Offset Providers

One of the objectives of the Mobility C3 Project is to establish a network of tree-planting organizations and/or forest management institutions operating across different Brazilian biomes in order to effectively offset the carbon emissions generated by motor vehicles monitored through the Mobility C3 Platform. In other words, forest partnerships are essential to enable Mobility C3 Platform clients to contract carbon offset services provided by forestry organizations, forestry companies, and carbon offset providers.

to support the restoration of approximately 1.2 million km² of degraded areas across different biomes and to offset carbon emissions.

Initially, a survey and assessment of various potential forest partners engaged in tree-planting activities throughout Brazil was conducted. Subsequently, an analysis was carried out focusing

specifically on organizations and companies involved in the generation and commercialization of carbon credits.

ATIVIDADES	DADOS	OBSERVAÇÃO	VISUAL
Settings da Parceiros Florestais	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nome da Empresa / Organização 2. Link web da Empresa / Organização. 3. Pessoa de contato: 4. Celular da pessoa de contato. 5. Geo-localização da empresa / organização. 	<p>Foto plantando</p>	
Compensação Ecológica	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Geo-localização dos locais de plantio de árvores. 	<p>Coordenadas geográficas UTM</p> <p>Lat Long -2.964984,-51.973267</p>	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Área plantada em hectares (ha) 	<p>2,5 ha</p> <p>Lat Long -2.964984,-51.973267</p>	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Comprovação da área plantada 	<p>Garantia que as árvores foram plantadas e que estão sendo manejadas e, mantidas vivas pelos 21 anos.</p> <p>Foto com coordenadas, localização e data (Ex. App Timelapse).</p>	<p>Foto do local de plantio de árvores.</p>

Table 19. Methodological steps for planting and silvicultural (ecological) management of trees.

The forest partners were classified into two groups: (i) forestry companies that plant trees, manage forest assets, and operate in the market for the production and commercialization of timber and timber-related products; and (ii) non-governmental organizations (NGOs) that develop silvicultural projects aimed at restoring degraded areas, promoting forest restoration, or planting trees for carbon offset purposes.

During this stage, contacts were also established with vehicle-tracking companies, including Getrak, BMS, and Trimble, in order to assess their CO₂ measurement systems and carbon offset practices. It was found that these companies do not currently operate carbon offset schemes.

Questionnaires

To establish the network of forestry organizations and companies, an initial internet-based survey was conducted, followed by the development and application of semi-structured questionnaires (Kitchin et al., 2000). The objective was to assess both the qualitative and quantitative capacities of these organizations with respect to tree-planting activities. The semi-structured questionnaires also served as a basis for collecting data regarding carbon offset potential and the costs associated with the services to be provided. The questionnaires are presented in **Annex III - 3**.

Initially, 15 questionnaires were distributed to non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and 9 questionnaires to major forestry companies operating across different Brazilian biomes.

The list of NGOs engaged in carbon offsetting, forest restoration, and the conservation of native forests across the various Brazilian biomes, which were contacted to respond to the semi-structured questionnaires, is presented below.

ONG	RESPONSÁVEL	CARGO	CONTATO
PRIMA, RJ.	Ricardo Harduim	Diretor	WhatsApp (21) 99962-1922 harduim.ricardo@gmail.com
SOS Amazônia, AM.	Álison S. Maranhão	Diretor Técnico	Celular 68 3223 1036 68 99214 0393 alisson@sosamazonia.org.br
GAMBA, BA.	Renato Cunha	Diretor	Email: renato@gamba.org.br
Etnia Planetária, RS.	Sieli	Diretora Financeira e de Assuntos Internacionais	Email: etniaplanetaria@etniaplanetaria.org
Projeto Saúde e Alegria, AM.	Fale Conosco	Coordenação	Celular: +55 93 3067-8000 / +55 93 99143-1091, Email: psa@saudeealegria.org.br
Instituto Peabiru, PA.	Fale Conosco	Coordenação	Celular: (91) 3222-6000 Email: peabiru@peabiru.org.br
Iniciativa Verde, SP.	Fale Conosco	Coordenação	Celular: (11) 3647.9293 / (11) 3647.9296 Email: contato@iniciativaverde.org.br
Instituto Floresta Viva, BA.	Fale Conosco	Coordenação	Celular: 73 3634 3526 Email: contato@florestaviva.org.br
Instituto Curicaca	Fale Conosco	Coordenação	Te. (51) 3332-0489 Email: curicaca@curicaca.org.br
ONG	RESPONSÁVEL	CARGO	CONTATO
Sociedade SPVS, PR.	Fale Conosco	Coordenação	Tel.: +55 (41) 3094-4600 Email: spvs@www.spvs.org.br
Instituto IPÊ, SP.	Fale Conosco	Coordenação	Tel.: +55 (41) 3094-4600 Email: ipe@ipe.org.br
Instituto Apremavi, SC.	Fale Conosco	Coordenação	Tel. (47) 3535-0119/ 98855-7323 Email: info@apremavi.org.br
Associação Cerrado de Pé, GO.	Fale Conosco	Coordenação	Tel.:(62) 99901-7268 Email: cerradodepe@gmail.com
SOS Mata Atlântica	Rafael	Contato	Tel.: (11) 3262-4088 Email: rafael@sosma.org.br
Restaura Brasil / TNC	Claudia Picone	Marketing	Tel: +55 (48) 99933 1545 Email: cpicone@TNC.ORG

Table 20. List of NGOs surveyed and contacted.

The nine large forestry companies surveyed and contacted to respond to the semi-structured questionnaire are listed below.

ORG. / EMPRESA	RESPONSÁVEL	CARGO	CONTATO
Klabin, PR, ES	Francisco C.Razzolini Júlio César Batista Nogueira	Diretor de Tecnologia Industrial	Tel.:08007187814 Email: rs@klabin.com.br ouvidoria@klabin.com.br planteco@klabin.com.br maklabinsc@klabin.com.br
Suzano	Fale Conosco Walter Schalka, presidente	Suzano Planin	Tel.: +55 (11) 2138-8919 e (11) 98937-6717 Email: ecofuturo@ecofuturo.org.br oresponde@suzano.com.br
Cenibra	Sandro Moraes	Coordenação	Tel. 08002833829 Email: sandro.morais@cenibra.com.br
A Mata, AM, PR,	Fale Conosco	Coordenação	Tel.: Email: corporativo@amatabrasil.com.br
Mil Madeiras, AM Grupo Precious Wood, SW	Fale Conosco (+330 million CO2 T 1.1 million ha tropical forests under long- term preservation)	Coordenação	Tel.: (+55 92 99136-5045 / +55 92 99136-5066 +55 92 98533-1664 / +55 92 98533-1682 Email: contato@milmadeiraspreciosas.com.br
ORG. / EMPRESA	RESPONSÁVEL	CARGO	CONTATO
Rigess Westrock, ES	Donald H. Thompson		Tel: +55 27 3250-1396 Email: donald.hunton@metacs.com.br meta@metacs.com.br
Futuro Florestal, SP	Fale Conosco	Coordenação	Tel:(14) 98128-2230 (14) 99761-0165 (11) 4780-4391Email: contato@futuroflorestal.com.br
Futuro Florestal, SP	Eduardo Ciriello Diretor Técnico		VIVEIRO FLORESTAL Fazenda Enseada Rural - Garça / São Paulo CEP: 17400-000 Telefone: (14) 99761-0165 (11) 4780-4391
ImaFlora Certificações	Marina Jordão	Comunicação	Tel. (19) 3429-0812.; 19) 3429-0822 Email: marina.jordao@imaflora.org Email: qualidade@imaflora.org imaflora@imaflora.org

Table 21. List of forestry companies surveyed and contacted.

Carbon Credits

The concept of carbon credits emerged with the Kyoto Protocol in 1997. The purpose of carbon credits is to contribute to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions; however, it was only after the adoption of the Paris Agreement in 2015 that the commercialization of carbon credits became a more pressing issue. In practice, one carbon credit represents one tonne of carbon dioxide that has not been emitted into the atmosphere. The most common method of trading carbon credits is through the direct commercialization of emission reductions. With the growing emphasis on sustainability initiatives, the carbon trading market has become highly profitable. Between 2018 and 2021, for example, this market increased in value by 187%, considering the units traded under the European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) (CredCarbo, n.d.).

EMPRESA	RESPONSAVEL	CARGO	CONTATO
Prima, RJ	Ricardo Harduim	Diretor	WhatsApp (21) 99962-1922 harduim.ricardo@gmail.com
Carbon Free, SP	Germano Fortkamp	Diretor	germano@carbonfreebrasil.com +55 11 4935-0177
EcoBraz, SP	Henrique Machado	Gerente Comercial	(11) 4329-2001 henrique.machado@ecobraz.org.br R. Dona Maria Quedas, 230 - Jardim Andaraí, São Paulo - SP, 02175-010
Way Carbon, MG	Ana Correa- Patricia Merola Luis Marques	Assessora de Imprensa	patricia.merola@waycarbon.com luis.marques@waycarbon.com ana.correa@waycarbon.com Tel. (31) 3656-0501 Inside Sales - Negócios de Carbono R. Paraíba, 1.000 7º andar Belo Horizonte / MG - CEP: 30130-141 Tel.: +55 (31) 3656-0501 - +55 31 99950 - 8147
Compensa, SP	Lucas Giestas	Diretor de vendas	germano@carbonfreebrasil.com lucas.giestas@compensa.eco
Moss Earth, SP	Luis Felipe Adaime	Analista de crédito de carbono	Tel. +55 11 4935-5919 felipealves@moss.earth contact@moss.earth https://moss.earth/#quem-somos
CredCarbon, RS	Henrique Machado	Gerente Comercial	0800 591 1050 (11) 93144-1780 (51) 3273-4057 contato@credcarbo.com R. Gaspar Martins, 166 - Floresta, Porto Alegre - RS, 90220-160
Carbonext, SP	Luciano Corrêa da Fonseca e Janaina Dallan	CEO Eng. Florestal	https://www.carbonext.com.br/contact Rua Gomes Carvalho, 1510, Edifício Atrium VI, 19º andar, Vila Olímpia, São Paulo, SP. Parceria Shell R\$ 200 Mil compensação.
Sustainable Carbon, SP	Stefano Emerlin	Diretor Presidente	https://www.sustainablecarbon.com/fale-conosco/ Cel./WhatsApp: +55 11 98882-2550 Tel.: +55 11 2649-0036 web@sustainablecarbon.com Vila Clementino São Paulo - Capital - Brasil Rua Dr. Bacelar, 368 - Conjunto 23
Iniciativa Verde, SP.	Fale Conosco	Coordenação	Celular: (11) 3647.9293 / (11) 3647.9296 Email: contato@iniciativaverde.org.br

EMPRESA	RESPONSÁVEL	CARGO	CONTATO
Carbon Free, SP	Germano Fortkamp	Diretor	germano@carbonfreebrasil.com +55 11 4935-0177
EcoBraz, SP	Henrique Machado	Gerente Comercial	(11) 4329-2001 henrique.machado@ecobraz.org.br R. Dona Maria Quedas, 230 - Jardim Andaraí, São Paulo - SP, 02175-010
Way Carbon, MG	Ana Correa-Patricia Merola Luis Marques	Assessora de Imprensa	patricia.merola@waycarbon.com luis.marques@waycarbon.com ana.correa@waycarbon.com Tel. (31) 3656-0501 Inside Sales - Negócios de Carbono R. Paraiba, 1.000 7º andar Belo Horizonte / MG - CEP: 30130-141 Tel.: +55 (31) 3656-0501 - +55 31 99950 - 8147
Compensa, SP	Lucas Giestas	Diretor de vendas	germano@carbonfreebrasil.com lucas.giestas@compensa.eco
Moss Earth, SP	Luis Felipe Adaime	Analista de crédito de carbono	Tel. +55 11 4935-5919 felipealves@moss.earth contact@moss.earth https://moss.earth/#quem-somos
CredCarbon, RS	Henrique Machado	Gerente Comercial	0800 591 1050 (11) 93144-1780 (51) 3273-4057 contato@credcarbon.com R. Gaspar Martins, 166 - Floresta, Porto Alegre - RS, 90220-160
Carnonext, SP	Luciano Corrêa da Fonseca e Janaina Dallan	CEO Eng. Florestal	https://www.carbonext.com.br/contact Rua Gomes Carvalho, 1510, Edifício Atrium VI, 19º andar, Vila Olímpia, São Paulo, SP. Parceria Shell R\$ 200 Mi compensação.
Sustainable Carbon, SP	Stefano Emerlin	Diretor Presidente	https://www.sustainablecarbon.com/fale-conosco/ Cel./WhatsApp: +55 11 98882-2550 Tel.: +55 11 2649-0036 web@sustainablecarbon.com Vila Clementino São Paulo - Capital - Brasil Rua Dr. Bacelar, 368 - Conjunto 23
Iniciativa Verde, SP.	Fale Conosco	Coordenação	Celular: (11) 3647.9293 / (11) 3647.9296 Email: contato@iniciativaverde.org.br

Table 22. List of companies / organizations offsetting carbon credits.

ANNEX I - 5

2.5. Method for Outcome 5 – Market Research

The Mobility C3 Platform is associated with carbon pricing systems, including carbon offset policies and the disclosure of sustainable corporate policy actions aligned with international agreements aimed at mitigating climate change, as well as financial strategies linked to market mechanisms and stock exchanges. Carbon pricing (or carbon credits) operates at two market levels: the first is the regulated government market, and the second is the voluntary market. Carbon credits in the voluntary market (alternative GHG market) are valued, on average, between US\$10.00 and US\$12.00 per credit (Valor Econômico, 2022). In contrast, regulated carbon credits range from US\$40.00 to US\$80.00 per tonne of carbon (GHG Protocol market) (World Bank, 2020).

A preliminary analysis of sustainability reports from several major corporations (e.g., Coca-Cola, Siemens, Banco Bradesco, and Grupo Natura in Brazil) indicated that, in general, initiatives involving tree planting to offset CO₂ emissions generated by gasoline- and diesel-powered vehicle fleets are virtually nonexistent. These companies are more focused on purchasing carbon credits and developing decarbonization technologies than on implementing tree-planting programs directly.

For additional information regarding the market research, see the document: *Braun (2023), Mobility C3 Business Plan*.

Questionnaires

Para conhecer melhor os potenciais clientes corporativos, foi elaborado um questionário semi-estruturado (Kitchin, et al, 2000) focando no interesse dessas empresa em medir e compensar as emissões de CO₂ da frota de veículos da empresa, conforme exemplificado a seguir.

Mobilidade C3

NEUTRALIZAÇÃO DE CARBONO

Como sabemos a neutralização de carbono é uma medida urgente para combater mudanças climáticas e seus impactos seguindo as recomendações do Painel Intergovernamental de Mudanças Climáticas (IPCC) e o objetivo 13 das Nações Unidas para sustentabilidade.

O Mobilidade C3 é um projeto de pesquisa e inovação para desenvolver uma plataforma digital 3 em 1 que mede em tempo real, a distância percorrida (km), a quantidade de CO₂ emitida pelo tipo e marca do veículo durante o percurso, e o número de árvores para compensar as emissões geradas pela viagem.

Estamos também mapeando ONGs e empresa florestais nos diversos biomas brasileiros, para prestarem serviços de neutralização de carbono através do plantio de árvores e da conservação de florestas nativas.

Nesse sentido gostaríamos muito de saber se a sua empresa tem interesse de medir e compensar as emissões de CO₂ de sua frota de veículos?

Em caso afirmativo, solicitamos a gentileza de preencher os dados abaixo e enviar para o nosso email : mobilidadec3@gmail.com

Agradecemos muito o seu tempo e interesse.

Atenciosamente,

Ricardo Braun
Coordenador do Projeto

PS.
Mais informações sobre o projeto Mobilidade C3 clique aqui: [\(FAPERJ\) \(LNCC / MCTI\)](#)

Projeto financiado pela Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado do Rio de Janeiro (FAPERJ), em parceria com a Incubadora do Laboratório Nacional de Computação Científica (LNCC / MCTI).

DADOS DA EMPRESA

Nome da empresa e unidade:	
Pessoa de contato:	
Email:	
Celular:	
Quantitativo da frota de veículos da empresa / Unidade:	
- Veículos de passeio:	
- Vans:	
- Caminhões:	
- Motos:	
- Outros:	
- Combustível utilizado pela frota:	
- Gasolina:	
- Diesel:	
- Alcool:	
- Gás Natural Veicular (GNV):	
- Outro:	

Figure 16. Questionnaire for corporate companies.

ANNEX II – RESULTS

ANNEX II - 1

3.1. Outcome of Target 1 – Project Planning and Operations

Based on the Mobility C3 Project Schedule and the Logical Framework (see **Annex I - 1**), a Project Evaluation Matrix was developed (see **Annex I - 1**), comparing what had been planned with what was effectively implemented and achieved throughout the 10-month duration of the Mobility C3 Project.

Based on the aforementioned Project Evaluation Matrix, a summarized matrix was prepared containing a synthesis of the outcomes (R) / targets achieved by the Mobility C3 Project, as presented below.

RESULTADOS / METAS DO PROJETO	A	PA	NA
R1 - Planejamento Operacional do Projeto	X		
R2 - Laboratório Prova de Conceito (PoC)	X		
R3 - Modelo da Plataforma	X		
R4 - Parcerias Florestais	X		
R5 - Pesquisa de Mercado		X	
R6 - Plano de Negócio	X		
R7 - Relatório Técnico Parcial	X		
Total	6/7	1/7	0

Legenda: **A** - alcançado; **PA** - parcialmente alcançado; **NA** - não alcançado

Table 23. Summary of the evaluation of the results achieved by the C3 Mobility Project.

Almost all seven (7) results (R) were achieved in this first phase of the Project.

Result R5 (Market Research) was partially achieved because it will also be developed in the second phase of the Project (Phase 2 Administrative and Commercial) after approval by FAPERJ.

ANNEX II - 2

3.2. Outcome of Result 2 – Proof of Concept (PoC) Laboratory

This was one of the most important stages of the Project because it addresses the overall objective of Call for Proposals 10/2021, namely, to promote the transformation of research, development, and innovation projects into ventures based on scientific and/or technological knowledge.

Research

Several outcomes were achieved during the Proof of Concept (PoC) phase, as presented in **Annex I - 1**, beginning with a review and analysis of the specialized literature from various authors (see the list of References). Subsequently, technical consultations were conducted with information technology specialists, involving contact with 20 IT professionals and experts, of whom 9 were interviewed through semi-structured questionnaires to guide the development of the Mobility C3 Platform (see the list of specialists in **Annex I - 2**).

Based on the research and interviews regarding the measurement of CO₂ emissions from motor vehicles, six of the most commonly used methods were identified, as presented in the box below.

Box of CO₂ Measurement Methods for Vehicles
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Installation of a device that measures CO₂ emissions directly from the vehicle's exhaust system;• Use of the vehicle's onboard computer to measure CO₂ emissions (closed system);• Adoption of a standard CO₂ emission factor based on fuel consumption, whereby 1 liter of fuel corresponds to 2.80 kg of CO₂ emissions;• Use of the engine's oxygen consumption, via the OBD2 system, as a means of calculating the vehicle's CO₂ emissions;• Adoption of a single CO₂ emission standard applicable to any vehicle type or brand (e.g., 170 g CO₂/km); and• Use of the engine CO₂ emission standard established by the manufacturer, based on the vehicle's make and model.

Based on the table above, the method selected for the laboratory tests was the vehicle manufacturer's CO₂ emission standard for the engine. The laboratory phase was developed in three stages: the offline measurement laboratory using volunteer motor vehicles, the OBD2 Bluetooth laboratory using volunteer motor vehicles, and the Mobility C3 Platform prototyping laboratory.

In the first laboratory, seven (7) vehicles were monitored over a period of fifteen (15) days across different locations in Brazil, resulting in a total of 4,583 km traveled, 891 kg of CO₂ emitted, the equivalent of nearly five trees required to be planted and maintained for 20 years to offset the amount of CO₂ generated, and the need to preserve 0.02 hectares of tropical forest within the Amazon or Atlantic Forest biomes. (See logbooks, data systematization, graphs, and tables in **Annex I - 2**.)

In the second laboratory (OBD2 Measurement Laboratory), four volunteer vehicles were equipped with Bluetooth-enabled OBD2 devices to monitor engine performance. Seven applications, compatible with both iOS and Android operating systems and developed by different manufacturers, were downloaded to record OBD2 data. The devices were tested in the participating vehicles over a ten-day period; however, only two of the tested applications produced satisfactory results. (See **Annex I - 2** for additional details.)

The third laboratory was based on seven interviews conducted with IT specialists, informal technical discussions, and internet-based research. This process made it possible to define nine

methodological stages for prototype development. Two potential technological pathways were identified as the basis for the platform: Google's cloud infrastructure (e.g., Google Maps Distance Matrix API) and Amazon Web Services (AWS). Research was also conducted on the range of available sensors, probes, electronic boards, and kits capable of measuring distance traveled and CO₂ emissions. The use of cloud-based services incurs costs once predefined usage thresholds are exceeded (e.g., AWS approximately US\$150.00; Google services ranging from US\$50.00 to more than US\$5,000.00, depending on usage levels).

Partnerships

Partnership discussions were conducted with vehicle-tracking companies that possess expertise in motor vehicle fleet monitoring and security, including GETRAK, BMS, and TRIMBLE (see *Mobility C3 Project Business Plan*, Braun, 2023). During these interactions, technical information was exchanged regarding motor vehicle monitoring systems and CO₂ emissions, including service pricing data used as benchmarks for defining the value of services to be offered by Mobility C3 (see *Mobility C3 Project Business Plan*, Braun, 2023).

ANNEX II - 3

3.3. Outcome of Result 3 –Mobility C3 Platform Model

Discussions and research related to the Mobility C3 Model began in 2021 with the first RicNetwork development team (Eng. Renan Machado and Richard Siqueira), which made it possible to organize both the back-end architecture of the Mobility C3 Platform and the methodological stages associated with its User Interface (UI) and User Experience (UX).

A table containing six stages for developing the operational and visual components of the Platform was also prepared (see **Annexes I - 2 and I - 3**). The table describes key platform components, including vehicle identification data, vehicle geolocation, identification buttons, data analysis features, forestry organizations, platform settings, and tree-planting maps.

Subsequently, in 2022, additional discussions were held with the IT company 11 Tech (Prof. Mozar Baptista da Silva, Eng. Claudio Temas, and Eng. Edrik Borges) regarding the design of the platform interfaces for the purpose of preparing a development budget. Once the budget was approved, the process advanced to the creation of an administrative website for data monitoring. The initial HTML structure of the Platform was also defined, and the subsequent stages were implemented as described in **Stage 3 – Online Prototyping Laboratory** under **Item 2.2. Method for Outcome 2 – Proof of Concept (PoC) Laboratory**.

NOTE. Additional information regarding the online prototyping laboratory will be complemented and submitted separately to FAPERJ.

ANNEX II - 4

3.4. Outcome of Target 4 – Forest Partnerships

The Mobility C3 Project is not limited to developing a digital platform for measuring carbon emissions from motor vehicles. It also seeks to identify ecological compensation mechanisms for carbon emissions in order to mitigate the impacts of the extreme climatic events currently being experienced.

Research

Research conducted using various literature sources (Freitas, 2022; Prima, 2020; Embrapa, 2020; Movida, 2019; Braun, 2015; MMA, 2012; Tonon, 2007; Santos, 2007; Imazon; among others), together with technical interviews with specialists in forest engineering and carbon offsetting,

provided an overview of ecological compensation practices in Brazil and internationally. Based on these studies, a carbon compensation table was developed using data from different authors, and the resulting information was systematized through graphical analyses (see **Annex I - 4**).

Data Systematization

The research and development of the ecological compensation table (see **Annex I - 4**) made it possible to systematize the carbon sequestration rate per tree, from planting through the first 20 years of growth and up to maturity, which generally occurs between 60 and 100 years of age. Based on the average values reported by the authors reviewed, the resulting estimate for carbon sequestration was 198 kg of carbon per tree over a period of 20 to 30 years. For one hectare of tropical forest, the average value reported by various authors was 68 tonnes of carbon sequestered per hectare over a period of 20 to 40 years (see graphs in **Annex I - 4**).

Questionnaires

A questionnaire was developed for forestry companies and NGOs to assess their quantitative and qualitative capacity for tree planting and atmospheric carbon sequestration (see questionnaire in **Annex II - 2**). The questionnaires were distributed to 23 forestry organizations and companies engaged in projects and business activities across different Brazilian biomes, as well as to 9 companies/organizations involved in carbon credit trading. The objective of the questionnaires was not only to collect data but also to establish partnerships (see the list of organizations and companies in **Annex I - 4**).

Partnerships

During this phase, several partnership contacts were also established with forest restoration NGOs, carbon offset organizations, forestry companies, and vehicle-tracking companies with expertise in fleet monitoring and security, including Getrak, BMS, and Trimble.

Forest partnerships are essential to enable Mobility C3 Platform clients to contract carbon offset services through forestry partners and carbon offset providers.

ANNEX II - 5

3.5. Outcome of Target 5 – Market Research

Research activities were conducted through internet-based sources, technical discussions, and the distribution of semi-structured questionnaires to companies in the corporate sector that maintain sustainability policies and/or are included in the Corporate Sustainability Index (ISE), as well as companies that publish international sustainability disclosure reports (e.g., GRI, Ethos, and the Global Compact). The objective was to assess corporate interest in offsetting the carbon footprint generated by vehicle fleets.

Questionnaires were distributed to several companies (e.g., Natura, Ambev, Americanas, Braskem, EcoRodovias, Bradesco, and Siemens Brazil, among others) in order to obtain an overview of the market and the potential demand for services offered by the Mobility C3 Platform.

During the second phase of the Project (Commercial and Administrative Phase), it is planned to conduct more targeted and intensive outreach activities through direct marketing campaigns, social media channels, and social partners (see *Mobility C3 Business Plan by Braun, 2023*).

ANNEX II - 6

DISCUSSION

4.2. Proof of Concept (PoC) Laboratory

Continuation...

Many ecological footprint applications use a single emissions standard for all vehicles (e.g., 170 g CO₂/km – Ecosia), while other models apply a fixed CO₂ emission factor based on fuel consumption. Both approaches generate generalized and often imprecise results, since each vehicle make and model has its own specific emission profile.

To determine the factory-standard CO₂ emissions for each vehicle, tests are conducted on the exhaust system, from which fuel consumption and distance traveled are calculated using a complex set of equations. Emissions are subsequently expressed in units of g/km (grams per kilometer). These values vary according to the vehicle model and manufacturer (e.g., Suzuki Grand Vitara: 200 g CO₂/km; Fiat Palio ELX Flex 1.4, 8V, Flex: 169.9 g CO₂/km; and so forth).

Some competitors provide fleet-emission calculation APIs (WayCarbon, 2023) and applications capable of calculating carbon emissions and the number of trees required for offsetting purposes (Trimble, 2023). However, these systems require users to manually input fuel consumption data and distance traveled (km) in order to perform the calculations. *Mobility C3* relies solely on the vehicle's factory-standard CO₂ emission rate.

Accuracy of CO₂ Measurement

A synthesis of the methods available for measuring CO₂ emissions from vehicles includes the following alternatives: (1) installation of a device that measures CO₂ emissions directly from the vehicle exhaust system; (2) use of the vehicle onboard computer to measure CO₂ emissions (available in vehicles manufactured after 2015); (3) adoption of a single CO₂ emission factor based on fuel consumption; (4) use of engine oxygen consumption through OBD2 as a means of calculating vehicle CO₂ emissions; (5) adoption of a single CO₂ emission standard for all vehicle types and brands; and (6) use of the manufacturer-established engine CO₂ emission standard based on vehicle type and model.

The first alternative provides the highest level of accuracy; however, it is also the most expensive in terms of manufacturing and installation costs. The second alternative is viable only for vehicles manufactured after 2015 and would require the development of specific applications capable of transmitting vehicle data to the *Mobility C3* Platform for each make and model. The third, fourth, and fifth alternatives rely on a single emission standard for all vehicles, reducing measurement accuracy. The sixth alternative was considered the most suitable for the current phase of the Project because each vehicle make and model has a factory-defined CO₂ emission standard based on engine type and fuel characteristics.

CO₂ Emission Calculation

The mathematical calculations performed for each vehicle (make and model) during the Offline Laboratory, as documented in the Logbooks (see **Annexes I - 1 and II - 2**), should be the same calculations implemented within the *Mobility C3* digital platform. In other words, the calculation of distance traveled, CO₂ emissions, and ecological compensation (number of trees to be planted,

preserved forest area, and carbon credits) should follow the same methodology within the Mobility C3 application.

Online Bluetooth OBD2 Laboratory

The laboratory demonstrated several advantages and disadvantages associated with the use of the OBD2 ELM327 Bluetooth scanner. Although this device is widely used by automotive repair workshops, numerous challenges remain regarding the measurement of CO₂ emissions within the Mobility C3 Platform.

Among the advantages of this online measurement system is the wide variety of applications available on the market capable of monitoring numerous vehicle variables. The combination of an OBD2 device and a compatible application allows users to monitor vehicle performance online via Bluetooth or Wi-Fi. A limited number of applications calculate CO₂ emissions based on fuel consumption and distance traveled, thereby enabling environmental monitoring. The OBD2 system also has potential for fleet monitoring, provided that an OBD2 device is installed in each vehicle and an appropriate application is deployed for monitoring purposes.

One possibility would be the development of an application compatible with OBD2 systems to calculate and monitor CO₂ emissions and distance traveled (km) through the individual smartphones of drivers. Monitoring reports generated daily, weekly, or monthly could then be transmitted to a central database application to consolidate information from all monitored vehicles and perform calculations related to distance traveled, CO₂ emissions, and tree-equivalent offsets. However, this remains a topic for future research.

Despite its advantages, the use of OBD2 presents several challenges. Many smartphone applications that theoretically support OBD2 monitoring often fail due to incompatibilities with specific OBD2 devices or mobile operating systems (iOS versus Android). Consequently, both the OBD2 hardware and the mobile application must be compatible. In addition, it is necessary to identify the most appropriate application for the specific vehicle being monitored. Some vehicles (e.g., a 2000 Suzuki Grand Vitara) manufactured before 2005 cannot be diagnosed through OBD2 systems because those vehicles were not originally programmed or standardized for this technology, excluding a substantial portion of the vehicle fleet from the sample. In practice, only vehicles manufactured from 2006 onward are potentially suitable for OBD2 monitoring.

Another limitation concerns the physical installation of the OBD2 device in certain vehicle models, such as the Fiat Palio. Furthermore, volunteer vehicle users often encounter difficulties in installing the OBD2 device independently, downloading and configuring the appropriate application, performing measurements, and generating performance reports. Finally, after data collection through Bluetooth OBD2 applications, there is no mechanism for aggregating information across an entire vehicle fleet. A dedicated back-end system would therefore need to be developed and programmed to perform calculations, data processing, and systematization for fleet-wide monitoring.

Vehicle Tracking Systems

In 2021, the Mobility C3 Project planned to evaluate several types of vehicle tracking systems during the PoC laboratory phase. These systems were selected through research conducted on specialized internet platforms. However, following a technical interview with a representative of the tracking company Getrak (see **Annex III - 1**), it became evident that hundreds of different tracking devices are available on the market. To avoid duplicating laboratory procedures already performed by companies in this sector, it was decided not to conduct tracker-based testing.

Furthermore, according to a technical interview with Prof. Licht of UCP (see **Annex III - 1**), vehicle trackers alone do not provide carbon emission data. Accurate CO₂ measurement would require the

development of a dedicated device, significantly more expensive than conventional trackers, to be installed directly in the vehicle exhaust system.

Based on these considerations, it was decided to focus the Proof of Concept (PoC) on smartphones, since most drivers already possess devices equipped with the necessary sensors (e.g., GPS, accelerometer, compass, among others) to perform Mobility C3 measurements.

Google Cloud vs. AWS Cloud vs. Heroku Cloud

Google Maps represents an accessible and highly experienced technological solution for the Mobility C3 Platform. Google tools such as Distance Matrix, Google Asset Tracking, and Google Timeline provide valuable functionalities for the Platform. According to RicsNetwork, the data generated through monitoring activities remain stored until deleted by the registered Google administrator. The Timeline database associated with monitored mileage (km) could subsequently be used to generate monthly or period-specific emission reports upon request.

Google Timeline records vehicle latitude and longitude coordinates at intervals measured in seconds, which may lead to inaccuracies in determining the actual distance traveled by the monitored vehicle. The greater the interval between geographic coordinate measurements, the lower the accuracy of the calculated displacement. Conversely, shorter intervals provide greater precision. For example, measurements taken every two seconds will be more accurate than those recorded every twenty-five seconds. Therefore, shorter measurement intervals are considered the preferred option for the Mobility C3 Platform. If displacement is measured only every 25 or 60 meters, an additional factor of approximately 20–30% could potentially be incorporated into CO₂ calculations to compensate for measurement uncertainty.

More recently, Google introduced Eco-Friendly Routing (Google Maps, 2022), which identifies routes that minimize environmental impact, fuel consumption, and estimated CO₂ emissions. However, this API does not identify the specific CO₂ emissions of individual vehicles. In contrast, Mobility C3 registers each vehicle individually and applies its specific factory-standard CO₂ emission factor.

According to Prof. Licht of UCP, Amazon Web Services (AWS) represents the best cloud-computing option for the Mobility C3 Platform. However, AWS does not provide publicly accessible navigation and tracking tools comparable to Google Maps or Google Timeline. AWS offers a service known as Amazon Location Service, which is charged based on usage volume.

While both AWS and Google provide free usage periods of approximately one year, Heroku Cloud was considered the most viable option because it offers free services for an indefinite period. Heroku provides automated orchestration infrastructure, high-availability automated scaling, built-in Zerops pipeline integration, unlimited development usage, and reduced requirements for installing configuration systems for different project components.

Based on technical interviews and research findings (see **Annexes III**), the methodological stages for developing the Mobility C3 Platform were established (see **Annexes I - 1 and I - 3**) for both Google Cloud and AWS environments. This methodology is also applicable to the Platform Model phase through the creation of a centralized database structure and management back-end, followed by the design and implementation of the User Interface (UI) and User Experience (UX) components (see **Annex I - 3**).

4.3. Forest Partnerships and Carbon Credits

Continuation...

In general, trees sequester larger amounts of carbon during their growth phase, with sequestration rates declining as they reach maturity. Approximately 70% of carbon sequestration occurs within

the first 30 years, after which sequestration tends to stabilize (Tonon, 2007). Accordingly, the Mobility C3 Platform will adopt average carbon sequestration indices derived from multiple authors for tropical forests (Atlantic Forest and Amazon Rainforest), as presented in the graphs (see **Annex I - 4**).

It is important to note that forest trees are not mechanical systems with perfectly predictable performance. Carbon sequestration is influenced by numerous factors, including soil nutrient availability, temperature variation, solar radiation, wind regimes, rainfall patterns, and other local and global climatic conditions. Consequently, carbon sequestration values should be interpreted as average estimates rather than absolute figures.

As previously discussed, the Mobility C3 Platform is intended to support the monitoring of motor vehicle travel distance (km), CO₂ emissions, and the number of trees required to offset those emissions. The effective offsetting of carbon emissions generated by monitored vehicles remains the responsibility of forest partners (NGOs and forestry companies) or organizations involved in carbon credit trading. In this regard, the Platform seeks to establish a connection between users and forest partners in order to facilitate carbon offsetting (ecological compensation). Mobility C3 will not directly plant trees, protect standing forests, or trade carbon credits.

Research on Companies and NGOs

Internet-based research was conducted to assess the capacity of major forestry companies (e.g., Suzano, Klabin, among others) to support carbon offset initiatives. Forestry companies generally possess a greater capacity for large-scale tree planting than NGOs. These companies operate with profit-oriented objectives, although some maintain protected areas and implement sustainability and environmental education programs.

NGOs, by contrast, focus on forest restoration while also working directly with local communities, schools, and associations. Many NGOs engage in forest restoration activities, which are generally more comprehensive than simple tree planting or degraded land recovery. Unlike forestry companies, NGOs are typically not profit-oriented.

Within the context of the Mobility C3 Project, it is important to establish partnerships with both NGOs and socially responsible forestry companies. Large forestry companies can support large-scale planting initiatives capable of offsetting substantial carbon emissions generated by extensive vehicle fleets.

Questionnaires

The questionnaires administered enabled an assessment of the capacity of each forestry company and NGO to plant trees and offset carbon emissions generated by motor vehicles. For example, the NGO Prima reported that its primary areas of activity include tree planting for carbon sequestration and offsetting, as well as climate-related environmental education. Its activities are conducted within the Cerrado, Atlantic Forest, and Caatinga biomes through partnerships with companies and other NGOs.

According to the information provided, the approximate cost of planting and managing a single seedling through forest partners is R\$50.00 per seedling. Under suitable site conditions, it is possible to plant approximately 5,000 seedlings within one week. These data provide an overview of market costs associated with tree-planting initiatives aimed at carbon offsetting, which the Mobility C3 Platform intends to promote.

Carbon Credits

As noted previously, one carbon credit represents one tonne of carbon dioxide that has not been emitted into the atmosphere. The most common form of carbon credit commercialization is through

the direct trading of emission reductions. Between 2018 and 2021, for example, this market increased in value by approximately 187%.

The carbon market is closely associated with certification mechanisms linked to the United Nations REDD+ Program (Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation) and certification organizations such as Verra Registry, BioCarbon Registry, Global Carbon Council, and others, which certify REDD+ projects in Brazil and internationally.

Most organizations and companies operating in the Brazilian carbon credit market are relatively small enterprises that commercialize carbon credits generated by projects certified under international standards. Examples include WayCarbon, Carbon Free Brasil, EcoBraz, Sustainable Carbon, among others (see **Table 22**). Mobility C3 is seeking to establish partnerships with such organizations.

The carbon market consists of two primary segments. The voluntary carbon market (alternative GHG market) typically trades carbon credits at values ranging from US\$10.00 to US\$12.00 per tonne (Valor Econômico, 2022). The regulated carbon market trades carbon credits at values ranging from US\$40.00 to US\$80.00 per tonne (GHG Protocol market) (World Bank, 2020). In Brazil, the voluntary market remains the predominant mechanism for carbon credit transactions. Mobility C3 intends to collaborate primarily with organizations operating within this voluntary market segment.

4.4. Market Research

Continuation...

For example, the Trimble vehicle-tracking application includes a dashboard displaying distance traveled, estimated CO₂ emissions, and the number of trees required for carbon offsetting. However, users must manually input fuel consumption data to calculate CO₂ emissions. Mobility C3 performs these calculations in real time. In addition, Trimble does not establish direct connections with carbon offset organizations or forestry partners capable of implementing the actual offset process.

Based on the objectives of the Project, the primary market segments for Mobility C3 include companies listed in the Corporate Sustainability Index (ISE) of the Brazilian Stock Exchange (e.g., Natura, Neoenergia, Banco Itaú, Lojas Renner, Americanas, among others). These organizations maintain sustainability policies and carbon-neutrality targets for social reporting and international disclosure purposes.

There is also potential for Mobility C3 to provide consulting services to vehicle-tracking companies that monitor commercial fleets, supporting the calculation of emissions and facilitating carbon offset solutions through commercial partnerships. In addition, consulting services could potentially be provided to federal and state governments regarding the taxation of CO₂ emissions generated by petroleum-based motor vehicles in Brazil.

In summary, Mobility C3 is innovative because it combines characteristics of a vehicle-tracking platform with those of a carbon-offset facilitation service.

Questionnaires

The standard questionnaire distributed to potential corporate clients with ISE certification is presented in **Annex III - 4**. These questionnaires were initially distributed to assess corporate interest in contracting Mobility C3 services. To date, only one company (Americanas) has responded.

ANNEX III

ANNEX III - 1

TECHNOLOGY QUESTIONNAIRES

Research funded by the Rio de Janeiro State Research Foundation (FAPERJ), in partnership with the Incubator of the National Laboratory for Scientific Computing (LNCC/MCTI). Call for Proposals
IT TECHNOLOGY

FEASIBILITY OF BUILDING THE DIGITAL PLATFORM FOR THE C3 MOBILITY PROJECT.

Preliminary Version subject to correction No. 00 / May 2020 and November 2021

The C3 Mobility Project's main objective is to monitor CO2 emissions from motor vehicles, or vehicle fleets, for ecological compensation, as an urgent measure to combat climate change and its impacts, following UN SDG 13.

The goal is to offset the CO2 emissions of companies that have sustainability policies aiming for zero carbon emissions in their production chain, or that apply corporate social responsibility standards for social balance sheet and international reporting purposes (e.g., GRI, Ethos, Global Compact, among others).

For any questions, please send information to mobilidadec3@gmail.com

a. **REGISTRATION FORM**

b.

c. a. Organization Name: RicsNetWork

d. b. Contact Persons: Richard Siqueira and Eng. Renan Machado

e. c. Address: Petrópolis - RJ

f.

g. Email: ricsnetwork@gmail.com

h. e. Mobile Phone: +55 24 -

i. f. Date: May 2020 and November 2022

j.

k. **QUESTIONS**

l.

m. What is the best way to develop the C3 Mobility digital platform in your opinion?

- n.
 - o. Define data collection platforms (e.g., cell phone, Arduino Kit, Raspberry Kit, trackers, Teltonika, CRX, Cal Amp, others)
 - p. Develop a data collection system for these devices
 - q. Choose a platform to store and process data (e.g., Google Platform), which charges for each service, initially being free 1 million times.
 - r. Create a data centralization system: route, carbon, and trees
 - s. Management back-end = What will manage everything, i.e., the skeleton code of a system.
 - t. Create the user interface; Functionality and visualizations
 - u. Develop a data collection system, estimated at 4 to 5 systems.
-

2. Devices and Sensors Required for the Development of theMobility C3 Platform

For the development of theMobility C3 platform, it is recommended to use prototyping and tracking devices widely employed in Internet of Things (IoT) and vehicle telematics projects. Among the main options are the Arduino Uno and Raspberry Pi kits, which provide flexibility for integration with sensors, communication modules, and data collection systems.

For tracking and geolocation purposes, commercial devices such as AirTag, TK915, TK-103B, and other equivalent equipment may be evaluated, provided that they meet the technical requirements of the platform.

Additionally, it is recommended to conduct a technical consultation with the company SixFab to verify the compatibility of device operating frequencies with the frequency bands used in Brazil. Brazilian mobile networks predominantly operate within the 1,800 MHz to 2,600 MHz range (Band 3 and related bands), whereas certain devices developed for the North American market may operate at different frequencies, such as 700 MHz, thereby requiring prior compatibility validation.

3. Technological Operation of theMobility C3 Platform

The technological process of the platform may be based on fleet and vehicle tracking services provided by the Google Maps Platform, particularly solutions dedicated to transportation and vehicle monitoring.

The platform will be responsible for recording vehicle trajectories through the periodic collection of geographic coordinates, enabling the determination of the actual distance traveled and the calculation of emissions associated with vehicle movement.

The data collection frequency may be parameterized according to project requirements, for example, by recording data every 5, 20, or 50 meters traveled. In situations where the sampling frequency is reduced to optimize processing and storage, correction factors may be adopted to compensate for the loss of accuracy in emission calculations.

4. Use of Google APIs in theMobility C3 Platform

The technological architecture of the solution may utilize services provided by the Google Cloud Platform, including resources from the Google Maps Platform and Google Firebase.

The mobile application will periodically capture the user's geographic location, recording spatial coordinates and information associated with the trip. These data will be transmitted to cloud-based storage, allowing the reconstruction of the actual route traveled by the vehicle.

Mileage will be calculated based on georeferenced points collected throughout the route, accurately reflecting the actual distance traveled. Additionally, complementary variables such as average speed and acceleration patterns may be incorporated to improve estimates of fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions.

Consequently, emission calculations will be based on real travel data, providing greater accuracy when compared to methods based solely on estimated distances.

5. Data Storage and Management

The data collected by the platform will be stored in a cloud environment through a centralized database and a management backend infrastructure.

This approach eliminates the need for local storage on users' mobile devices, reducing smartphone memory consumption while ensuring greater security, availability, and integrity of information.

The database will include technical information on registered vehicles, such as manufacturer, model, year of manufacture, fuel type, and CO₂ emission factor per kilometer traveled. This repository will be continuously expanded as new vehicles are incorporated into the platform.

Travel records will remain stored for the period established in the application's data retention policy, enabling the generation of historical emissions reports for specific periods, such as weeks, months, or years.

The use of managed cloud services offers significant operational advantages, including automatic scalability, continuous infrastructure updates, reduced maintenance costs, and support for compliance with data protection regulations, such as those established under Brazil's General Data Protection Law (LGPD).

6. API Concept Applied to the Project

An API (Application Programming Interface) is a set of protocols and routines that enables communication between different computer systems.

Within the context of the Mobility C3 platform, Google Maps Platform APIs will provide geolocation, mapping, route calculation, and spatial data processing functionalities, allowing these capabilities to be integrated into the application without the need to develop such technologies independently.

7. Database Scalability

The proposed architecture has been designed to operate within a scalable cloud-computing environment, enabling the gradual growth of users, monitored vehicles, and stored records without significant impairment of operational performance.

Services provided by Google Cloud offer automatic scalability features, ensuring processing and storage capacities compatible with the evolving demands of the platform.

8. Development of the Platform's Graphical User Interface

Following the implementation of the database infrastructure and backend services, the subsequent phase will consist of developing the platform's graphical user interface, encompassing both User Experience (UX) and User Interface (UI) design aspects.

According to preliminary information provided by the lead researcher, the application is expected to contain approximately ten main screens dedicated to functionalities such as user and vehicle

registration, location monitoring, trip visualization, CO₂ emissions tracking, environmental offset indicators, and report generation.

9. Development Timeline

The preliminary schedule estimates a development period of approximately six months, corresponding to 180 calendar days of work from the official commencement of project activities.

This period includes the stages of planning, technological infrastructure development, mobile application implementation, cloud service integration, operational testing, functional validation, and deployment of the initial version of the Mobility C3 platform.

Pesquisa financiada pela Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado do Rio de Janeiro ([FAPERJ](#)), em parceria com a Incubadora do Laboratório Nacional de Computação Científica ([LNCC / MCTI](#)). Edital

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

FEASIBILITY OF DEVELOPING THE DIGITAL PLATFORM FOR THE Mobility C3 PROJECT

Preliminary Version – Subject to Revision No. 00 / January 2022

The Mobility C3 Project aims primarily to monitor CO₂ emissions from motor vehicles and vehicle fleets for ecological compensation purposes, as an urgent measure to combat climate change and its impacts, in accordance with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 13 (SDG 13).

The objective is to offset the CO₂ emissions of companies that implement sustainability policies aimed at achieving carbon neutrality throughout their production chains, or that adopt corporate social responsibility standards for social reporting and international disclosure purposes (e.g., GRI, Ethos, Global Compact, among others).

For further information, please contact: mobilidadec3@gmail.com

REGISTRATION INFORMATION

- a. Organization Name:** RicsNetWork
- b. Contact Persons:** Eng. Paulo Jesus (IT) and Richard Siqueira
- c. Address:** Petrópolis, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
- d. E-mail:** ricsnetwork@gmail.com
- e. Mobile Phone:** +55 24 -

f. Date: January 2022

QUESTIONS

1. In this new phase of the project, what would be the most appropriate approach for developing theMobility C3 digital platform?

The data collection platform from mobile devices will be based on Amazon Web Services (AWS).

The project will require an IT Architect/Software Developer with expertise in cloud computing, a Web Designer, and UI/UX Designers. These professionals will be responsible for developing technologies capable of integrating with any type of vehicle (e.g., FIA-compliant applications).

The lead software developer specializes in the Amazon Web Services (AWS) platform. The proposed solution consists of creating a centralized data collection and management system capable of storing and processing route, carbon emission, and tree-compensation data.

Measurement Devices:

- Mobile Devices: 5 vehicles
- GPS Devices: 5 vehicles
- Arduino Kit: 1 vehicle

Total: 11 vehicles

The project will require the development of a management back-end system responsible for coordinating all platform operations, including:

- Arduino Plug-in Integration;
- Mobile Application Plug-in Integration;
- GPS Tracker Plug-in Integration.

Additional development activities include:

- Designing and implementing the user interface;
- Defining functionalities and data visualizations;
- Developing the data collection architecture, estimated to comprise four to five integrated subsystems.

On mobile devices, data collection may be automatically activated when the application is launched, allowing the monitoring and recording of vehicle trips.

2. Which AWS tools are required to develop theMobility C3 platform?

The development of theMobility C3 platform may utilize a combination of AWS cloud services to support data collection, storage, processing, security, scalability, and visualization.

The main AWS services recommended for the project include:

Amazon EC2 (Elastic Compute Cloud):

Provides scalable virtual servers for hosting applications, APIs, and back-end services.

Amazon S3 (Simple Storage Service):

Used for secure storage of application files, reports, logs, backups, and other digital assets.

Amazon RDS (Relational Database Service):

Provides managed relational databases for storing vehicle information, user registrations, emission records, and operational data.

Amazon DynamoDB:

A fully managed NoSQL database suitable for high-volume real-time geolocation and telemetry data.

AWS Lambda:

Enables serverless execution of business logic and event-driven processing, reducing infrastructure management requirements.

Amazon API Gateway:

Provides secure and scalable APIs for communication between mobile applications, GPS devices, IoT sensors, and cloud services.

AWS IoT Core:

Facilitates communication and management of connected devices, including Arduino-based systems, GPS trackers, and future IoT sensors.

Amazon Cognito:

Manages user authentication, authorization, and access control.

Amazon CloudWatch:

Provides monitoring, logging, and operational performance tracking for the platform.

Amazon QuickSight:

Supports the generation of dashboards, reports, and analytical visualizations related to vehicle usage, CO₂ emissions, and environmental compensation indicators.

AWS Amplify:

Itens	Descrição	Unidades	Quant.	VI unit	VI Total	Observações
1	Computer Node (EC2)	1	24	R\$ 269,78/mês	R\$ 6.474,72	Servidor onde a aplicação e toda sua estrutura ficará alocada
2	DataBase (RDS)	1	24	R\$ 351,93/mês	R\$ 8.446,32	Banco de Dados onde ficará armazenado os dados obtidos pelo rastreamento.
3	Amazon API Gateway	1	24	R\$ 2,38/mês	R\$ 57,12	Adicionar proteção e autenticação entre o rastreador e a aplicação.
4	DNS Route 53	1	24	R\$ 14,30/mês	R\$ 343,20	Converte nomes para endereços IP numéricos como 192.0.2.1, usados pelos computadores para se conectarem entre si.
5	S3 (100GB)	1	24	R\$ 12,18/mês	R\$ 292,32	Storage onde ficarão armazenados documentos e dados referentes ao projeto.
6	Domain (Domínio)	1	24	R\$ 63,56/mês	R\$ 1.524,44	Domínio da C3 na internet.
7	Amazon CloudFront	1	24	R\$ 19,33/mês	R\$ 463,92	Otimiza a performance da aplicação para região da América do Sul.
	Valor Total			R\$ 733,46/mês	R\$ 17.602,04	

Accelerates the development and deployment of mobile and web applications integrated with AWS services.

Through the integration of these services, theMobility C3 platform would benefit from a secure, scalable, and highly available cloud architecture capable of supporting future growth in the number of users, vehicles, and monitored routes.

3. How Would the Technological Process Operate in theMobility C3 Project?

Store data, for example, records associated with 100 Iveco vehicles, 400 Ford vehicles, and others. Reduce the energy consumption and battery usage resulting from the operation of the platform. Develop user interfaces including maps, CO₂ emissions graphs, distance traveled (km), and the estimated number of trees required for carbon offsetting.

5. What Is the Cost of Developing theMobility C3 Platform?

The cost is significantly higher than the amount originally budgeted and submitted to FAPERJ, namely R\$ 20,000.00 for the Information Technology team. Paulo Jesus proposed becoming a partner in the futureMobility C3 company.

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

FEASIBILITY OF DEVELOPING THE DIGITAL PLATFORM FOR THEMobility C3 PROJECT

Preliminary Version – Subject to Revision No. 00 / January 2022

The primary objective of theMobility C3 Project is to monitor CO₂ emissions from motor vehicles and vehicle fleets for ecological compensation purposes, as an urgent measure to combat climate change and its impacts, in accordance with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 13 (SDG 13).

The goal is to offset the CO₂ emissions of companies that have sustainability policies aimed at achieving net-zero carbon emissions throughout their production chains, or that implement corporate social responsibility standards for social reporting and international reporting purposes (e.g., GRI, Ethos, Global Compact, among others).

For further information, please contact: mobilidadec3@gmail.com

REGISTRATION FORM

a. Organization Name: GETRAK

b. Contact Persons: Giver de Oliveira and Isabela Guimarães

c. Address: Belo Horizonte, Minas Gerais, Brazil

d. E-mail: isabela.guimaraes@getrak.com.br; giver@getrak.com.br

e. Mobile Phone: +55 31 9874-9122

f. Date: January 2022

QUESTIONS

1. How can we jointly develop theMobility C3 digital platform in partnership with GETRAK?

GETRAK is one of the largest vehicle tracking companies in the market. We are the owners of Localiza. We work with the FIAT automotive manufacturer and provide fleet monitoring services.

We develop platforms for use by our clients. Clients may customize their own platforms and commercialize vehicle monitoring services.

2. What devices/sensors are required to develop theMobility C3 platform?

GETRAK utilizes more than 100 types of tracking devices available on the market.

We operate a platform called “Iceberg,” which includes a complete backend infrastructure. We can provide a skeleton code framework of our system for implementation within theMobility C3 Project.

We work with Amazon Web Services (AWS).

3. How would the technological process operate within theMobility C3 Project?

- GETRAK would provide access to theMobility C3 Project.
- We would provide an API and the source code of the Iceberg software.
- Your engineer (Paulo Jesus) would analyze the system and provide approval.
- GETRAK would send the NDA (UniBrasil).
- The project would then be developed and adapted to this platform.
- A partnership agreement would subsequently be established.

4. How can we strengthen the partnership?

TheMobility C3 Project team should submit its proposal together with a Confidentiality and Non-Disclosure Agreement, after which a partnership agreement may be signed by both parties.

5. What is the cost of developing theMobility C3 platform?

The development cost of a software platform may reach approximately **R\$ 300,000.00**.

Note: After preliminary information regarding theMobility C3 Project and a Confidentiality and Non-Disclosure Agreement were submitted to GETRAK, the company did not provide any further response. Several follow-up attempts were made via e-mail; however, no additional communication was received.

Research funded by the Rio de Janeiro State Research Support Foundation (FAPERJ), in partnership with the Incubator of the National Laboratory for Scientific Computing (LNCC/MCTI).

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

FEASIBILITY OF DEVELOPING THE DIGITAL PLATFORM FOR THEMobility C3 PROJECT

Preliminary Version – Subject to Revision No. 00 / February 2022

The primary objective of the Mobility C3 Project is to monitor CO₂ emissions from motor vehicles and vehicle fleets for ecological compensation purposes, as an urgent measure to combat climate change and its impacts, in accordance with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 13 (SDG 13).

The goal is to offset the CO₂ emissions of companies that have sustainability policies aimed at achieving net-zero carbon emissions throughout their production chains, or that implement corporate social responsibility standards for social reporting and international reporting purposes (e.g., GRI, Ethos, Global Compact, among others).

For further information, please contact: mobilidadec3@gmail.com

REGISTRATION FORM

Organization Name: IT Consultant – Inovacell Comércio de Eletrônicos LTDA

Contact Person: Daniel Roberto dos Santos Pinto

Address: Rio de Janeiro, RJ, Brazil

E-mail: danrsp@icloud.com; danrsp@gmail.com

Mobile Phone: +55 (021) 96415-9150

Date: January 2022

QUESTIONS

1. In your opinion, how does OBD2 technology (On-Board Diagnostic System for Motor Vehicles) operate within the Mobility C3 digital platform?

OBD technology emerged from governmental efforts to control vehicle pollutant emissions in the United States, where automobile production was growing rapidly. In 2010, automobile manufacturers operating in Brazil adopted a standardized vehicle diagnostic protocol known as OBD2.

The OBD2 scanner is capable of extracting a maximum amount of information from a specific protocol. It can also interpret multiple protocols and perform vehicle-related operations through the OBD interface. The OBD2 connector consists of 16 pins, each responsible for transmitting specific information. Each protocol functions as a type of dictionary that translates the information communicated through each pin.

2. How can information from an OBD2 device installed in a monitored vehicle be measured?

Devices used to diagnose vehicle operation may include scanners or devices equipped with a cellular communication chip capable of transmitting data in real time to a server, where the information is processed and made available to the user.

The most common method involves a Bluetooth-enabled device connected to a mobile application (such as Torque for Android and iOS), which displays vehicle information through a smartphone.

Several OBD2 applications are available for vehicle diagnostics, including:

- InfoCar
- Car Scanner
- Scanner ELM OBD2
- EOBD Facile
- OBD2 Carrorama
- Track Replay
- Torque
- InfoCar

Among these, Car Scanner is considered one of the leading options for iOS, while Torque is widely used on Android devices.

3. What type of information does OBD2 provide?

In general, OBD2 provides information regarding:

- Fuel consumption;
- Oxygen levels;
- Engine RPM;
- Catalytic converter performance;
- Exhaust gas sensors (CO₂);
- Oxygen sensors;
- NOx/SCR monitoring systems;
- Other vehicle operating parameters.

Depending on the vehicle model, available information may be limited to parameters such as fuel consumption, temperature, speed, and related operational data.

Following data collection, the mobile application can be configured to generate a diagnostic report for the monitored vehicle.

4. What are the disadvantages of using OBD2?

There are numerous OBD2 devices available on the market, including the ELM327 model. However, not all devices are compatible with all applications. In other words, interoperability is not always guaranteed.

Therefore, it is necessary to use compatible combinations, such as the Torque application with the ELM327 OBD2 device. Otherwise, some devices may fail to establish Bluetooth connectivity and consequently be unable to provide vehicle data.

5. What is the cost of an OBD2 device?

The cost of OBD2 devices may range from approximately **R\$ 15.00 to R\$ 260.00**, depending on the manufacturer, model, and functionality.

Pesquisa financiada pela Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado do Rio de Janeiro ([FAPERJ](#)), em parceria com a Incubadora do Laboratório Nacional de Computação Científica ([LNCC / MCTI](#)). Edital

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

FEASIBILITY OF DEVELOPING THE DIGITAL PLATFORM FOR THE Mobility C3 PROJECT

Preliminary Version – Subject to Revision No. 00 / August 2022

The primary objective of the Mobility C3 Project is to monitor CO₂ emissions from motor vehicles and vehicle fleets for ecological compensation purposes, as an urgent measure to combat climate change and its impacts, in accordance with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 13 (SDG 13).

The goal is to offset the CO₂ emissions of companies that have sustainability policies aimed at achieving net-zero carbon emissions throughout their production chains, or that implement corporate social responsibility standards for social reporting and international reporting purposes (e.g., GRI, Ethos, Global Compact, among others).

For further information, please contact: mobilidadec3@gmail.com

REGISTRATION FORM

- a. **Organization Name:** BMS Rastreamento
- b. **Contact Person:** Sirlei Roieski
- c. **Address:** Florianópolis, Santa Catarina, Brazil
- d. **E-mail:** sirlei@bmsrastreamento.com.br
- e. **Mobile Phone:** (48) 99166-3332
- f. **Date:** January 2022

QUESTIONS

1. How does motor vehicle tracking technology work?

A: A tracking module is installed in the vehicle to capture telematics and GPS positioning data. The information is transmitted via GPRS to our servers every 30 seconds. Monitoring is subsequently performed through mobile applications and web-based platforms.

2. Is it possible to calculate the CO₂ generated from the kilometers traveled by a specific vehicle model?

A: CO₂ emissions are calculated by dividing the distance traveled by the volume of fuel consumed, regardless of the vehicle model, thereby obtaining the fuel consumption rate in km/L. We provide fuel consumption reports that calculate averages for each refueling event, provided that the

information is entered manually or uploaded through fuel consumption files (fuel card records). A sample report is attached.

3. Is it possible to calculate the CO₂ generated from the kilometers traveled by a specific vehicle model?

Emissions Example: $50 \times 0.82 \times 0.75 \times 3.7 = 114$ kg CO₂-eq per week.

CO₂ emissions are calculated by dividing the distance traveled by the volume of fuel consumed, regardless of vehicle model, resulting in a fuel consumption rate expressed in km/L. The platform provides fuel consumption reports that calculate average values for each refueling event, either through manual entry or by uploading fuel transaction files.

Because the report is generated in Excel format, an emissions formula may be incorporated. For example, if a vehicle consumes one tank of gasoline (50 liters) per week and travels 500 km per week, corresponding to a fuel efficiency of 10 km/L, the resulting greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions would be:

Emissions: $50 \times 0.82 \times 0.75 \times 3.7 = 114$ kg CO₂-eq per week.

A sample report is attached.

4. What is the source of this calculation?

A: See the data provided by the Tropical Silviculture Laboratory:

https://esalqlastrop.com.br/capa.asp?pi=calculadora_emissoes

Research funded by the Rio de Janeiro State Research Support Foundation (FAPERJ), in partnership with the Incubator of the National Laboratory for Scientific Computing (LNCC/MCTI).

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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For further information, please contact: mobilidadec3@gmail.com

REGISTRATION FORM

a. Organization Name: Information Technology Department, Catholic University of Petrópolis (UCP)

b. Contact Person: Prof. Fabio Licht

c. Address: Av. Barão de Amazonas, 124 – Centro, Petrópolis, RJ, 25685-100, Brazil

d. E-mail: fabio.licht@ucp.br

e. Telephone: +55 24 2244-4130

f. Date: September 2022

QUESTIONS

1. In your opinion, is the Mobility C3 digital platform technically feasible?

Yes

If yes, briefly explain the fundamental activities required to make the platform viable.

Develop a sensor-based system using the Arduino Uno platform and appropriate sensors to measure CO₂ emissions from vehicle exhaust systems. These sensors can be acquired commercially. The Arduino kit would need to be assembled within a protective enclosure. High-temperature-resistant sensors installed in the exhaust outlet or after the catalytic converter may involve relatively high costs.

However, developing a dedicated monitoring device may be expensive, potentially reaching approximately R\$ 1,800.00.

The assembled system would require extensive testing over a period of at least three months to minimize errors, while six months of testing would be considered ideal.

The project could be implemented in three phases:

Phase 1: Interface development.

Phase 2: Testing and validation.

Phase 3: Calibration and iterative improvement through trial-and-error procedures.

The interface would require the use of Google APIs to display and process collected data, with GPS services continuously active.

An alternative is the OBD2 device, which performs diagnostics of the engine and electrical systems while displaying information through a mobile application. Although numerous OBD2 applications are available, not all are compatible with every OBD2 device. Therefore, for fleet monitoring purposes, it would be necessary to acquire standardized devices recommended by the same software developer.

In either case, the data obtained from both Arduino-based systems and OBD2 devices would need to be integrated into a cloud-based platform to calculate vehicle-specific indicators such as distance traveled, CO₂ emissions, and the number of trees required for carbon offsetting.

2. What are the advantages and disadvantages of the OBD2 sensor for vehicle diagnostics and CO₂ emission measurements?

Among its advantages, OBD2-based systems provide access to a wide range of vehicle performance variables. The combination of an OBD2 device and a compatible application enables users to monitor vehicle operating conditions in real time through Bluetooth or Wi-Fi connectivity.

One of the primary limitations of OBD2 systems is the dependence on compatible applications for specific vehicles.

Additional disadvantages include installation difficulties in certain vehicle models (e.g., Fiat Palio), challenges associated with user installation and testing procedures, and compatibility limitations related to vehicle manufacturing year. Vehicles manufactured before 2005 generally do not support standardized OBD2 protocols. Consequently, only vehicles produced from 2006 onward are typically suitable for generic OBD2 devices.

3. Why is the development of a prototype based on an Arduino Uno board and CO₂ probes not recommended for the Mobility C3 Project?

The Arduino Uno board receives information from sensors (such as CO₂ probes) installed in the vehicle's exhaust system. However, the development, calibration, validation, and long-term reliability testing of such equipment may significantly increase project costs and complexity.

4. What alternatives exist for measuring CO₂ emissions from motor vehicles?

Many modern vehicles already include manufacturer-provided applications capable of monitoring and estimating CO₂ emissions. Since approximately 2015, a significant proportion of vehicles have incorporated systems capable of providing emissions-related information.

Similarly, many automatic-transmission vehicles include fuel consumption and emissions monitoring functions.

However, a dedicated software solution would still be required to aggregate and integrate these data into a cloud-based platform.

5. Is Google Timeline a viable tool for the Mobility C3 Project?

Google provides a variety of highly capable digital tools. Google Timeline, for example, records and stores historical information regarding the routes traveled by an individual or vehicle over time.

6. If Google Timeline is viable, is it possible to develop a data capture tool capable of collecting Google Timeline information and storing data related to distance traveled, CO₂ emissions, and carbon offsetting requirements?

The system would require extensive testing over at least three months, with six months considered ideal.

Implementation would involve three stages:

Phase 1: Interface development.

Phase 2: Testing and validation.

Phase 3: Calibration and iterative refinement.

The interface would require integration with Google APIs, while GPS services would remain continuously active.

7. If feasible, is it possible to store data from an entire vehicle fleet for monitoring purposes?

Yes, by utilizing cloud-based services such as Google Cloud and related technologies.

8. Are there alternative tools available on the market that provide functionality similar to Google Timeline?

What are these alternatives?

9. What would be the minimum estimated time required to develop the technology described above?

The assembled system would require extensive testing over a minimum period of three months. A six-month testing period would be preferable to ensure reliability and accuracy.

10. What is the estimated cost of developing the technology described above?

The development of such a platform may involve substantial financial investment.

Research funded by the Rio de Janeiro State Research Support Foundation (FAPERJ), in partnership with the Incubator of the National Laboratory for Scientific Computing (LNCC/MCTI).

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

FEASIBILITY OF DEVELOPING THE DIGITAL PLATFORM FOR THE Mobility C3 PROJECT

Preliminary Version – Subject to Revision No. 00 / November 2022

REGISTRATION FORM

a. Organization Name: 11 Tec – Department of Computer Engineering, Catholic University of Petrópolis

b. Contact Person: Prof. Mozart – Computer Science Professor, UCP

c. Address: Av. Barão de Amazonas, 124 – Centro, Petrópolis, RJ, 25685-100, Brazil

d. E-mail: rsermeno@google.com

f. Date: October 2022

QUESTIONS

1. Which platform does Google recommend for the Mobility C3 platform?

I suggest using the Heroku platform.

3. How does this platform work?

It is recommended because it offers a free usage tier without time limitations. Charges apply only after a certain volume of data and usage is exceeded.

5. What could serve as the platform's storage infrastructure?

Storage could be implemented through a combination of mobile devices and the Heroku platform.

AWS is a robust platform; however, its free tier is generally limited to one year. Similarly, Google's cloud services typically provide free access only for a limited introductory period.

6. If Heroku is a viable solution for the Mobility C3 Project, is it possible to create a mobile data collection system capable of storing distance traveled, CO₂ emissions, and tree compensation data?

The proposed procedure would be as follows:

- a. Design the application screens. The prototype architecture would then be developed based on these interface designs.
- b. Register vehicle information, including manufacturer, year, fuel type, and factory-standard CO₂ emissions.
- c. Configure the mobile device to use NFC tags installed in the vehicle. Upon entering the vehicle, the user would activate the entry NFC tag to start tracking. Upon exiting, the user would activate the exit NFC tag to terminate data collection.
- d. Develop an administrative website to monitor data transmitted from mobile devices. Each mobile device would function as a client within the system. The platform would display indicators such as distance traveled, CO₂ emissions, and the number of trees required or effectively planted for compensation.

Note: The mobile device collects route data and transmits the information to the server (e.g., Heroku). Tabular data are generally less expensive to implement than graphical visualizations. As the number of features, data fields, and interface elements increases, so does the architectural complexity and cost.

- e. Implement a simple access-control mechanism within the platform.

Note: A dedicated technical professional should be responsible for maintaining the website and generating monitoring reports.

- f. System testing may be conducted through a parallel testing application developed specifically to validate and maintain the platform. Although this approach increases costs because it effectively requires two systems operating simultaneously, it provides a substantially higher level of reliability and security. Examples include national examination systems, aircraft onboard systems, and banking applications.

7. If feasible, what would be the cost of this service for a single vehicle?

[No response provided.]

Ricardo Braun
Mobilidade C3 Project
FAPERJ

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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For further information, please contact: mobilidadec3@gmail.com

REGISTRATION FORM

a. Organization Name: Ministry of Interior

b. Contact Person: Lucas Zefi

c. Address: Belgium

d. E-mail: —

e. Mobile Phone: +32 472 33 50 72

f. Date: November 2022

QUESTIONS

1. Does your organization develop software applications?

Yes.

2. The Mobility C3 Platform is intended to monitor motor vehicles and calculate CO₂ emissions. The platform could operate in a manner similar to Google Maps. What would be the estimated cost of developing such a platform in Belgium?

The overall development cost is estimated to range between **EUR 60,000.00** and **EUR 100,000.00**.

3. What would be the estimated time required to develop a prototype of the Mobility C3 Platform?

Approximately one month or less.

4. How long would it take to develop the final version of the Mobility C3 application?

The development of a fully operational version of the application would require approximately **10 to 15 months**. Extensive testing, calibration, validation, and iterative improvements would be necessary throughout the development process.

5. What would be a viable strategy for developing this application?

One possible approach would be to establish partnerships with Information Technology companies. Such organizations could finance the development costs in exchange for an equity stake or a percentage participation in the project.

Ricardo Braun
Mobilidade C3 Project
FAPERJ

ANNEX III - 2

Logbooks

Vehicle 1 - Suzuki Gran Vitara 4X4

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO							
PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3							
Suzuki / Gran Vitara 1.6 / 2001		KILOMETRAGEM			EMISSÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	Nº ÁRVORES	ha
18-Mar-22	G	146866	146914	48	9,6	0,0582	0,0001
19-Mar-22	G	146914	146914	0	0	0,0000	0,0000
20-Mar-22	G	146914	146914	0	0	0	0
21-Mar-22	G	146914	146914	0	0	0	0
22-Mar-22	G	146914	146928	14	2,8	0,0170	0,0000
23-Mar-22	G	146928	146928	0	0	0,0000	0,0000
24-Mar-22	G	146928	146937	9	1,8	0,0109	0,0000
25-Mar-22	G	146937	146944	7	1,4	0,0085	0,0000
26-Mar-22	G	146944	146944	0	0	0,0000	0,0000
27-Mar-22	G	146944	146954	10	2	0,0121	0,0000
28-Mar-22	G	146954	146954	0	0	0,0000	0,0000
29-Mar-22	G	146954	146954	0	0	0,0000	0,0000
30-Mar-22	G	146954	146954	0	0	0,0000	0,0000
31-Mar-22	G	146954	146963	9	1,8	0,0109	0,0000
1-Apr-22	G	146963	146966	3	0,6	0,0036	0,0000
		TOTAL		100	20	0,1212	0,0002

Vehicle 2 - Fiat Palio

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO							
PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3							
FIAT PALIO ELX Flex 1.4, 8v, FLEX, 2016		KILOMETRAGEM			EMISSÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D / GS)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	Nº ÁRVORES	Ha
15-Mar-22	G	48733	48778	45	7,65	0,0464	0,0001
16-Mar-22	G	48778	48778	0	0	0,0000	0,0000
17-Mar-22	G	48778	48808	30	5,1	0,0309	0,0001
18-Mar-22	G	48808	48821	13	2,21	0,0134	0,0000
19-Mar-22	G	48821	48841	20	3,4	0,0206	0,0000
20-Mar-22	G	48841	48852	11	1,87	0,0113	0,0000
21-Mar-22	G	48852	48883	31	5,27	0,0319	0,0001
22-Mar-22	G	48883	48920	37	6,29	0,0381	0,0001
23-Mar-22	G	48920	48949	29	4,93	0,0299	0,0001
24-Mar-22	G	48949	48957	8	1,36	0,0082	0,0000
25-Mar-22	G	48957	48970	13	2,21	0,0134	0,0000
26-Mar-22	G	48970	48991	21	3,57	0,0216	0,0000
27-Mar-22	G	48991	49001	10	1,7	0,0103	0,0000
28-Mar-22	G	49001	49038	37	6,29	0,0381	0,0001
29-Mar-22	G	49038	49080	42	7,14	0,0433	0,0001
		TOTAL		347	69,4	0,4206	0,0007

Vehicle 3 - Renault Sandero

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO

PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3

RENAULT, SANDERO, 1.0 12 V, Expression, 2018, FLEX		KILOMETRAGEM			EMISSÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D / GS)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	ÁRVORES/MÊS	Floresta (ha)
14-Mar-22	G	35400	35400	0	0	0,0000	0,0000
15-Mar-22	G	35400	35480	80	7,2	0,0436	0,0001
16-Mar-22	G	35480	35500	20	1,8	0,0109	0,0000
17-Mar-22	G	35500	35500	0	0	0,0000	0,0000
18-Mar-22	G	35500	35530	30	2,7	0,0164	0,0000
19-Mar-22	G	35530	35550	20	1,8	0,0109	0,0000
20-Mar-22	G	35550	35575	25	2,25	0,0136	0,0000
21-Mar-22	G	35575	35575	0	0	0,0000	0,0000
22-Mar-22	G	35575	35575	0	0	0,0000	0,0000
23-Mar-22	G	35575	35650	75	6,75	0,0409	0,0001
24-Mar-22	G	35650	35693	43	3,87	0,0235	0,0000
25-Mar-22	G	35693	35722	29	2,61	0,0158	0,0000
26-Mar-22	G	35722	35864	142	12,78	0,0775	0,0001
27-Mar-22	G	35864	35864	0	0	0,0000	0,0000
28-Mar-22	G	35864	35864	0	0	0,0000	0,0000
		TOTAL		464	92,8	0,5624	0,0005

Vehicle 4 - Citroen Picasa

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO

PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3

Citroen Picasso Xsara 2003, 2.0, gasolina		KILOMETRAGEM			EMISSÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D / GS)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	Nº ÁRVORES	Ha
15-Mar-22	G	150418	150472	54	10,26	0,0622	0,0001
16-Mar-22	G	150472	150474	2	0,38	0,0023	0,0000
17-Mar-22	G	150474	150476	2	0,38	0,0023	0,0000
18-Mar-22	G	150476	150543	67	12,73	0,0772	0,0001
19-Mar-22	G	150543	150548	5	0,95	0,0058	0,0000
20-Mar-22	G	150548	150570	22	4,18	0,0253	0,0000
21-Mar-22	G	150570	150581	11	2,09	0,0127	0,0000
22-Mar-22	G	150581	150621	40	7,6	0,0461	0,0001
23-Mar-22	G	150621	150738	117	22,23	0,1347	0,0002
24-Mar-22	G	150738	150742	4	0,76	0,0046	0,0000
25-Mar-22	G	150742	150757	15	2,85	0,0173	0,0000
26-Mar-22	G	150757	150777	20	3,8	0,0230	0,0000
27-Mar-22	G	150777	150780	3	0,57	0,0035	0,0000
28-Mar-22	G	150780	150829	49	9,31	0,0564	0,0001
29-Mar-22	G	150829	150921	92	17,48	0,1059	0,0002
		TOTAL		503	100,6	0,6097	0,0011

Vehicle 5 - Citroen Cactus

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO

PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3

CITROEN CACTUS C4 SHINE 1.98, 170CV / 1598 - 2022		KILOMETRAGEM			EMISSÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA	
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	Nº ÁRVORES	Ha	
7-Mar-22	G	197	267	70	7,7	0,0467	0,0001	
14-Mar-22	G	267	407	140	15,4	0,0933	0,0002	
15-Mar-22	G	407	407	0	0	0,0000	0,0000	
16-Mar-22	G	407	407	0	0	0,0000	0,0000	
17-Mar-22	G	407	407	0	0	0,0000	0,0000	
18-Mar-22	G	407	407	0	0	0,0000	0,0000	
19-Mar-22	G	407	649	242	48,4	0,2933	0,0005	
20-Mar-22	G	649	660	11	2,2	0,0133	0,0000	
21-Mar-22	G	660	667	7	1,4	0,0085	0,0000	
22-Mar-22	G	667	671	4	0,8	0,0048	0,0000	
23-Mar-22	G	671	679	8	1,6	0,0097	0,0000	
24-Mar-22	G	679	921	242	48,4	0,2933	0,0005	
25-Mar-22	G	921	931	10	2	0,0121	0,0000	
26-Mar-22	G	931	931	0	0	0,0000	0,0000	
27-Mar-22	G	931	1003	72	14,4	0,0873	0,0002	
		TOTAL			736	134,6	0,8158	0,0015

Vehicle 6 - Renault Sandero 2013

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO

PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3

Renault/Sandero Exp 10 16V ano 2012 mod 2013 álcool/gasolina		KILOMETRAGEM			EMISSÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA	
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D / GS)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	Nº ÁRVORES	Ha	
16-Mar-22	G	109073	109112	39	6,24	0,0378	0,0001	
17-Mar-22	G	109112	109132	20	3,2	0,0194	0,0000	
18-Mar-22	G	109132	109132	0	0	0	0,0000	
19-Mar-22	G	109132	109155	23	3,68	0,0223	0,0000	
20-Mar-22	G	109132	109253	121	19,36	0,1173	0,0002	
21-Mar-22	G	109132	109306	174	27,84	0,1687	0,0003	
22-Mar-22	G	109253	109381	128	20,48	0,1241	0,0002	
23-Mar-22	G	109381	109479	98	15,68	0,0950	0,0002	
24-Mar-22	G	109479	109494	15	2,4	0,0145	0,0000	
25-Mar-22	G	109494	109523	29	4,64	0,0281	0,0001	
26-Mar-22	G	109523	109523	0	0	0,0000	0,0000	
27-Mar-22	G	109523	109539	16	2,56	0,0155	0,0000	
28-Mar-22	G	109539	109623	84	13,44	0,0815	0,0001	
29-Mar-22	G	109623	109623	0	0	0,0000	0,0000	
30-Mar-22	G	109623	109745	122	19,52	0,1183	0,0002	
		TOTAL			869	173,8	1,0533	0,0015

Vehicle 7 - Renault Orch

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO

PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3

Renault 1.6 / Orch, Camionete 4x2, 120cv, 2021		KILOMETRAGEM			EMISSÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	PRESERVAÇÃO DE FLORESTA NATIVA
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D / GS)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO2/Kg	Nº ÁRVORES	Ha
23-Apr-22	G	12625	12790	165	19,8	0,1200	0,0002
24-Apr-22	G	12790	12797	7	0,84	0,0051	0,0000
25-Apr-22	G	12797	13003	206	24,72	0,1498	0,0003
26-Apr-22	G	13003	13091	88	10,56	0,0640	0,0001
27-Apr-22	G	13091	13171	80	9,6	0,0582	0,0001
28-Apr-22	G	13171	13254	83	13,28	0,0805	0,0001
29-Apr-22	G	13254	13340	86	13,76	0,0834	0,0002
30-Apr-22	G	13340	13595	255	40,8	0,2473	0,0004
1-May-22	G	13595	13696	101	16,16	0,0979	0,0002
2-May-22	G	13696	13838	142	22,72	0,1377	0,0003
3-May-22	G	13838	13839	1	0,16	0,0010	0,0000
4-May-22	G	13839	13942	103	16,48	0,0999	0,0002
5-May-22	G	13942	13950	8	1,28	0,0078	0,0000
6-May-22	G	13950	14075	125	20	0,1212	0,0002
7-May-22	G	14075	14192	117	18,72	0,1135	0,0002
		TOTAL		1567	313,4	1,8994	0,0025

ANNEX III - 3

Forest Partnership Questionnaire

Pesquisa financiada pela Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado do Rio de Janeiro ([FAPERJ](#)), em parceria com a Incubadora do Laboratório Nacional de Computação Científica ([LNCC / MCTI](#)).

CARBON MARKET

REGISTRATION OF FORESTRY PARTNERS FOR THE CARBON MARKET OF THE Mobility C3 PROJECT

Version No. 00 / April 2022

The primary objective of the Mobility C3 Project is to monitor CO₂ emissions from motor vehicles and vehicle fleets for ecological compensation purposes, as an urgent measure to combat climate change and its impacts, in accordance with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 13 (SDG 13).

To achieve this objective, we are establishing a network of forestry organizations, companies, and silvicultural enterprises interested in participating in the voluntary carbon market across the different Brazilian biomes.

The goal is to offset the CO₂ emissions of companies that have sustainability policies aimed at achieving net-zero carbon emissions throughout their production chains, or that implement corporate social responsibility standards for social reporting and international reporting purposes (e.g., GRI, Ethos, Global Compact, among others).

To register your organization, company, or association, please complete the questionnaire below and send it to mobilidadec3@gmail.com.

REGISTRATION FORM

- a. **Organization Name:** PRIMA – Atlantic Forest and Sustainability
- b. **Contact Person:** Ricardo Harduim
- c. **Address:** Av. Roberto Silveira, 349/401, Icaraí, Niterói, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
- d. **E-mail:** harduim.ricardo@gmail.com
- e. **Mobile Phone:** (21) 99962-1922
- f. **Legal Registration (CNPJ/CPF):** 06.034.803/0001-43

QUESTIONS

1. Does your organization follow any Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations 2030 Agenda?

Yes ___ No

If yes, which SDG(s)?

SDG 13 – Climate Action

2. Area(s) of Activity of Your Organization/Company (select more than one if applicable)

Tree planting for carbon sequestration/carbon neutrality

___ Rehabilitation of degraded areas (PRAD)

___ Reforestation for economic purposes

___ Forest restoration

___ Silviculture

___ Production of native biome seedlings

___ Commercial seedling production

Academic research

___ Sustainable agriculture

Other (please specify)

Specification: Climate Environmental Education

For Organizations/Companies Engaged in Carbon Sequestration/Neutralization Activities Only

3. If your organization/company is engaged in tree planting for carbon sequestration/carbon neutrality, what is the value in Brazilian Reais (R\$) for the amount of carbon offset?

50 kg: R\$ _____

100 kg: R\$ _____

200 kg: R\$ _____

300 kg: R\$ _____

500 kg: R\$ _____

1,000 kg: R\$ _____

More than 2 metric tons: R\$ _____

4. What is the value in Brazilian Reais (R\$) of a single planted tree seedling?

R\$ 50.00

5. What is the value in Brazilian Reais (R\$) for one hundred planted tree seedlings?

R\$ 5,000.00

6. What is the value in Brazilian Reais (R\$) for one thousand planted tree seedlings?

R\$ 50,000.00

For All Organizations/Companies

7. In which Brazilian biome(s) does your organization operate? (Select more than one if applicable)

Amazon

Cerrado

Caatinga

Atlantic Forest

Pantanal

Pampa

8. Does your organization work with native species from the biome in which it operates?

Yes No

9. Does your organization work with exotic species for commercial purposes?

Yes No

If yes, please specify the species:

10. What is the estimated weekly production capacity of forest seedlings by your organization or partner organizations/companies?

50

100

200

300

500

1,000

5,000

10,000

More than 10,000

Note: Depending on site conditions, planting 10,000 trees in a single week would require the establishment of a large workforce and the implementation of an intensive operational scheme.

11. Are there plans to increase seedling production?

Yes No

If yes, please specify quantitatively the expected increase, the anticipated timeline, and the projected implementation date:

12. How many partners, employees, and/or volunteer collaborators does your organization/company have?

Number of Employees: _____

Partners: **10**

Volunteer Collaborators: **10**

13. Social Participation

How many individuals from communities surrounding your organization/company are involved in seedling production and/or planting, forest management, forest protection, or related activities?

14. Does your property contain degraded area(s) that could be reforested with species native to the biome?

Yes No

If yes, what is the approximate size of the degraded area?

_____ ha

15. If no, are there degraded areas adjacent to your property that could be reforested?

What is the approximate size of the degraded area in the surrounding area?

_____ ha

16. Does your company utilize forest insurance?

Yes No

If yes, please specify the type of insurance:

ANNEX III – 4

Questionnaire for ISE Companies

Questionnaire sent to several corporate companies.

Mobility C3

CARBON OFFSETTING

Carbon offsetting is an urgent measure to combat climate change and its impacts, in accordance with the recommendations of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 13 (SDG 13).

Mobilidade C3® is a research and innovation project aimed at developing a three-in-one digital platform capable of measuring, in real time, the distance traveled (km), the amount of CO₂ emitted according to the vehicle type and brand during a journey, and the number of trees required to offset the emissions generated by that trip.

We are also establishing partnerships with non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and forestry companies across the various Brazilian biomes to provide carbon offsetting services through tree planting and the conservation of native forests.

Based on this initiative, we would like to know whether your company is interested in measuring and offsetting the CO₂ emissions generated by its vehicle fleet.

If so, we kindly request that you complete the information below and send it to our e-mail address: mobilidadec3@gmail.com.

We appreciate your time and interest.

Sincerely,

Ricardo Braun
Project Coordinator

P.S.

For additional information about the Mobility C3 Project, please click here: (FAPERJ) (LNCC / MCTI).

Research funded by the Rio de Janeiro State Research Support Foundation (FAPERJ), in partnership with the Incubator of the National Laboratory for Scientific Computing (LNCC/MCTI).

ANNEX III – 5

Document Detailing the Formulas for Calculating CO₂ Emissions, Number of Trees Required, Preserved Forest Area, and Carbon Credits.

R. Braun - Projeto Mobilidade C3 FAPERJ / Incubadora LNCC / 11 Tech

FÓRMULAS PARA CÁLCULO DE KM, EMISSÃO DE CO₂, NÚMERO DE ÁRVORES E HECTARES DE FLORESTA

Versão preliminar nº 01 12/01/23

FÓRMULAS PARA CÁLCULO DE KM, EMISSÃO DE CO₂, NÚMERO DE ÁRVORES E HECTARES DE FLORESTA

1. Introdução

Cálculo realizado com o aplicativo Excel (Microsoft) ou Numbers (Apple), para a Plataforma Mobilidade C3, considerando a quilometragem (Km) percorrida pelo veículo, a emissão de CO₂ do veículo monitorado, o número de árvores a serem plantadas para compensação ecológica, e os hectares (Ha) a serem preservados de floresta.

Os dados de medição de distância percorrida (Km), emissão de CO₂ e cálculo do número de árvores a serem plantadas e/ou floresta a ser preservada, baseia-se nos resultados do laboratório offline realizado em 2022 com diversos veículos voluntários.

Importante notar que árvores em uma floresta não são computadores per se. O sequestro de carbono é um processo que depende de diversos indicadores como condições de nutrientes dos solos, variação da temperatura, insolação, regime de ventos e chuvas, dentre outros, que variam de acordo como as condições climáticas locais e globais. Portanto os números de sequestro de carbono são estimativas médias de autores, e não números absolutos.

2. Métodos

Cálculo de Km:

- GPS e Google (ex. Google Tracking, Google Timeline, Distance Matrix API.)
- Odômetro manual (ex. Usuário insere manualmente no aplicativo a quilometragem inicial e final).

Cálculo de CO₂:

O cálculo baseia-se na emissão padrão do veículo monitorado (ex. Suzuki Gran Vitara, ano 2001 = 200 gr / Km).

Para cada veículo insere-se o padrão (ex. Suzuki Gran Vitara, ano 2001 = 200 gr / Km; Citroen Cactus, ano 2022 = 111 gr / Km, outros).

Cálculo de Nº de árvores

Para a quantidade de CO₂ emitido tem-se o número de árvores a serem plantadas.

Preliminarmente usaremos o valor de 198 Kg sequestrado por árvore plantada durante 20 anos.

Cálculo de Hectares de Floresta

1 hectare de floresta sequestra aproximadamente 75,6 toneladas de carbono no período entre 20 a 40 anos.

Cálculo de Créditos de Carbono

As organizações / empresas de compensação de carbono estão trabalhando com a variável 'créditos de carbono. Um crédito de carbono equivale a 1 tonelada de CO₂.

R. Braun - Projeto Mobilidade C3 FAPERJ / Incubadora LNCC / 11 Tech

3. Memória de Cálculo

As tabela a seguir, Excel ou Numbers, resumem os cálculos necessários para cada veículo monitorado individualmente. No exemplo o veículo Suzuki Gran Vitara, 1.6., cuja emissão é de 200 g / CO₂ / Km.

DIÁRIO DE BORDO DO VEÍCULO / SIMULADO									
PROJETO MOBILIDADE C3									
Suzuki / Gran Vitara 1.6 / 2001		KILOMETRAGEM			EMISSÃO	COMPENSAÇÃO	FLORESTA NATIVA	CRÉDITOS DE CARBONO	
DATA	COMBUSTÍVEL (G / A / D)	Km Inicial	Km Final	Total Dia	CO ₂ /Kg	Nº ÁRVORES	ha	ton	
18-Mar-22	G	146856	146914	48	9,6	0,0485	0,0001	0,0096	

Tabela 1. Diário de Bordo em excel / Numbers.

PARÂMETRO	COLUNA	FÓRMULA	CÁLCULO
Km Quilometragem Total Dia	E6	$\sum D6 - C6 = E6$	D6 Somatório Km final - C6 KM inicial = E6
CO ₂ / Kg (Suzuki 200 gr / Km)	F6	$E6 \times 0,2 = F6$	Constante do Gran Vitara 200gr/CO ₂ por Km ou 0,20 KJ / CO ₂ / Km $E6 \times 0,2 = F6$
Árvores (1 compensa 198 Kg CO ₂)	G6	$F6 + 198 \text{ CO}_2/\text{Km} = G6$	Valor médio: 1 árvore compensa 198 Kg CO ₂ .
Floresta Preservada (Hectares)	H6	$G6 + 550 \text{ (árvores)} = H6$	Valor médio: 1 hectare de floresta
Crédito de Carbono (Toneladas)	I6	$F6 : 1000 = I6$	I6 corresponde ao valor em toneladas de carbono, para se chegar a 1 crédito de carbono (1 Tonelada de carbono)

Tabela 2. Cálculo por coluna.

Obs. De acordo com a literatura e os avanços das pesquisas mundiais sobre sequestro de carbono (carbon sink) em regiões tropicais, os números podem variar a medida que o tempo avança.

ANNEX III – 6

Digital screen of Mobility C3 application (TRL7)

Business Model and TRL7 Certification

ATESTADO DE MATURIDADE TECNOLÓGICA (TRL)

ATESTAMOS que o **Mobilidade C3** é uma plataforma digital de monitoramento ambiental de veículos individuais ou frota de veículos automotores, emissão de gases de efeito estufa (CO₂) e a compensação de carbono, desenvolvida pela empresa **11Tech** sob contrato de prestação de serviços do pesquisador Ricardo Augusto Braun, Programa Doutor Empreendedor da Fundação de Amparo a Pesquisa do Rio de Janeiro (FAPERJ) Edital 10/2021.

O Nível de Maturidade da Tecnologia (NMT), ou conhecido como TRL (The Technology Readiness Level), é uma sistemática métrica, com nove etapas, desenvolvida pela *National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA)* [Administração Nacional de Aeronáutica e Espaço dos Estados Unidos] que permite ordenar as novas tecnologias, com os objetivos fundamentais de possibilitar a comparação com outras e de facilitar o entendimento sobre o estágio atual de desenvolvimento.

Com base no expertise em Tecnologia da Informação (TI) da empresa 11 Tech, arquiteta e programadora do aplicativo Mobilidade C3 versão 0.1, definiu-se, no seu atual estágio o Nível de Maturidade Tecnológico **TRL 7**, com vistas a alcançar o Nível **TRL 8**.

Petrópolis, 11 de Junho de 2024.

Prof. Mozar Baptista da Silva (M.Sc.)

11 Tech

Assinatura

Prof. Mozar Baptista da Silva (M.Sc.): Diretor da empresa de TI 11TECH: <https://www.11tech.com.br/>. Possui graduação em Bacharelado em Informática pela Universidade Federal Fluminense(1998) e mestrado em Computação pela Universidade Federal Fluminense (1999). Atualmente é professor titular da Universidade Católica de Petrópolis, professor titular do Instituto Superior de Tecnologia (FAETEC/IST) e Coordenador/Gerente da área de Desenvolvimento da ALLEN Rio Serviços e Comércio de Produtos de Informática LTDA. Tem experiência na área de Ciência da Computação, com ênfase em Metodologia e Técnicas da Computação.CV Lattes: <http://lattes.cnpq.br/9627783851815804>